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A.C.

**UNRAVELING THE COMPLEX DYNAMICS
BETWEEN WATER QUALITY AND THE MICROBIAL
COMMUNITIES OF A SUBTROPICAL LAKE: A
SEQUENCING APPROACH TO THE INSIGHTS OF
THE BIOGEOCHEMICAL CYCLES.**

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Sin otro particular, aprovecho la oportunidad para enviarle un cordial saludo.

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“Science and everyday life cannot and should not be separated”

Rosalind Franklin.

Summary

The municipality of Tlajomulco de Zúñiga, in the state of Jalisco, Mexico, is home to Lake Cajititlán, a shallow, endorheic, subtropical lake. Due mainly to untreated or partially treated wastewater discharged into the lake from municipal wastewater treatment plants, and the excessive use of fertilizers in agriculture in the basin this water body suffers under anthropogenic eutrophication problems. As a result of these sources of nutrient pollution, the lake's water quality and ecological integrity have been significantly affected, leading this reservoir to a hypereutrophic state, triggering a massive phytoplankton bloom that has generated several episodes of fish mortality during the rainy season due to oxygen depletion (hypoxia) at night caused by the respiration process by these primary consumers, from 2013 to date, and mainly during or immediately after the rainy season. Therefore, in this thesis work, we focused on characterizing the microbial communities of this lake during the rainy season using targeted metagenomic sequencing (16S and 18S rRNA) and shotgun sequencing to reveal the main physicochemical and environmental variables influencing the dynamics of microbial communities in response to anthropogenic pollutant inputs, to provide a scientific basis for protecting the aquatic ecosystem's stability. First, we describe the changes in the phytoplankton community in Lake Cajititlán during the rainy season by sequencing 16S and 18S rRNA amplicons, as well as the association between these changes and the lake basin's physicochemical water quality and environmental characteristics. The results indicate that nutrient carryover due to runoff during the rainy season causes rapid changes in the physicochemical parameters, and important variations in the composition of the phytoplankton community. *Planktothrix* and *Cylindrospermopsis* (16S rRNA) were found to be the dominant genera in the cyanobacterial community, whereas the Chlorophyceae, Chrysophyceae, and Trebouxiophyceae (18S rRNA) classes were the most abundant in the microalgae community. Furthermore, possible relationships between the TN:TP ratio and the relative abundances of specific populations of cyanobacteria and microalgae were discovered. The evidence found showed that the death of fish in Lake Cajititlán could be related mainly by hypoxia, caused by the rapid depletion of DO levels as a result of phytoplankton blooms. These blooms were the result of nutrients entering the lake through direct urban wastewater discharges and agricultural runoff during the rainy season. Using high-throughput 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing and a functional inference approach (PICRUSt2), the temporal

dynamics of bacterial communities within Lake Cajititlán and their associated genes with biogeochemical cycles of nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and carbon during the rainy season were investigated. In addition, the influence of physicochemical and environmental variables on these dynamics and their microbial functional profiles were also analyzed. The main findings of this section of the thesis were that the nutrient load that reaches Lake Cajititlán modifies the physicochemical parameters, which in turn impact the taxonomic and functional structure of the bacterial communities. Genes associated with biogeochemical cycles were more abundant at the beginning of the rainy season and when the lowest levels of DO were detected. The last section of this thesis focuses on understanding Lake Cajititlán's water quality from physicochemical variables and shotgun metagenomic data. The most relevant results of this section indicate that most of the physicochemical variables analyzed (DO, pH, Secchi disk, NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , BGA-PC, TP, and Chlorophyll-*a*) exceed recommended criteria for the protection of aquatic life. These parameters are altered by point and non-point pollutant sources reaching the lake during hot-dry and wet seasons. Likewise, genetic evidence from microbial communities reveals that anthropogenic sources of nutrients that reached the lake altered genes involved in the metabolism of nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and carbon, resulting of excess of microorganisms that can thrive in environments with high nutrient content and low dissolved oxygen typically found in hypertrophic lakes.

Keywords: subtropical lake, hypereutrophic lake, fish kill, physicochemical and environmental parameters, 16S and 18s rRNA gene sequencing, shotgun sequencing, pathogenic bacteria, biogeochemical cycling.

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GENERAL INTRODUCTION

General introduction

Lake Cajititlán is a small endorheic, subtropical, shallow lake located in the municipality of Tlajomulco de Zúñiga, Jalisco, Mexico (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). The lake represents a symbol of identity and an essential source of income for the inhabitants of the municipality of Tlajomulco and its surroundings, particularly for the local riverside communities, since activities such as tourism, recreation and fishing depend on it. Such a symbol of identity and source of income is at risk of severe damage and degradation, since several actors negatively affect the conservation of the lake and its ecosystem, such as the creation of new housing developments, overexploitation of local aquifers, wastewater discharges directly to the lake and agricultural returns (Caro-Becerra *et al.*, 2017).

Agriculture is the main economic activity in the Lake's Cajititlán basin; nevertheless, due to the excessive use of fertilizers, these agricultural practices are one of the primary sources of nutrient pollution, resulting in the process of eutrophication that is exacerbated by the endorheic nature of this reservoir (de Anda *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, insufficient capacity of municipal wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), absence of tertiary treatment to remove nutrients, and the endorheic condition of the waterbody leads to rapid nutrient enrichment of this reservoir particularly during rainy season (de Anda *et al.*, 2019, 2022). As a result of this contamination, the lake has become hypereutrophic, triggering a phytoplankton bloom which has resulted in several episodes of massive fish kills, particularly between June and October from 2013 to date, mainly during or immediately after the rainy season (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2018; de Anda *et al.*, 2019). These kill events are attributed to the high rates of dissolved oxygen consumption by primary consumers (i.e., San Francisco Bay, Lake Erie, backwaters of Puducherry Southeast coast of India, Chamo Lake Ethiopia) during the night due to the respiration process and have led to episodes of oxygen depletion (anoxia/hypoxia) (Wolf *et al.*, 2017; Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2018, 2020; Mishra *et al.*, 2022; Reddythota and Teferi, 2022; SFEI, 2022).

One of the most critical climatological features of tropical and subtropical regions is heavy rainfall, which causes significant nutrient runoff from agricultural areas to surface waters. Additionally, due to the fact that rainwater mixes with sanitary water in the urban drainage, the

capacity of the wastewater treatment plants considerably exceeds its treatment capacity during the rainy season and a significant amount of raw wastewater is discharged directly on the lake. On the other hand, high temperatures and nutrient enrichment that occur throughout the year in the lake waters make it highly susceptible to cultural eutrophication when compared to temperate environments, where spring and summer are the seasons in which the productivity of phytoplankton increases (Cunha *et al.*, 2013; Thornton, 1987; Rast and Thornton, 1996). Although rainfall and temperature can significantly alter the physical, chemical, and biological features of lakes, their water quality is the result of a complex set of among multiple interactions among physical, chemical and biological parameters, including the natural and anthropogenic inputs of pollutants, climatic conditions (such as temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, sunshine duration, and rainfall), the hydrodynamics of the lake, and *in-situ* biological and chemical processes (such as microbial metabolism), among others (Niencheski and Windom, 1994). Furthermore, changes in lake water quality cause alterations in the structure and functions of the microbial communities that regulate biogeochemical processes such as the sulfur, nitrogen, phosphorus, and carbon cycles (Liu *et al.*, 2018; Wang *et al.*, 2018; Yao *et al.*, 2018); similarly, the metabolic activity of microorganisms has a significant impact on lake water quality via diverse biogeochemical processes (Hupfer and Lewandowski, 2008).

Understanding the interactions between water quality and biogeochemical processes within lake ecosystems is still limited (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2022). The rapid microbial changes in subtropical lakes, mostly brought on by rainfall and surface runoff, pose an even greater difficulty in understanding the microbial community structure and their corresponding biochemistry (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). As a result, more research is needed to understand how microbial metabolism and metabolic interactions drive biogeochemical changes at the ecosystem scale (Newton *et al.*, 2011; Graham *et al.*, 2016). Metagenomic approaches have been highly developed and have proven to be effective in studying microbial ecology and facilitate understanding of the links between microbial dynamics and biogeochemical processes in nature (Mackelprang *et al.*, 2011; Fierer *et al.*, 2012; Llorens-Marès *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, microbial metagenomics has proven invaluable in informing remediation strategies for impaired ecosystems (Bowker, 2007; Steven *et al.*, 2012). Lack of comprehensive understanding of the microbial community can severely restrict understanding of what drives species distribution, environmental sustainability, and ecological

interactions, all of which can negatively influence informed conservation decision-making (Guisan *et al.*, 2013).

Most of the previous studies have not explored the connection between the physicochemical and environmental factors impacting lake water quality and the structure and functional variations of the microbial communities (Wilburn *et al.*, 2019; Oyewusi *et al.*, 2020; Ahmad *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, most of the existing metagenomic studies have been conducted in temperate and deep-water sources, with a metagenomic focus on a single gene. Other studies have analyzed one, two, or no biogeochemical cycles, and there are no studies that have yet reported metagenomic data linked to physicochemical and environmental variables in a subtropical and hypereutrophic water body (Wilburn *et al.*, 2019; Wu *et al.*, 2019; Li *et al.*, 2020; Oyewusi *et al.*, 2020; Ahmad *et al.*, 2021). Thus, the objective of this study was to characterize the microbial communities of a hypereutrophic subtropical lake during the rainy season using shotgun and targeted metagenomic sequencing (16S and 18S rRNA gene regions) in order to reveal the primary physicochemical and environmental variables that influence the dynamics of the microbial community in response to anthropogenic pollutant inputs to provide a better understanding of the processes that lead to hypertrophic conditions of lakes located in subtropical regions.

Thesis outline

The thesis is divided into four chapters, three of which are scientific articles, and one is a literature review. The general conclusions and perspectives are presented at the end of the final chapter. In particular, Chapter I contextualizes the thesis topic. The chapter is divided into five parts. The first one presents an overview of lakes general aspects (origin, trophic status, and eutrophication). The second part describes the generalities of Lake Cajititlán (hydrology, physical characteristics, and pollution of the surface water). The third section presents a description of phytoplankton (cyanobacteria and cyanotoxins, and toxic effects produced by microcystin in fish). The following section outlines aquatic systems' major biogeochemical (carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur) cycles. The last part focuses on different metagenomic approaches, such as 16S and 18S rRNA gene sequencing and shotgun metagenomics; in addition, the phylogenetic analysis of communities by reconstruction of unobserved states (PICRUSt2) is contextualized.

Chapter II is focused on describing the changes in Lake Cajititlán's phytoplankton community during the rainy season and the association between these changes and the physicochemical quality of the water and the environmental parameters measured in the lake basin. The conclusions of this section indicate that the climatic fluctuations in the Lake Cajititlán region cause high seasonal surface runoff, rapid changes in water quality, and variations in the phytoplankton community composition. The information provided in this part supports the hypothesis that fish mortality in Lake Cajititlán is mainly due to hypoxia, which is induced by abrupt changes in water quality during the rainy season. This chapter's experimental analysis of phytoplankton communities was carried out using high-throughput 16S rRNA and 18S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing.

Chapter III presents an investigation of the temporal dynamics of bacterial communities within Lake Cajititlán and their genes associated with nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and carbon biogeochemical cycles during the rainy season using high-throughput 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing and a functional inference approach (PICRUSt). Furthermore, the influence of physicochemical and environmental variables on these microbial dynamics was also analyzed.

This chapter's main findings were that surface runoff carries a high load of nutrients to the lake during the rainy season, altering the bacterial communities and causing temporal variations in their composition and abundance. Furthermore, increased abundances of functional genes involved with diverse metabolic pathways of the nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur cycles were observed. The findings improved our understanding of the bidirectional interactions between bacterial communities and major biogeochemical processes in subtropical eutrophic lakes.

Chapter IV focuses on characterizing the water quality of Lake Cajititlán from physicochemical variables to shotgun metagenomic data. The conclusions of this section indicate that abiotic factors could influence the microbial communities of Lake Cajititlán, generating a surplus of microorganisms that can thrive under high amounts of nutrients and low dissolved oxygen, causing impairments in the lake limiting enough oxygen concentration to sustain aquatic life. In addition, genetic evidence from the microbial communities suggests that genes involved in nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and carbon metabolism were regulated by anthropogenic sources of nutrients that reached the lake from point and non-point sources.

CHAPTER I: LITERATURE REVIEW

The first section of this chapter presents an overview of the generalities of the lakes (A.1. origin, A.2. trophic status, A.3. eutrophication, and A.4. shallow and eutrophic lakes). The second section describes the generalities of Lake Cajititlán (B.1. hydrology, B.2. physical characteristics, and B.3. pollution of the surface water). The third section presents the generalities of phytoplankton (C.1. cyanobacteria and cyanotoxins, and C.2. toxic effects produced by microcystin in fish). The following fourth section outlines the D. major biogeochemical (carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur) cycles in aquatic systems. The last section focuses on different E. metagenomic approaches, such as 16S and 18S rRNA genes and shotgun metagenomics; in addition, PICRUST2 analysis is contextualized.

A. Generalities of the lakes

A lake is a body of water of considerable size, localized in a basin, that is surrounded by land apart from a river or other outlet that serves to feed or drain the lake (Purcell and Adam, 2012). Lakes lie on land and are not part of the ocean, and therefore are distinct from lagoons, and are also larger and deeper than ponds (pmfias, 2015). Natural lakes are generally found in mountainous areas, rift zones, and areas with ongoing glaciation. Most lakes have at least one natural outflow in the form of a river or stream, which maintain a lake's average level by allowing the drainage of excess water. Other lakes are found in endorheic basins. Some lakes do not have a natural outflow and lose water solely by evaporation or underground seepage or both. They are termed endorheic lakes. The majority of lakes on Earth are freshwater, and most lie in the Northern Hemisphere at higher latitudes. Canada, Finland, and Siberia contain most of the freshwater lakes (Seekell *et al.*, 2021).

In human society, lakes are traditionally undervalued resources. Nevertheless, basins where these water bodies are located serve various purposes and are ideal places for human settlement. Some of the examples of services that are obtained from the lakes are municipal drinking water supply, industrial water supply, navigation, power generation, recreational and commercial fishing, among other aesthetic recreational applications (Bhast and Qayoom, 2021). Furthermore, lake water is used for agricultural irrigation, canalization, and waste disposal (Gibbs and Hickey, 2012). These applications are clearly in conflict with the degradation of water caused by agricultural use as well as industrial and municipal waste disposal practices (Bhast and Qayoom,

2021). Thus, the management of lakes is often focused on resolving these conflicts (Ayres *et al.*, 1997).

Lake water quality is essential for the preservation of recreation and fishing, as well as the supply of municipal drinking water (Bhast and Qayoom, 2021). Lake water quality management often focuses on resolving conflicts related to water degradation caused by industrial and municipal waste disposal practices and agricultural use. Nowhere in the world has lake management been a completely successful endeavor. However, substantial progress has been achieved, particularly about waste emissions from regulated point sources (Macfarlane, 2022).

A.1. Origins of lakes

In geological terms lakes are ephemeral. They originate as a product of geological processes and end due to the loss of the ponding mechanism, by evaporation induced by changes in the hydrological balance, or by filling caused by sedimentation (Chapman, 1992). Hutchinson (1957) classified 11 primary lake types, further subdivided into 76 sub-categories, and evaluated the formation methods. Although a comprehensive study is beyond the scope of this thesis, a summary of the major categories of lake origin is provided below (Meybeck, 1995; Chandra, 2012).

Glacial lakes: lakes located in ice-scraped rocky basins, on or under the ice, frozen over by the ice. Glacial lakes are by far the most numerous in all mountainous areas, subarctic areas, and on Pleistocene surfaces. This category includes all the world's lakes that are cold-temperate and several lakes that are warm-temperate.

Tectonic lakes: Lakes formed by large-scale crustal movements that separate bodies of water from the sea. lakes created by the earth's tectonic faults, folding, or tilting. These types of lakes might be ancient.

Fluvial lakes: Lakes generated by river meandering in flood plains, such as oxbow and levee lakes, and lakes formed by fluvial damming induced by tributary sediment deposition.

Shoreline lakes: Lakes that are isolated from the ocean by spits that form due to sediment accumulation brought on by long-shore sediment flow, such as the coastal lakes in Egypt.

Volcanic lakes: lakes that form in craters and calderas, including those dammed due to volcanic activity.

A.2. Trophic state

Early limnologists such as Thienemann (1925, 1931) and Nauman (1932) introduced the concept of trophic status as a system of lake classification and it has been subject to continuous change (Vollenweider, 1968; Pourriot and Meybeck, 1995). The trophic status in a given water body is defined as the total weight of biomass at the time of measurement (Chapman, 1992). The trophic state index was proposed by Rober Carlson in 1977. It is one of the most widely used trophic indices and is used by the United States Environmental Protection Agency. This index is based on the use of the Secchi Disk to measure the level of transparency of the water through the lake's water column. This transparency determines the level of refraction of light through turbidity and the color presented by the volume of water, due to the effect of discharges of solids (suspended, volatile or sedimentable) or due to the formation of colloidal systems or complex solutions (Carlson, 1977). According to the US EPA, the Carlson index should only be used in lakes with relatively few rooted plants and sources of turbidity other than algae (EPA, 2006). The most widely used trophic state index for water bodies is proposed by the Organization for Economic Cooperation (OECD), which determines the level of eutrophication and its effects through three traditional trophic categories: total phosphorus (TP), chlorophyll-a and Secchi depth (OECD, 1982). In the following section, the classification of lakes according to their trophic level is presented in more detail.

A.3. Eutrophication

Eutrophication is the enrichment of surface waters with nutrients for plants that occur naturally and are normally associated with anthropogenic sources of nutrients (Huang *et al.*, 2014). Agriculture is one of the main factors in eutrophication of surface waters (Gomes de Quevedo *et al.*, 2016). Although both nitrogen and phosphorus contribute to eutrophication, the trophic status classification is usually based on the nutrient that represents a limitation. In most cases, the

limiting factor is phosphorus (Bruce, 2011). Although both nitrogen and phosphorus contribute to eutrophication, the trophic status classification is usually based on the nutrient that represents a limitation. In most cases, the limiting factor is phosphorus (Bruce, 2011). Although the effects of eutrophication, such as phytoplankton blooms, are easily visible, the eutrophication process is complex and offers quantification difficulties (Gomes de Quevedo *et al.*, 2016). The symptoms and effects of eutrophication are as follows: (Gomes de Quevedo *et al.*, 2016)

1. Increased production and biomass of phytoplankton-associated algae and macrophytes.
2. Modification of the characteristics of the habitat due to the transformation of the set of aquatic plants.
3. Production of toxins by certain cyanobacteria.
4. Deoxygenation of the water, especially at the end of phytoplankton's proliferation, normally leading to fish mortality.
5. Economic losses due to the modification of fish species, and mortality of fish.

The main anthropogenic causes of eutrophication processes can be: (Gomes de Quevedo *et al.*, 2016)

1. One of the oldest causes is the discharge of wastewater, which is rich in nutrients, contributing to the trophic change of the receiving water body.
2. Excessive use of fertilizers fundamentally generates water pollution through the contribution of nitrogen (in the form of nitrate salts and ammonium) and phosphorus (as phosphate).
3. Deforestation and erosion in agricultural soils influence the nutrient load since the runoff, passing through unprotected land, washes the fertile layer, taking nutrients with it.
4. The presence of environmental gases such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and sulfur oxides (SO_x), upon contact with atmospheric water, form nitrate and sulfate ions, which form soluble salts when they reach the soil with their cations, generating an impoverishment of said ions. These salts are easily dumped into bodies of water, giving rise to eutrophication.

According to different authors, there are various morphometric (depth, the margin of the basin, among others), chemical (hypolimnetic oxygen and nutrients) and biological (productivity, biomass, indicator species) characteristics that allow evaluating the effects of variations in the trophic states (Moreno-Arbeláez and Ramírez-Restrepo, 2010).

The classification of eutrophic lakes ranges from oligotrophic to hypereutrophic (OECD, 1982). In many shallow lakes, eutrophication may be shown by macrophyte growth rather than phytoplankton growth. However, the interaction of various factors, which collectively define the growth circumstances, determines how effectively the nutrients are utilized, and as a result, the overall biomass output at the primary producer level (Asaeda and Van Bon, 1997). Eutrophication can have a negative impact on lake water quality and severely limit the purposes for which the water is suitable. However, it should be understood that the negative effects come from the poor use of phytoplankton biomass, which is obtained from increasing nutrient availability. This is due to shifts in the dominance of algae species that are not or are ineffectively consumed by zooplankton grazers (Padedda *et al.*, 2017).

According to trophic level, lakes are categorized into the following empirically defined productivity range, from very low to very high production:

Oligotrophic lakes: An oligotrophic lake is a body of water with low primary productivity due to low nutrient content (Songyan *et al.*, 2016). These lakes have low production of algae, and consequently, they have extremely clear water with high-quality drinking water. The surface waters of these lakes typically have a lot of oxygen. Therefore, such lakes support many fish species, such as lake trout, which require cold, well-oxygenated water. Its oxygen content is higher in deep lakes deep having larger hypolimnetic volumes. Ecologists use the term oligotrophic to distinguish unproductive lakes, characterized by deficiencies of nutrients, from eutrophic or productive lakes with ample or excessive nutrient supply (Nemery *et al.*, 2016). Oligotrophic lakes are more common in cold regions, with beds of resistant igneous rocks (especially granitic) (Likens, 1975; Dingman and Johnson, 1971).

Mesotrophic lakes: A mesotrophic lake is a body of water with an intermediate level of productivity, greater than that of an oligotrophic lake, but less than that of a eutrophic lake. These lakes commonly have clear waters, support beds of submerged aquatic plants, and average nutrient levels. These lakes are less defined than oligotrophic or eutrophic lakes, and it is generally assumed that they are transitional lakes between the two conditions. During the summer season, there is a significant decrease in O₂ concentrations in the hypolimnion (Häkanson, 1980; Häkanson and Jansson, 1983; Meybeck *et al.*, 1989).

Eutrophic lakes: Nutrient-rich bodies of water that facilitate the proliferation of phytoplankton. When the algae die, they are decomposed by bacteria in aerobic processes that consume oxygen. When the oxygen finishes, many organic remains remain deposited at the bottom undergoing anaerobic processes that release H₂S (bad odors) and other gases, giving a nauseating appearance to the waters in cases of eutrophication extreme. In these lakes the light penetrates with difficulty in the water and the living beings are characteristic of oxygen-poor waters. During summer stratification, oxygen concentrations in the hypolimnion can drop to deficient levels, frequently less than 1 mg l⁻¹ (Häkanson, 1980; Häkanson and Jansson, 1983; Meybeck *et al.*, 1989).

Hypereutrophic lakes: Extremely eutrophic lakes that produce a lot of biomass due to their enormously high nutrient contents. Anoxia or complete loss of oxygen often occurs in the hypolimnion during summer stratification (Häkanson, 1980; Häkanson and Jansson, 1983; Meybeck *et al.*, 1989).

Dystrophic lakes: Lakes with high levels of organic matter (humic and fulvic acids) coming from external inputs from the watershed (Häkanson, 1980; Häkanson and Jansson, 1983; Meybeck *et al.*, 1989).

Each subtype has different evidence in terms of productivity and depth. Thus, the more oligotrophic a lake is, the more constant its production level is, in relation to the increase in depth. In contrast, a eutrophic system will have a high productivity at a certain depth after which it decreases (Nemery *et al.*, 2016). This is due to the extinction of light, that is, there is a decrease in the photic layer due to the concentration of algae, causing the lower areas to darken. On the other

hand, in the hypereutrophic type, its production is localized superficially due to the enormous concentration of nutrients and algae on the surface, drastically reducing the photic layer.

A.4. Shallow eutrophic lakes

Shallow lakes are the most abundant lake type on a global scale (Wetzel, 1990). This type of lake has been defined in very different ways; Scheffer (2004), in his work “Ecology of Shallow Lakes”, describes them as “lakes that can be largely colonized by macrophytes and that do not present thermal stratification for long periods in summer”. On the other hand, Wetzel (2001), in his book "Limnology: Lake and River Ecosystems", defines shallow lakes as "permanent bodies of water shallow enough to be capable of allowing light to enter their bottom and therefore the growth of higher aquatic plants in the whole lake or a large part of it". The diagnostic characteristics of shallow lakes are derived from these definitions, the main one being shallowness, as its name indicates. Although these lakes have a highly variable area (<1 km² or > 100 km²), their average depth does not usually exceed 3 m. The shallow depth favors the complete mixing of the water column, which explains the lack of thermal stratification for long periods and the fact that they are often called polymictic lakes (Scheffer *et al.*, 1993). In addition, the high surface: volume ratio favors an intense interaction between the sediments and the water column (Scheffer *et al.*, 1993). These features imply that the functioning of shallow lakes differs from that of deep lakes. For example, the close contact between the sediments and the water column leads to greater recycling of nutrients and, therefore a greater availability of these for primary producers, which is why shallow lakes are usually more productive than deep ones. In the same way, shallow lakes often have a larger littoral zone, facilitating a more intense exchange of matter and organisms between the terrestrial and aquatic environments (Meerhoff and Jeppesen, 2009).

As ecosystems, shallow lakes provide a wide range of services, which can be understood as "the conditions and processes through which natural systems, and the species that are part of them, sustain and satisfy the needs of human life" (Daily, 1997). Many shallow lakes are essential for developing economic and recreational activities such as agriculture, fishing, bird watching, swimming, boating or tourism, and also provide aesthetic benefits (Postel and Carpenter, 1997; Dodds *et al.*, 2008; McNeary *et al.*, 2013). Despite this, over recent decades shallow lakes have

been subjected to different degradation processes, such as fluctuations in water level, contamination by heavy metals or pesticides, and cultural eutrophication (Planta and Carrasco, 1985; Nöges and Nöges, 1999; Coops *et al.*, 2003; Zan *et al.*, 2011). Among these processes, cultural eutrophication should be highlighted as it represents a problem that seriously compromises the protection of water resources on a global scale (Smith, 2003; Yang *et al.*, 2008). Furthermore, the fact that shallow lakes are often located in flat and fertile areas makes them particularly sensitive to human activities in their watersheds (Meerhoff and Jeppesen, 2009).

Shallow eutrophic lakes can exist in two alternative stable states: a clear condition characterized by high water transparency, low phytoplankton biomass, and high abundance of submerged macrophytes, and a turbid state characterized by low water transparency, phytoplankton dominance. And submerged macrophytes are practically absent (Scheffer *et al.*, 1993). In this context, the interaction between macrophytes and water turbidity is decisive. On the one hand, the high turbidity of the water restricts the availability of light that penetrates the water column, preventing the growth of macrophytes; on the other hand, macrophytes enhance water clarity by reducing sediment resuspension, increasing sedimentation, competing with phytoplankton, or providing shelter for zooplankton from predation by fish (Scheffer *et al.*, 1993; Ibelings *et al.*, 2007). The relevance of this interaction is evidenced by the fact that lakes with an extensive cover of submerged macrophytes tend to be more transparent than those with a scarce cover and in a similar trophic state (Scheffer *et al.*, 1993). It is important to highlight that the clear and cloudy states can occur under similar environmental conditions, that is, under a certain range of moderate concentrations of nutrients (i.e., 0.025 - 0.15 mg L⁻¹ of total phosphorus) and that they show some stability against external disturbances, i.e., increased nutrient load (Scheffer *et al.*, 1993; Meerhoff and Jeppesen, 2009). Consequently, state changes are not usually gradual but abrupt, due to feedback mechanisms causing system insensitivity to the increase of a certain impact (hysteresis period). When a critical value or inflection point is reached, a catastrophic transition to the alternate state occurs; to reverse this state, the impact must be reduced well below its critical value (Scheffer *et al.*, 1993). However, recently, at the closing conference of the “8th International Shallow Lakes Congress” (Antalya, Turkey, 2014), Brian Moss drew attention to the fact that our concept of what a shallow lake should be in pristine conditions may be distorted by being defined based on the experience gained in North America and Europe. Specifically, he gave

as an example the lakes not subjected to anthropic impact located in floodplains in Tanzania, where submerged vegetation was absent due to grazing by large herbivores, which in turn provided nutrients in large quantities, favoring the appearance of cyanobacterial blooms on the banks.

Most measures aimed at restoring or improving the trophic status of eutrophic lakes (oligotrophication) have focused on reducing nutrient loads of allochthonous origin, especially phosphorus (Gulati and Van Donk, 2002; Søndergaard *et al.*, 2002). Although this measure has resulted in a rapid and notable improvement in the trophic status of some lakes, in many others a delay or absence of response has been observed, which is mainly explained by i) the internal load of nutrients accumulated in the sediments throughout the eutrophication period and ii) by resistance associated with the fish community (Jeppesen *et al.*, 2007). For example, the search for food by benthivores and planktivorous fish, which are very abundant in shallow eutrophic lakes, leads to the resuspension of the sediment (bioturbation), which hinders the penetration of light into the water column, essential for the development of macrophytes (Jayaweera and Asaeda, 1995). Since the reduction of external loads is often insufficient to mitigate eutrophication, different complementary restoration measures have been tried, such as the construction of green filters, the immobilization of phosphorus accumulated in the sediments through the use of calcium carbonate or clays adsorbents (bentonite), sediment dredging or biomanipulation (Jeppesen *et al.*, 2007; Cooke *et al.*, 2005). The latter implies manipulation of the trophic network by reducing the population of planktivorous and benthivores fish and the introduction of piscivorous fish, so that top-down control (from higher to lower trophic levels) exercised by fish over zooplankton is reduced. Another potentially useful restoration measure is hydrological manipulation, which involves adding water that is poor in nutrients and preferably rich in Ca and HCO₃ to the lake (Gulati and Van Donk, 2002; Ibelings *et al.*, 2007). Given the nature of the Cajititlán basin, closely linked to the agricultural environment and with a water regime highly controlled by man, the reduction of nutrient loads of allochthonous origin, together with the manipulation of the flow of water that crosses it, could facilitate his recovery largely. The use of water flow pulses has been proposed at the end of winter, the time when the maximum flooding of the lake and the surrounding fields occurs under natural conditions; these flood conditions had been maintained by traditional farmers since 1850 (Miracle *et al.*, 2012).

B. Generalities of Lake Cajititlán

Lake Cajititlán is a small, shallow subtropical lake located into an endorheic basin, situated between 20° 26' 13.20" and 20° 24' 07.91" north latitude and 103°22' 31.36" and 103°17' 00.48" west longitude. It is within the Lerma-Chapala-Santiago hydrological basin in the municipality of Tlajomulco de Zúñiga at the South of the State of Jalisco. Moreover, the lake is 30 km away from the city of Guadalajara, which is the second largest metropolitan area in Mexico. It is a perennial, endorheic, lake with intermittent runoff, with an average annual rainfall of 822 mm. The surface area is 1744 ha, the highest storage volume attained is 70.89 hm³, and the maximum depth is 5.4 m (de Anda *et al.*, 2019; Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Location of the Cajititlán aquifer, Jalisco. Source: CONAGUA, 2020.

There are four main types of natural vegetation in the lake's basin aquatic vegetation: thorny forest, subtropical deciduous forest, and pine-oak forest. Among the aquatic vegetation of the lake, the plant community of Tule (*Typha dominguensis*), Tulillo (*Cyperus articulatus*), water lily (*Eichhornia crassipes*), thorny forest (*Acacia farnesiana*), guamúchil (*Pithecellobium dulce*) grasslands of introduced forage grasses such as African star (*Cynodon dactylon* and *Cynodon plestostachus*) as well as deciduous plants, pines, and oaks (Luján-Godínez *et al.*, 2014).

Regarding the fauna of Lake Cajititlán, there is the following inventory of fish: 7 genera and 13 species, Common Carp (*Cyprinus carpio*), Mirror Carp (*Cyprinus carpio var. specularis*), Sardine (*Astyanax fasciatus*), Mudfish (*Poeciliopsis infans*), Popocha or Mudfish (*Goodea atripinii*), Blue-eared Mojarra (*Lepomis rafinesque*), Blue-eared Mojarra (*Lepomis macrochirus*), Silver Mojarra (*Oreochromis aureus*), Black Mojarra (*Oreochromis mossambicus*), Grated Mojarra (*Oreochromis nilotica*), Creole Mojarra (*Cichlasoma beani*). In addition, 59 species of aquatic birds and 32 of the terrestrial part surrounding the wetland (Luján-Godínez *et al.*, 2014).

The lake's basin significantly contributes to the economy of the region with fish production, craft, tourism, agriculture, livestock production, and recreational activities. Within the region of the sub-basin there are multiple attractions of a traditional and cultural type, typical handicrafts, ancient temples and chapels of the Franciscan route with religious images dating from 300 to 500 years, and natural areas where various tours can be taken. The representative crafts of the towns located on the shores of the lake are burnished clay, basalt stone, ropes for charrería, objects such as horsehair muzzles and articles of tule. In the region there are also pre-Hispanic ruins that constitute evidence of the ancient inhabitants of the area, dating back to 600 A.D. (Chávez-Hernández *et al.*, 2015; Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Lake Cajititlán. Source: Laguna De Cajititlan, 2018.

B.1. Hydrology of Lake Cajititlán

Lake Cajititlán, which is a part of the Tlajomulco-Cajititlán sub-basin, captures around 15,000 m³ of urban water, 30% of which receives primary treatment (Luján-Godínez *et al.*, 2014). As an endorheic sub-basin, it is dependent on the collection of water from the surrounding mountains to maintain the water tables in the region, which in turn allows for the maintenance of various springs, hot springs, deep waters, and other water collection sites. Additionally, due to its geomorphological and physical characteristics, it can operate as a local temperature regulator, favoring the climate in the area. It plays an important role in fishing, ecotourism activities, canoeing, a means to generate transportation, water recharge of wells and springs in the region, flood control, protection and shelter for wild fauna and flora, rest area, recreation, and leisure for the inhabitants of the region and an important support for the craft work of tule, clay, mud, and basalt rock (Luján-Godínez *et al.*, 2014). Due to the amount of water that it captures mainly from groundwater sources, it gives the possibility of maintaining important industries and productive activities in the region (some of which are for exporting products) and the possibility of sustaining in its diverse habitats and microclimates a quantity of flora and important fauna at the local, state, national and international levels (Luján-Godínez *et al.*, 2014).

B.2. Physical characteristics

The Köppen climate classification system is one of the most widely used across the world. It is used to identify different climatic zones on Earth based on local vegetation. Köppen's classification is based on a subdivision of terrestrial climates into five primary categories, denoted by the capital letters A, B, C, D, and E. Except for B, each of these climatic categories is characterized by temperature criteria. Köppen's map uses various colors and shades to represent the world's climatic zones. While most of the zones are structured based on a region's temperature, Zone B focuses on a region's aridity (Köppen, 1934; Köppen, 1984; Beck *et al.*, 2018). These zones are as follows:

1. Zone A: Tropical or equatorial zone. Its main climatic feature is the absence of winter and an average temperature above 18°C in all months of the year. It is also characterized by a type of tropical vegetation (represented by blue colors on most maps).
2. Zone B: Arid or dry zone. Little rainfall, evaporation exceeds annual rainfall. Vegetation

is limited to xerophytic plants. There are no trees (represented by red, pink, and orange colors on most maps).

3. Zone C: Warm/mild temperate zone. It is characterized by having mild winters in which the coldest month never has average temperatures below -3°C . This temperature is the limit of permafrost or permanently frozen ground. zone (represented by green colors on most maps).
4. Zone D: Continental zone. The winters are cold, so much so that the average monthly temperature of these months is below -3°C , although on the other hand the temperature of the warmest month of the year exceeds 10°C . That figure is the one that marks the limit of tree growth (represented by purple, violet, and light blue colors on most maps).
5. Zone E: Polar zone. Without summer, where the temperature of the warmest month of the year does not reach 10°C and where trees do not grow (represented by gray colors on most maps)

Temperature, as previously stated, characterizes the other four major climatic types. These are further classified, with extra letters used to identify the various subtypes. The seasonality of precipitation differentiates the three types of zone A climates: Af (no dry season), Am (short dry season), and Aw (winter dry season). Type E climates (the coldest) are conventionally separated into snow/ice (EF) and tundra (ET). A second letter, f (no dry season), w (winter dry), or s (summer dry), and a third symbol (a, b, c, or d [the last category exists only for D climates]), indicating the warmth of the summer or the coldness of the winter, are assigned to the mid-latitude C and D climates. Although Köppen's classification does not take into consideration the uniqueness of highland climate zones, the highland climate category, or H climate, is occasionally added to climate classification systems to account for altitudes over 1,500 meters (about 4,900 feet; (Köppen, 1934; Köppen, 1984; Beck *et al.*, 2018).

The climate of the Lake Cajititlán's sub-basin area according to the Köppen Climate Classification System corresponds to type (A) C (WO) (w) to (i) semi-warm sub-humid climate, with an average precipitation of 883 mm, a maximum of 900 mm, and a minimum of 600 mm. Regarding temporal distribution, 88.5% of the rains occur between June and October, 8.3% between January and May, and the remaining 3.2% between November and December

(CONAGUA, 2020).

The mean annual temperature conditions are between 19.9° C, with average values below 7.7° C and a maximum average of 31.7° C. The current thermal oscillation is 24 °C, with 200 hours of cold on average, even when they present zones with up to 500 hours per year (CONAGUA, 2020).

Lake Cajititlán is located in the neovolcanic axis, is a structure with a north-south direction, and is formed of various sub-regions, one of which is the Cajititlán and Chapala trench (Luján-Godínez *et al.*, 2014). Lake Cajititlán is situated on a tectonic depression that is partially filled with fluvial conglomerates, volcanic ash, and lacustrine deposits. The Cajititlán depression, having no communication with the sea, does not drain, and its waters have an average depth of 2.5 m. (State Water and Sanitation Commission of the Government of the State of Jalisco (CEA, 2004; Alatorre-Zamora *et al.*, 2015).

B.3. Pollution of the surface water

Lake Cajititlán is an endorheic basin formed by runoff from Cerro-Viejo and wastewater discharges from the populations settled on its banks: Cajititlán, San Miguel Cuyutlán, Tlajomulco, Cuescomatitlán, San Juan Evangelista and San Lucas Evangelista (Vizcaíno *et al.*, 2015). The state government constructed three nearby wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) that discharge their treated water directly into the lake. The WWTP with the highest capacity is San Miguel Cuyutlán (“SM”), whose treatment capacity is around 60 l/s, followed by the Cajititlán WWTP (“CAJ”), which treats approximately 12 l/s, and finally the San Juan Evangelista WWTP (“SJE”), which treats approximately 4 to 5 l/s (Fig. 3). Unfortunately, these facilities are inefficient as the discharged water does not reach national water quality requirements mandated by federal legislation. In addition, the process that is given to wastewater is only a primary and secondary treatment, with no tertiary treatment where nutrients are removed. In this instance, wastewater that hasn't been adequately treated is discharged right into the lake (de Anda *et al.*, 2019). On the other hand, there are no separate pipelines for wastewater and stormwater in the sewage systems of the communities located around the lake. Therefore, during the rainy season, WWTPs typically receive significantly more water than their installed capacity, which lowers

their operational efficiency. During the wet season, excess wastewater combined with rainwater are released directly into the lake. Furthermore, the community of Cuexcomatlán, which has around 2,316 (mexico.pueblosamerica, 2020) inhabitants and is located on the lake's western shore, discharges raw sewage directly into the lake without treatment. On the other hand, agriculture is the main economic activity in the basin. However, since most agriculture is rainfed, fertilizers are often used excessively during the rainy season; these agricultural practices have been identified as one of the primary drivers of nutrient pollution in the lake, resulting in cultural eutrophication (de Anda *et al.*, 2019). The lake has become hypertrophic due to this pollution, resulting in several episodes of mass fish kill, particularly between June and October 2013 to date. These events occurred during or immediately after the rainy season and die-offs have been attributed mainly to oxygen depletion (hypoxia/anoxia) that occurs at night due to the respiration process (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2018; de Anda *et al.*, 2019). The contamination problems of this lake have also been evidenced by the presence of large amounts of blue-green algae (~ 250,000 cells/mL), high concentrations of chlorophyll (~ 50 mg/L) and high relative turbidity (~ 90 NTU) (de Anda *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 3. Location of the treatment plants of Lake Cajititlán.

To avoid the massive loss of fish, in 2016, the Municipal Government of Tlajomulco de Zúñiga began to carry out actions to capture the species before presenting its possible mortality and convert it into compost for application in agricultural fields and in this way, replace the excessive application of agrochemicals in the farming areas of the basin because during the rainy season they drain into the lake (Iacoperacha.org.mx, 2016). However, this activity reduces the economic value of the product, and composting is a subsidized action that the municipality will not be able to sustain in the medium term. In addition, the Environmental Protection Agency stated that this action would not prevent the fish from dying since the environmental problem must be addressed from the source of the contamination (INFORMADOR.MX, 2016).

C. Generalities of phytoplankton

Phytoplankton are structural components of aquatic ecosystems; they function as a community of photosynthesizing microscopic organisms that remain suspended in a water column's photic zone (Thurman, 2007; Pierella *et al.*, 2020a, 2020b). They have been used to characterize the productive potential of the system and they can identify not only key species for the community and areas of biological importance, but also that provide an excellent background for monitoring the changes associated with the climatic and hydrological regime at different temporal and spatial scales (Kuhn *et al.*, 2019). Phytoplankton from continental waters develops mainly in lentic environments, or stagnant waters (lakes, lagoons, and reservoirs), with some also developing in lotic environments with unidirectional flowing water (springs, rivers, streams, waterfalls, and canals). The optimal environmental conditions for the development of phytoplanktonic species in lakes and rivers vary due to factors such as size, depth, temperature, light, transparency, oxygen, nutrients, pH, and salinity, among others (Wher *et al.*, 2015).

In Mexico, epicontinental phytoplankton comprises approximately 1,025 species, accounting for 6.8 % of continental algae worldwide, with 15,000 species (Bourrelly, 1990). It is divided into 17 classes, with the Bacillariophyceae having the most species, followed by the Cyanoprokaryota, Chlorophyceae, and Zygnematophyceae, and, to a lesser extent, the Dinophyceae and Xanthophyceae (Oliva-Martinez *et al.*, 2014).

The exponential growth of certain phytoplankton microorganisms is increased when the water

conditions are optimal, that is when there are events derived from natural phenomena and an increase in nutrients (Anderson *et al.*, 2002). Some of these blooms are considered harmful because they have a negative impact on the bodies of water in which they develop by gradually changing the physicochemical characteristics of the system, having an adverse effect on the local biota, mainly the consumers of the ecosystem (Anderson *et al.*, 2002). These blooms are caused by events of accelerated multiplication and massive accumulation of cells that result in a significant increase in their abundance (Anderson *et al.*, 2002).

A harmful algal bloom (HAB) is characterized by a massive increase in the biomass of phytoplankton cells. Each bloom can be made up of one or a few species. Even within a single species bloom there may be a mixture of toxic and non-toxic strains (Bhaskar and Sant, 2020). They generally occur at the end of summer, in periods of hours to days, and are arranged on the surface of the water forming a viscous green sheet that can have the appearance of foam (Pizolon, 1996; De León, 2002). These HABs are characterized by using the available oxygen and some essential nutrients for other organisms, directly suppressing the development of the aquatic biota. This is happening more frequently in some areas where industrialization and increased agricultural activity have not been adequately accompanied by the development of wastewater treatment (Azevedo *et al.*, 2002). The importance of studying HABs lies in the fact that some organisms are capable of producing toxins; as a result, an increase in cell biomass and the presence of cyanotoxins represent a threat to both humans and other aquatic organisms (Smayda, 1997).

C.1. Cyanobacteria and cyanotoxins

Cyanobacteria are prokaryotic organisms that can perform oxygenic photosynthesis and nitrogen fixation (Flores *et al.*, 2015). Due to their capacity to absorb sunlight at wavelengths that the majority of photosynthetic organisms are unable to, these pigmented protophytes have been crucial in the oxygenation of the earth's atmosphere (Aráoz *et al.*, 2010). They are a very diverse group in terms of morphology and metabolic capabilities, reflecting billions of years of evolution (Herrero and Flores, 2008). There is a wide of species and strains of cyanobacterial that can be harmful to humans and other animals who consume them or come into contact with contaminated water because they can produce toxic and other biologically active compounds (Codd *et al.*, 2005;

Quesada *et al.*, 2006), as well as for the environment (O'Neil *et al.*, 2012). Its presence affects water quality by altering pH, taste, transparency, and odor (Bláhová *et al.*, 2009). It is estimated that between 25 and 75 % of cyanobacterial blooms are toxic. *Microcystis*, *Cylindrospermopsis*, *Aphanizomenon*, *Nodularia*, *Anabaena*, *Nostoc*, *Oscillatoria*, and *Lyngbya* are the most important genera of cyanobacteria due to their impact on human and animal health and the environment due to their ability to produce toxins (Corbel *et al.*, 2014).

For all this, some authors warn that, at a given moment, it is possible that all the world's water reserves may contain cyanobacteria (Mankiewicz *et al.*, 2001), thus becoming a water quality problem in many countries of the world (Zhang *et al.*, 2009) and with important economic consequences (Carmichael, 2001, 2008), and on health (Codd *et al.*, 2005).

Cyanotoxins are extremely varied in terms of both chemical structure and toxicity (Briand *et al.*, 2003), and may be categorized into five classes based on the harmful effects they produce (Gutiérrez-Praena *et al.*, 2013):

- Hepatotoxins: microcystins and nodularia.
- Neurotoxins: anatoxin-a, anatoxin-a(s), saxitoxins.
- Cytotoxins: cylindrospermopsin.
- Dermatotoxins: aplisiatoxins, lyngbyatoxins.
- Irritating toxins: lipopolysaccharides.

Cylindrospermopsin and microcystins merit special attention among cyanotoxins since they are the only ones that have produced major intoxication events in human and fish populations (Bláha *et al.*, 2009; Landsberg *et al.*, 2020).

C.2. Toxic effects produced by microcystins in fish

Microcystins (MC) are hepatotoxins, with a cyclic heptapeptide structure (Imanishi *et al.*, 2005; Fig. 4), produced by species of cyanobacteria belonging to different genera such as *Microcystis*, *Anabaena*, *Planktothrix* (*P. agardhii* and *P. rubescens*), *Oscillatoria*, *Anabaenopsis*, *Nostoc* (*N. rivulare*), *Aphanizomenon* (*Aph. flos-aquae*) and even terrestrial genera such as *Hapalosiphon*

(Kaebernick and Neilan, 2001), with *Microcystis aeruginosa* standing out as one of the main producing species (Chorus, 2001). There are more than 70 different types of MC identified, which differ like two L-amino acids located in positions 2 and 4, and in the degree of methylation, hydroxylation and epimerization, using in their nomenclature the composition of such amino acids as a two-letter suffix, with MC-LR (contains leucine and arginine), MC-RR (arginine in both positions), and MC-YR (tyrosine and arginine) being the most studied (Zurawell *et al.*, 2005; Moreno *et al.*, 2003).

Figure 4. General structure of microcystin

It has been estimated that approximately 25-75% of cyanobacterial blooms are toxic (Zurawell *et al.*, 2005). In general, blooms tend to occur as a result of increased eutrophication, usually anthropogenic in nature, of aquatic ecosystems (Mankiewicz *et al.*, 2001). This is becoming more frequent, mainly in some regions where the growth of agricultural activity and industrialization have not been followed by adequate development of wastewater treatment (Azevedo *et al.*, 2002).

MCs can affect many terrestrial animals, birds, and aquatic organisms, from microalgae to mammals, including humans (Teixeira *et al.*, 1993; Oliveira *et al.*, 2005; Wiegand and Pflugmacher, 2004). The lack of alternative phytoplankton as food when cyanobacteria are the dominant species forces zooplankton to consume them. Some species of crustaceans avoid ingesting cyanobacteria containing MC. However, other cladoceran species are less selective, being able to ingest both toxic and non-toxic cyanobacteria under conditions of food scarcity,

accumulating MC and potentially transferring them to higher levels of the food chain (Mitrovic *et al.*, 2005). Thus, one of the routes of MC exposure in man is through the food chain through the ingestion of fish and mollusks that have been exposed to cyanobacteria and bioaccumulated these toxins (Ferrão-Filho and Kozlowsky-Suzuki, 2011).

The World Health Organization established a provisional guideline value of 1 µg/L of MC-LR in drinking water, including both intracellular and extracellular MC, based on the results of various toxicological studies conducted. In Spain, Royal Decree 140/2003 specifies a maximum MC level of 1 µg/L (WHO, 2017). Similarly, a preliminary Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI) of 0.04 g/Kg/day of MC-LR equivalents has been determined (WHO, 2020).

Fish kills have been associated with toxic cyanobacterial blooms on several occasions, and MCs have been linked to Netpen Liver Disease (NPLD) in captive-bred Atlantic salmon, causing significant losses in the marine farming industry (Ismael, 2012; Rolton *et al.*, 2022; Shartau *et al.*, 2022). Although the LD₅₀ for fish is higher than for rodent mammals, it should be noted that MCs in fish are not only hepatotoxic, but also affect other organs and that cyanobacteria may be present in the diet of some fish species such as cichlids and tropical cyprinids (Malbrouck and Kestemont, 2006). Microcystins cells have been found in fish stomachs, confirming this fact (Bowen, 1982).

D. Biogeochemical cycles in aquatic systems

The water quality of aquatic systems with respect to nutrient concentration is the result of the complex interaction between different factors, such as water movement, nutrient inputs, as well as *in situ* biological and chemical processes and anthropogenic inputs (Niencheski and Windom, 1994). Shallow aquatic environments allow the penetration of solar radiation into the sediment and its resuspension by wind action (Bonilla *et al.*, 2006). In turn, in these shallow systems the time scales in the water-sediment interactions are short, the hydrodynamic regime is varied, and the contribution of organic matter to the benthos is high and complex (Fonseca, 2004).

The benthic community in these environments generally plays an important role in the production and mineralization of organic matter, making the system more heterogeneous. The sediment plays

a very important role in the process of organic matter degradation, and therefore in the recycling of nutrients (Fonseca, 2004).

Intense and complex biogeochemical processes take place in lakes, such as nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, and/or carbon exchange. There is a strong link between biogeochemical cycles in terrestrial ecosystems and fractions of dissolved and particulate materials (e.g., nutrients, pollutants; Bianchi, 2007). In this sense, these systems can play different roles in the nutrient cycling process, since they can act as a "source" for the export of nutrients (heterotrophic metabolism), in which processes related to mineralization prevail. Or on the contrary, they can function as a "sink" in the case in which they absorb or retain a fraction of the nutrients that enter the system (autotrophic metabolism), in which primary production processes predominate over mineralization and/or respiration (Rodó, 2016).

Studies in tropical and temperate zones have shown strong associations between large-scale changes in land use and related nutrient flows between watershed and aquatic systems (Borbor-Cordoba *et al.*, 2006). Through different studies, a change in the metabolism of the systems with the addition of nutrients has been observed, going from a heterotrophic system to a purely autotrophic one (Wiegner *et al.*, 2003).

Nitrogen constitutes in most lacustrine, estuarine, and coastal aquatic systems, the limiting element of primary production, and therefore is the main responsible for their eutrophication (Struyf *et al.*, 2004). The denitrification process presents ecological and geochemical implications in these systems, representing a control of the degree of the eutrophication process. There is evidence that nitrogen loss via denitrification in lacustrine systems exceeds nitrogen input through the fixation process. An amount equivalent to between 40-50% of the dissolved inorganic nitrogen inputs to the system is estimated (Seitzinger, 1988).

Phosphorus in shallow aquatic systems is characterized by rapid processing through biological uptake and by geochemical processes that are interspersed between assimilation, adsorption, and desorption of particles (Brandini, 2008). The domain of any of these processes depends on physical and chemical factors, such as the pH, the oxidation-reduction layer, the residence time of

the water in the system, as well as the stratification of the water column and turbidity (Fonseca, 2004).

Sulfur compounds in natural waters come from rocks, sediment, fertilizers, and atmospheric transport due to precipitation and deposition of dry material, the latter being a source of great importance due to the increase in the combustion of industrial products (Ramos, 2001). Like other nutrients, sulfur has a cycle within aquatic systems presenting itself in two inorganic forms: hydrogen sulfide and sulfate ion (Ramos, 2001). Sulfates are of enormous environmental importance because they form compounds with many toxic agents, organic material and with hydrogen in surface waters, becoming the first acidifying agent in many rivers (Ramos, 2001). The presence of sulfides is common in wastewater due to the decomposition of organic matter, industrial waste, bacterial reduction in sulfates, although they are also often found in groundwater such as springs and some wastewater discharges (Ramos, 2001). The presence of hydrogen sulfide can be associated with soil decomposition processes; while sulfates are widely distributed in nature, with mine drainage being one of the main sources due to the oxidation of pyrite (De Anda-Hurtado and Miranda Herrera, 2004).

Lakes are seen as "reactors" in which carbon is transformed, buried in sediments, or emitted into the atmosphere rather than simply transported (Tranvik *et al.*, 2009). Carbon in freshwater ecosystems is produced within the system (autochthonous) through photosynthetic carbon assimilation and imported from outside (allochthonous). Through the complementary process of aerobic respiration, the production and consumption of both carbon dioxide (CO₂) and oxygen (O₂) become closely coupled. The interaction between lakes and streams and the terrestrial environment is strong (high shoreline-to-surface area ratio), and it is especially noticeable in smaller lakes and streams (Sand-Jensen and Staehr, 2007; Hotchkiss *et al.*, 2015). Thus, they receive organic carbon inputs in both dissolved (methane) and particulate forms (detritus), dissolved inorganic carbon, and dissolved organic carbon. The relative proportions of inorganic carbon forms vary depending on pH and water temperature; the main inorganic species are mainly CO₂ and acid carbonate (HCO₃⁻) (Stumm and Morgan, 1970). The organic portion is derived from recent terrestrial output, which has varying degrees of deterioration. Dissolved CO₂ from soil respiration either directly enters freshwater systems or contributes to the formation of carbonic

acid (H_2CO_3) in the soil, which leads to the weathering of calcite and silicate minerals and the formation of carbonate alkalinity (Berner and Berner, 2012). Depending on the system, atmospheric CO_2 may also infiltrate subsaturated surface waters, as is prevalent throughout the summer in eutrophic lakes (Balmer and Downing, 2011). Organic matter that has not been entirely mineralized to CO_2 or CH_4 can be exported or buried for potential long-term storage within the system. Much of the generated CO_2 or CH_4 can be emitted into the atmosphere depending on the physical conditions. Atmospheric gas fluxes can be calculated and linked to environmental variables measured in freshwaters and surrounding ecosystems (Thorø-Martinsen, 2021).

E. Metagenomic approaches

Metagenomics is a culture-independent genomic analysis of microbial communities having the potential to solve basic and fundamental microbial ecology questions. Through the exploration of novel genes, catalytic enzymes, metabolic pathways, and bioactive compounds with biochemical activities, metagenomics helps in the bioprospection of "hidden" genetic traits that leads to the development of innovative biotechnological applications. Furthermore, the approach provides a deeper knowledge of an extreme spectrum of selective pressures in adverse environments, as well as any genetic flexibility and metabolic adaptability of microbial communities (Shikha *et al.*, 2021).

Metagenomics has been used to solve fundamental environmental microbiology problems such as: how many are there? Who are they? And what are they capable of doing? metagenomics is an important tool for the study of microbial ecology and prospecting metabolic potential by analyzing taxonomic diversity and the location of genes responsible for the synthesis of molecules with properties of biotechnological interest (Handelsman, 2004; Steele and Streit, 2005). With the emergence of high-throughput Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) technology, researchers now have a feasible, scalable method to detect unculturable bacteria in their natural environments (Margulies *et al.*, 2005).

There are two primary approaches to applying NGS in microbial ecology, each with its own set of costs and advantages. To produce metagenomes, the direct shotgun technique entails sequencing

all the DNA in a particular sample. Because it explicitly observes genes in the environment, a shotgun metagenome can reveal functional information about a microbial community (Sharpton, 2014). Shotgun metagenomic sequencing also enables researchers to collect all genes from all species present in a complex sample. Microbiologists can use the approach to assess microbial diversity and abundance in a variety of environments (Illumina, 2022). On the other hand, 16S and 18S ribosomal rRNA gene amplification and sequencing approaches are the most widely used genes in phylogenetic research. These genes allow the coding of bacterial, archaean and eukaryotic communities, with some conserved sections in the tree of life. Universal PCR primers can be constructed to amplify the intermediate neutral evolution bases by hybridizing to these regions of the gene (Lane *et al.*, 1985). While the concept of sequencing these environmental genes is not new, next-generation sequencing has made it possible on a far bigger scale (Caporaso *et al.*, 2012). The limitation of 16S and 18S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing is that it provides minimal information about the function of a microbial community, making it less preferable than per-sample shotgun metagenome sequencing (Louca *et al.*, 2018).

PICRUSt1 was the first tool developed in 2013 for predicting function from 16S rRNA marker sequences (Langille *et al.*, 2013). The latest version of this tool was developed in 2020 and is called PICRUSt2. Specifically, PICRUSt2 contains a revised and extended library of gene families and reference genomes, provides interoperability with any OTU selection or denoising algorithm, and can predict phenotypes. Benchmarking reveals that PICRUSt2 outperforms the first version (PICRUSt1) and other competitive approaches in general. Custom reference databases can also be added to PICRUSt2 (Douglas *et al.*, 2020).

F. Aims of the thesis

Rainfall and other anthropogenic pollutant sources can significantly alter the physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of lakes in tropical and subtropical regions, altering the water quality and influencing the microbial communities that regulate the biogeochemical cycles within these ecosystems. There is still limited knowledge of the interactions between water quality and biogeochemical processes within tropical and subtropical lake ecosystems. Therefore, it is crucial to understand how microbial metabolism drives biogeochemical processes in these types of lakes that have high levels of nutrient pollution. Microbial metagenomics has proven to be quite valuable for the design of remediation strategies in deteriorated ecosystems. This technique allows for a broader understanding of the microbial community and their drivers, which is necessary for informed decision-making.

Lake Cajititlán is a small endorheic, subtropical, and shallow lake. Agriculture is the main economic activity in the lake's basin, with most agricultural production occurring during the rainy season. The use of large amounts of fertilizers generates nutrient enrichment of the lake through surface runoff. In addition, effluents from three WWTPs located along the reservoir's shoreline contribute strongly to nutrient enrichment since these facilities do not adequately treat their municipal sewage. As a result, the lake's water quality and ecological integrity have been severely affected, leading the reservoir to a hypereutrophic state, manifested through several episodes of fish kills during the rainy season due to oxygen depletion (hypoxia) at night, from 2013 to date.

The overall goal:

To characterize the microbial communities of Lake Cajititlán, a subtropical and hypereutrophic lake, during the rainy season in response to physicochemical and environmental variables from anthropogenic inputs, analyzing both microbial diversity and biogeochemical nutrient cycles.

The main objectives:

1. To evaluate the physicochemical and environmental parameters temporally and spatially of Lake Cajititlán.
2. To characterize the changes in the lake's phytoplankton communities during the rainy season using 16S and 18S ribosomal RNA metagenomics, as well as the bidirectional association between these changes and water physicochemical quality and environmental factors.

3. To characterize the temporal dynamics of bacterial communities and their genes associated with nutrient biogeochemical cycles during the rainy season through 16S ribosomal RNA metagenomics and Phylogenetic Investigation of Communities by Reconstruction of Unobserved States (PICRUSt2), as well as the influences of physicochemical and environmental variables on such dynamics.
4. To elucidate the influences of microbial communities on nutrient biogeochemical cycles in a hypereutrophic and subtropical lake using high-throughput shotgun sequencing.

G. Hypothesis

H₁: The bidirectional effects between the structure and diversity of microbial communities and the physicochemical parameters are determinant factors influencing the trophic state and biogeochemical cycles and successional stages of subtropical lakes during the rainy season.

H₂: There are temporal variations in the diversity and abundance of Lake Cajititlán's microbial communities caused by changes in the reservoir's water quality during the rainy season.

H₃: There are temporary variations in functional genes of the microbial communities associated with the biogeochemical cycles of nutrients (N, P, C, and S), as well as a greater abundance of these at the beginning of the rainy season due to the anthropic inputs of nutrients that reach Lake Cajititlán from diffuse and non-diffuse sources.

CHAPTER II: RAPID CHANGES IN THE PHYTOPLANKTON COMMUNITY

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Chapter II is focused on describing the changes in the phytoplankton community in Lake Cajititlán during the rainy season and the association between these changes and the physicochemical quality of the water and the environmental parameters measured in the lake basin. The summary conclusions of this section indicate that the climatic fluctuations that occur in the Lake Cajititlán region cause high seasonal surface runoff and rapid changes in water quality, and variations in the phytoplankton community composition. The information provided in this part supports the hypothesis that fish mortality in Lake Cajititlán is mainly due to anoxia, which is induced by abrupt changes in water quality during the rainy season. This is one of the first studies on the phytoplankton community in a subtropical lake using high-throughput 16S rRNA and 18S rRNA amplicon sequencing. Special attention should be paid to small, shallow endorheic lakes located in subtropical areas, which are highly vulnerable to pollutant runoff in the rainy season. In addition, this chapter is part of the first publication of this thesis.

Original Research

Rapid Changes in the Phytoplankton Community of a Subtropical, Shallow, Hypereutrophic Lake During the Rainy Season

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A. Summary

Lake Cajititlán is a small, shallow, subtropical lake located in an endorheic basin in western Mexico. It is characterized by a strong seasonality of climate with pronounced wet and dry seasons and has been classified as a hypereutrophic lake. This eutrophication was driven by improperly treated sewage discharges from four municipal wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and by excessive agricultural activities, including the overuse of fertilizers that reach the lake through surface runoff during the rainy season. This nutrient rich runoff has caused algal blooms, which have led to anoxic or hypoxic conditions, resulting in large-scale fish deaths that have occurred during or immediately after the rainy season. This study investigated the changes in the phytoplankton community in Lake Cajititlán during the rainy season and the association between

these changes and the physicochemical water quality and environmental parameters measured in the lake's basin. *Planktothrix* and *Cylindrospermopsis* were the dominant genera of the cyanobacterial community, while the Chlorophyceae, Chrysophyceae and Trebouxiophyceae classes dominated the microalgae community. However, the results showed a significant temporal shift in the phytoplankton communities in Lake Cajititlán induced by the rainy season. The findings of this study suggest that significant climatic variations cause high seasonal surface runoff and rapid changes in the water quality (Chlorophyll-*a*, DO, NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻) and in variations in the composition of the phytoplankton community. Finally, an alternation between phosphorus and nitrogen limitation was observed in Lake Cajititlán during the rainy season, clearly correlating to the presence of *Planktothrix* when the lake was limited by phosphorus and to the presence of *Cylindrospermopsis* when the lake was limited by nitrogen. The evidence presented in this study supports the idea that the death of fish in Lake Cajititlán could be mainly caused by anoxia, caused by rapid changes in water quality during the rainy season. Based on our review of the literature, this is the first study on the phytoplankton community in a subtropical lake during the rainy season using high throughput 16S rRNA and 18S rRNA amplicon sequencing.

B. Introduction

Lake Cajititlán is a small, shallow subtropical lake located in an endorheic basin in the municipality of Tlajomulco de Zúñiga in the state of Jalisco, Mexico at 1552 m a. s. l. (Limón-Macias *et al.*, 1983). It represents an important regional water resource for the harvesting of endemic fish species such as: charal (*Menidia Grandocule*), tiro (*Goodea atripinnis*), popocha (*Algansea popoche*) and pintitas (*Posiliopsis infans*) (Luján-Godínez *et al.*, 2014; Rosales-Figueroa, 1994; Vizcaíno-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2018; Caro-Becerra *et al.*, 2017). The basin of Lake Cajititlán is characterized by strong seasonality of climate with pronounced wet and dry seasons. Agriculture is the main economic activity within the basin. However, most of the agriculture is rainfed, which means that fertilizers are used during the rainy season, often in excessive amounts. These agricultural practices are one of the principal sources of nutrient contamination leading to cultural eutrophication in the Lake (de Anda *et al.*, 2019b). The poor water quality in the Lake is also due to partially treated sewage that is discharged into the lake from three municipal WWTPs; these discharges frequently do not meet the water quality standards required by federal

regulations (de Anda *et al.*, 2019a). As a result of this nutrient pollution, the Lake has been classified as hypereutrophic (de Anda *et al.*, 2019b). This process of cultural eutrophication is exacerbated by the endorheic nature of the Lake (IIEG, 2018; de Anda *et al.*, 2019a).

Previous studies have demonstrated the water quality of Lake Cajititlán, as measured by an ecosystem-specific water quality index developed for this lake, has consistently reached its lower values during and immediately after the wet season (June-September) for a monitoring period of nine years (2009-2018) (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2020b). Several episodes of sudden, large-scale fish mortality have been reported since 2013, mainly during or immediately after the rainy season (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2018). During this period, runoff from agricultural land and discharges of partially treated wastewater mixed with rainwater result in a large input of nutrients, organic matter, and other pollutants to the lake, causing phytoplankton blooms. As a result, high rates of dissolved oxygen (DO) consumption during the night, have led to episodes of anoxic (zero dissolved oxygen) or hypoxic (low dissolved oxygen) conditions. These conditions are largely responsible for the large-scale fish mortality (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2018; de Anda *et al.*, 2019a; Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2020a, b).

Phytoplankton are the autotrophic component of the planktonic community and therefore the base of the trophic network in aquatic ecosystems. Phytoplankton include photosynthetic prokaryotic (cyanobacteria) and eukaryotic (microalgae) organisms that live near the surface of the water column, where they can capture the necessary light to support photosynthesis (Rouco, 2011). Phytoplankton abundance and distribution in aquatic systems depend on environmental and physicochemical factors, such as nutrient availability (phosphorus and nitrogen) (Rouco, 2011; Mur *et al.*, 1999), light intensity (Su *et al.*, 2014; Rouco, 2011), temperature (Zhang *et al.*, 2016; Bormans *et al.*, 2004; Rouco, 2011), water clarity (turbidity) (Zhang *et al.*, 2016) and the abundance of other planktonic organisms or predators (Rouco, 2011), as well as their characteristic ecophysiology (e.g., growth rate) (Mur *et al.*, 1999). Phytoplankton blooms impact aquatic ecosystems by depleting oxygen at night and reducing light penetration (Ssebiyonga *et al.*, 2013). In addition, several cyanobacterial genera (*Microcystis*, *Anabaena*, *Planktothrix*, *Oscillatoria*, *Anabaenopsis*, *Nostoc*) produce a group of peptide toxins, known as microcystins (WHO, 1999; Kaebernick and Neilan, 2001). These cyanotoxins may be absorbed in fish through

their gills, or through diet, accumulating in organs, resulting in major damage to the liver and kidney (Lance, 2008), as well as causing cell damage and death through the inhibition of phosphatases (Fu, 2005; Yoshizawa *et al.*, 1990).

Tropical and subtropical regions display specific sensitivities to eutrophication because of their climatological attributes. High rainfall in these regions may enhance nutrient runoff from agricultural areas to surficial waters (Cunha *et al.*, 2013). In these regions, nutrient contamination is more strongly oriented towards nitrogen, the most likely limiting nutrient in tropical and subtropical lakes. Primary production in tropical and subtropical lakes is sustained throughout the year as a result of higher temperatures, as opposed to temperate lakes, where the productive seasons are spring and summer (Talling, 1992; Cunha *et al.* 2013). The limnology of temperate regions has been increasingly focused on the changes in the phytoplankton communities during different seasons (Wei *et al.*, 2020; Lenard and Wojciechowska, 2013; Wojciechowska and Lenard, 2014; Hampton *et al.*, 2015; Kalinowoska and Grabowska, 2016; Özkundakci *et al.*, 2016; Grosbois *et al.*, 2017; Lenard *et al.*, 2019). Yet, there are few studies on the temporal dynamics of phytoplankton during different seasons in tropical or subtropical shallow lakes, and even fewer studies that examine the rainy season (Lewis, 1990; Idumah and Ugwumba., 2013).

In comparison to culture-based studies, high throughput sequencing (HTS) can detect a large majority of microbial taxa present. This helps to generate a deeper understanding when comparing populations of phytoplankton (Falconer *et al.*, 2005; Brooks *et al.*, 2015; Tragin *et al.*, 2017). In this study, we have used HTS to assess the phytoplankton community during the rainy season in a eutrophic subtropical and shallow lake. This was accomplished by targeting two hypervariable regions: V3-V4 of the 16S rRNA gene and V4 of the 18S rRNA gene. Based on our review of the literature, this is the first study on the phytoplankton community in a subtropical lake during the rainy season using 16S rRNA and 18S rRNA amplicon HTS.

The objective of this study was to analyze the phytoplankton dynamics during the rainy season in Lake Cajititlán, which has a pronounced hot-dry season (February-May) and a wet season (June-September), as well as strong anthropogenic inputs of pollutants. Additionally, we sought to determine how physicochemical and environmental factors associate with these variations. A

deeper understanding of these elements will contribute to our understanding of the impact of seasonality on the water quality of these types of lakes.

C. Experimental methods

C.1. Study site

Lake Cajititlán has an average surface area of 17.44 km², a maximum depth of 3.87 m, and an average storage volume of approximately 70.89 Hm³ (de Anda *et al.*, 2019b). According to Lewis (1983), it is classified as a warm polymictic lake. An important feature of the Lake is that it is in an endorheic basin surrounded by small hills. The area of the basin is approximately 201.8 km² (de Anda *et al.*, 2019b) (Fig 5). Three seasons generally occur in this basin (i): the hot-dry season (February-May), the wet season (June-September), and the cold-dry season (October-January) (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2020a).

Figure 5. Location of the sampling stations in Lake Cajititlán.

C.2. Characterization of the annual behavior of climate data and the water quality features of Lake Cajititlán

Precipitation rates (mm), evaporation rates (mm) and maximum/minimum air temperatures (°C) from both 2018 (when the sampling was performed) as well as historically (from 1998 to 2019) were retrieved from of the National Water Commission of Mexico (“CONAGUA” COMISIÓN NACIONAL DEL AGUA). These measurements were made at a climatological station (ID # 00014072) located 20 km from Lake Cajititlán. These data were analyzed to characterize the climate of this subtropical region. Furthermore, total nitrogen (TN) and total phosphorus (TP) (mg/L) values were retrieved from the State Water Commission (Spanish acronym CEA) data repository for the same five sampling points as used in this study (CEA-1, CEA-2, CEA-3, CEA-4, and CEA-5) at a depth of 0.8 m (Fig. 5). These data were obtained as a time series with monthly periodicity from September 2009 to April 2019 (CEA-Jalisco 2019).

During our field sampling, physicochemical parameters were measured once per month during the rainy season (July–September) to assess the water quality of Lake Cajititlán. Five sampling points (CEA-1, CEA-2, CEA-3, CEA-4, and CEA-5) and two monitoring depths (80 cm and interstitial) were selected. These sampling points corresponded to the sites established by the CEA to monitor the water quality of the lake (Fig. 5). This study period (July–September) was chosen because, historically, the greatest variations in rainfall and TN:TP ratio occur in this season (Fig. 6A, E), as well as the lowest average values of the ecosystem-specific water quality index of Lake Cajititlán (Fig. 6F; Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2020b). Only one measurement (a total of 30 measurements) was taken for each physicochemical parameter, using two previously calibrated environmental probes (6600 and 6829 V2 YSI® a xylem brand) (YSI, 2009). The following physicochemical parameters were analyzed: dissolved oxygen (DO), water temperature (WT), electrical conductivity (EC), turbidity, pH, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrates (NO₃⁻), phycocyanin-containing blue-green algae (BGA-PC), Chlorophyll-*a* and Secchi depth.

Figure 6. Annual behavior of the mean temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) (maximum and minimum), rainfall (mm), and evaporation (mm) of Lake Cajititlán over a 21-year period (1998-2019). Annual behavior of the ecosystem-specific water quality index (ES-WQI) of Lake Cajititlán in the period 2009-2017. Annual behavior of the mean TN:TP ratio in Lake Cajititlán over a ten-year period (2009-2019). A: Rainfall (mm); B: Evaporation (mm); C: Maximum temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$); D: Minimum temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$); E: TN:TP ratio (mg/L); F: ES-WQI.

Water samples for sequencing were taken from Lake Cajititlán using a Van Dorn type bottle and placed in plastic containers of 1 L capacity that were previously disinfected and washed. Two replicates of each sample were obtained, resulting in 2 L per sample and a total of 60 water

samples. These samples were taken at the same sampling points, depth, and study period, as the measurements of physicochemical parameters. All of the samples were transported at 4°C to the Laboratory of Biotechnological Bioprocesses of Tecnológico de Monterrey at the Guadalajara campus for subsequent analyses.

C.3. DNA extraction, PCR amplification and sequencing

To retain different microbial fractions, both water sample replicates were filtered independently using two different pore sized cellulose nitrate membranes (Whatman™) connected to a vacuum pump. First, each replicate was filtered using a membrane with a pore size of 20-25 µm. Afterwards, the obtained filtrate was passed through a second membrane with a pore size of 0.45 µm. Therefore, in total, two membranes of different pore sizes were obtained per replicate. Each of these two filters was then separately cut into pieces using sterile scissors and 100 mg of each were weighed and added to a lysing matrix to perform a DNA extraction and purification of the samples using the FastDNA Spin Kit for Soil (MP Biomedicals, OH, USA), according to the manufacturer's instructions. The concentration of purified DNA was measured using a NanoDrop® ND-1000 UV-Vis spectrophotometer (NanoDrop Technologies, Wilmington, DE).

To understand the abundance/composition of the cyanobacteria and microalgae communities present in Lake Cajititlán, PCR amplification was carried out separately for prokaryote *vs.* eukaryote identification. For prokaryotes, a *ca.* 460 bp fragment covering the V3-V4 hypervariable regions of the 16S rRNA gene was PCR amplified following the Illumina protocol for 16S Metagenomic Sequencing Library Preparation (Amplicon, 2013). For eukaryotes, a *ca.* 470 bp fragment of the V4 region of the 18S rRNA gene was amplified with primers previously shown to preferentially amplify microalgae (forward 5'-CCAGCASCYGCGGTAATTCC-3' and reverse 5'-ACTTTCGTTCTTGATYRATGA -3'; (Tragin *et al.*, 2017). PCR products were run on a 1% agarose gel in a TAE buffer and visualized by GelRed staining (Biotium, USA) under UV light. A nested PCR was then performed to attach the dual indices and Illumina sequencing adapters using the Nextera XT Index kit (illumina®), and electrophoresis was performed with the PCR products (1% agarose gel) to confirm that indexes and adapters were successfully attached to the libraries. A clean-up of the sequencing libraries was carried out with magnetic beads from the

AMPure XP kit (Beckman Coulter) to later quantify using a Qubit 2.0 fluorometer (Life Technologies, Invitrogen™).

To achieve maximum operational efficiency in the Illumina sequencing platform, a single sequencing run was performed for both prokaryotic and eukaryotic 96-sample libraries combined in a single prep-plate and uniquely indexed (Amplicon, 2013). This was carried out by combining the prokaryotic and eukaryotic amplified products per sample, using a ratio of 70:30 prokaryotic to eukaryotic PCR product concentration, respectively. For high-throughput sequencing, the 96 samples were pooled at a concentration of 8 pM and loaded together with 10% Phix control into an Illumina® MiSeq sequencer using the MiSeq Reagent Kit v3 (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) in the sequencing facilities of Tecnológico de Monterrey, Campus Monterrey. The sequencing run has been uploaded to the NCBI Sequence Read Archive with accession numbers PRJNA626359 (16S rRNA gene sequences) and PRJNA626364 (18S rRNA gene sequences).

C.4. Bioinformatic analyses

For sequencing data analyses, 16S rRNA and 18S rRNA gene sequences were split using the primer sequences as a criterion for division on the Galaxy open-source platform (Afgan *et al.*, 2018). Once prokaryotic and eukaryotic sequences were separated, these were analyzed in the software QIIME 2.0 (Quantitative Insights into Microbial Ecology; Boylen *et al.*, 2019) following a standard bioinformatics pipeline. First, raw reads were demultiplexed and denoised into amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) using DADA2 (p-trim-left 0, p-trunc-len 440 nts). Afterwards, two characteristics tables (FeatureData[Sequence] and FeatureData[Taxonomy]) were constructed using 99% similarity, with the SILVA version 132 and RDP version 11 databases used for 16S rRNA and the PR² version 4.12.0 database used for 18S rRNA. (Quast *et al.*, 2013; Yilmaz *et al.*, 2014; Cole *et al.*, 2013; Guillou *et al.*, 2013; del Campo *et al.*, 2018). Then, the classifier was trained using the primers and the length of the samples through the Naives Bayes classifier method. Finally, taxonomic classification was performed with classify-sklearn and the file of the denoised sequences together with the trained classifier (Boylen *et al.*, 2019). Taxa bar plots were generated to assign the corresponding taxonomy to the ASV table, which were downloaded in CVS format from view.qiime2.org to continue further analysis.

C.5. Statistical analyses

To understand the effects of climatic conditions during the sampling period (2018) as well as over a period of 21 years (1998 to 2019), CONAGUA datasets were used to construct box plots comparing rainfall, evaporation rates, maximum and minimum temperatures (CONAGUA Gobierno de México, 2020). A box plot of the TN:TP relationship was also constructed to better understand the limiting nutrient in Lake Cajititlán throughout the sampling year (2018) and during a ten-year history (2009-2019). In the case of tropical lakes/reservoirs, a ratio higher than 9 indicates a phosphorus-limited body of water, while a ratio lower than 9 represents nitrogen limitation (Salas and Martino, 2001). Likewise, a boxplot was constructed to depict the yearly behavior of the ecosystem-specific water quality index using an algorithm from a previous report (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2020b). Additionally, physicochemical parameters were analyzed spatially and temporally, and box plots were created.

Sequencing depth of the 16S and 18S rRNA genes was represented by a rarefaction curve performed in R by the rarefy function based on Hurlbert's (1971) formulation, and the standard errors were based on Heck *et al.* (1975). For the following analyzes, only the taxonomic information of the cyanobacterial and microalgae communities was used. Read numbers were normalized using the package DESeq2 (Anders and Huber 2010). To visualize, analyze and compare the information, bar plots of relative read abundance were performed using the Scale package. Taxa with proportions <0.01% were grouped as “others” and unclassified genera (cyanobacteria) or families (microalgae) were denoted by “Un”, and the previous taxonomic level identified. Alpha diversity indices of Shannon (diversity), Simpson (proportional abundance) and Chao1 (microbial richness) were calculated using the diversity (Shannon and Simpson) and estimateR (Chao1) functions (Fisher *et al.*, 1943; Cori *et al.*, 2013), which were presented in a boxplot to observe the spatial and temporal variation within these diversity indices (Miller, 1981; Yandell, 1997).

Furthermore, changes in microbial community structure were analyzed by principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) using the cmdscale function in the vegan package, based on Bray-Curtis distances (Oksanen *et al.*, 2016). In addition, using the Bray and Curtis dissimilarity index,

permutational multivariate analysis of variance (perMANOVA) ($P < 0.05$) and analysis of similarity (ANOSIM) were used to test statistically significant differences in phytoplankton community composition at the spatial scale of Lake Cajititlán and temporal form (Anderson *et al.*, 2006; Clark, 1993; Anderson, 2001; Oksanen *et al.*, 2016).

Unless stated otherwise, all statistical analyses were conducted with R version 3.5.3 (R Core Team, 2019) using the *vegan* package (Oksanen *et al.*, 2016). Box plots and line diagrams were built using the *ggplot2* package (Wickham, 2009). All boxplots were prepared to include the results of one-way analyses of variance (ANOVA) ($\alpha = 0.05$) and Tukey's HSD tests to determine significant differences.

C.6. Detection and quantification of total microcystin content

For microcystin analysis, additional water samples were obtained from the same sampling sites and depths on July 15, 2019. This is historically the month that many fish die in Lake Cajititlán (Alatorre, 2015). This month has also been reported to present the lowest values of the water quality index specific for Lake Cajititlán, as reported by Gradilla-Hernández *et al.* (2020b), for a period of 9 years (Fig. 6F).

Duplicate water samples were collected using a horizontal “Grab” or Van Dorn type bottle and placed in 500 mL high-density polyethylene wide-mouth bottles. All samples were transported at 4°C to the molecular microbiology laboratory of CIATEJ (Centro de Investigación y Asistencia en Tecnología y Diseño del Estado de Jalisco, A.C.) and were processed within 24 hours.

Quantitative measurement of total microcystin content was carried out in duplicate by an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) with microcystin specificity, using a commercial kit and following the manufacturer's protocol (Prod. No. ALX-850-319, Enzo Life Science Inc. Farmingdale, USA). In accordance with the instructions and recommendations described by the manufacturer (Fischer *et al.*, 2001), the cell lysis procedure of the samples was performed by freezing, thawing and sonication methods. Optical density values were measured at 450 nm using a Cytation™ 3 (BioTek™) microplate spectrophotometer, with a microcystin detection limit of

0.1 $\mu\text{g/L}^{-1}$. Total microcystin concentrations of the samples were determined by interpolating a standard curve constructed with each run.

D. Results

D.1. Climatological characterization and water quality characteristics of the Lake Cajititlán

According to the historical behavior of climatological data, the climatological parameter that displayed the greatest variations during the rainy season was precipitation (Fig. 6A), with July being the month that historically receives the highest rainfall, and consequently, an intensive runoff of pollutants to the lake. Tropical and subtropical lakes are more susceptible to excessive pollutant runoff, since the rainy season is very intense and changes in water quality parameters are reflected even faster in shallow and small lakes (Nobre *et al.*, 2020). These trends are strongly associated with the lowest ES-WQI values observed during the month of July in Lake Cajititlán (Fig. 6F), as well as with the greatest variations in the TN:TP ratio observed during the rainy season (Fig. 6E).

The annual behavior of the TN:TP ratio uncovered temporal shifts triggered by the onset of the wet season (Fig. 6E). The wet season (June–September) showed the highest values in June (> 9) and then values close to 9 in July. These results suggest that Lake Cajititlán shifts from being phosphorus-limited at the beginning of the rainy season (June-July) and at the end of the rainy season (September), to being limited by nitrogen (< 9) in August (Salas and Martino, 2001). These alternations are associated with the intensive runoff of fertilizers at the onset of the rainy season, increasing the TN:TP ratio during June and July, and then decreasing the ratio in August as a result of the consumption of nitrogenous compounds by the increasing phytoplankton communities (Hem, 1985; Raven *et al.*, 1992; Cabello *et al.*, 2009; Prangnell *et al.*, 2019). Alternation between phosphorus and nitrogen limitation has been previously documented for tropical or subtropical lakes (Morris and Lewis, 1998). Fig. 6E shows the mean annual behavior of the TN:TP ratio in Lake Cajititlán for the period (2009-2018).

Similar to the changes historically observed for the behavior of the TN:TP ratio, the results of our monitoring program throughout the rainy season (July-September) indicated that most of the physicochemical parameters monitored showed significant temporal variations when comparing the values reported for the three different months (Fig. 6A). NH_4^+ , NO_3^- and ORP were found to decrease over time (from July to September), whereas dissolved oxygen (DO) and Chlorophyll-*a* increased, indicating an increase in the photosynthetic activity in phytoplankton communities (Steel, 1980). Additionally, in small and shallow tropical lakes, such as Lake Cajititlán, very rapid and significant changes occur in the concentration of water quality parameters due to the effects of the rainy season (Nobre *et al.*, 2020). In the case of Lake Cajititlán, the concentration of nutrients (NH_4^+ , NO_3^-) were highest in July as a result of a concentration process due to evaporation during the hot-dry season (February-May) (Fig. 7B) and due to the runoff of pollutants after the first rains. During the rainy season (August-September), the concentrations of nutrients were found to decrease as a result of a dilution process caused by high precipitation rates (Fig. 7A). pH, turbidity, and BGA-PC displayed similar temporal patterns during the study period. Spatial analysis indicated significant variations in fewer parameters: WT, BGA-PC, EC, NH_4^+ and DO. DO displayed the most spatial variation, presenting hypoxic average concentrations ($< 2.0 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$; Wu, 2009) at the two deepest analyzed sample sites (CEA-3 and CEA-5) (Fig. 7B). Such DO levels ($< 5.0 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) are considered unsuitable for most aquatic organisms (Wu, 2009).

During the sampling months of this study, the water transparency was evaluated using a Secchi disc. Values ranged between 8.20 and 21.80 cm (Table 1). In an attempt to evaluate eutrophication in tropical areas, several indices (Lamparelli's index or the Carlson's Trophic State Index) that consider the particular characteristics of tropical environments have been developed. Some of these indices, however, do not consider water transparency, because this parameter is directly affected by the naturally high turbidity of tropical waters during most of the year, but especially during the rainy season (Toledo *et al.*, 1983; Salas and Martino, 1991; Lamparelli, 2004; Carlson, 1977). However, if the results obtained from Secchi transparency and Chlorophyll-*a* of this study and the TP history database are compared with the Lamparelli's index or the Carlson's Trophic State Index, Lake Cajititlán is classified as hypereutrophic. This condition was previously reported by de Anda *et al.* (2019b) for Lake Cajititlán. This condition was previously reported by de Anda *et al.* (2019b) for Lake Cajititlán.

Table 1. Secchi depth by month and sampling site.

Sampling point	Secchi depth (cm)		
	July	August	September
CEA-1	9.5	36	8
CEA-2	7	15	8
CEA-3	10	17	9
CEA-4	8.5	23	8
CEA-5	10	18	8
Mean ± SD	9.00 ±1.14	21.80 ±7.57	8.20 ±0.44

D.2 Bioinformatic analysis

Table 2 shows the number of reads obtained from 96 water samples collected from Lake Cajititlán. A total of 6,075,574 raw reads were sequenced for the hypervariable region V3-V4 of the 16S rRNA gene. From these, 42.71% were classified as bacteria using both the SILVA reference database and RDP, where cyanobacteria represented 0.45% and 0.53%, respectively for each database. Unclassified reads represented 57.29% for SILVA and 57.24% for RDP. A total of 3,189,413 raw reads were sequenced for the V4 region of 18S rRNA gene and classified using the

PR² reference database. From these, 67% were classified as eukaryotic, and microalgae represented 61.74%. Unclassified reads represented 32.95% of total eukaryotic sequences.

Table 2. Number of reads obtained from sequencing data analysis.

Gene region	Raw reads	Classified reads		Unclassified reads
		SILVA	RDP	
V3-V4 16S rRNA	6,075,574	Bacteria:	Bacteria:	Silva:
		2,594,766	2,597,984	3,480,808
		Cyanobacteria:	Cyanobacteria:	RDP:
		11,732	13,741	3,477,590
		(0.45%)	(0.53%)	
PR²				
V4		Eukaryotes:		
18S rRNA	3,189,413	2,138,457		1,050,956
		Microalgae:		
		1,320,388		
		(61.74%)		

Figure 8A shows the general results of the bacteria taxonomic annotation pipeline, in which very similar taxonomic classification results (bacterial phyla) were obtained using SILVA *vs.* RPD (Figure 8A, Table 3). The three most abundant phyla were Proteobacteria (SILVA: 44.79%, RDP: 44.89%), Bacteroidetes (SILVA: 34.42%, RDP: 33.92%) and Actinobacteria (SILVA: 9.54%, RDP: 9.62%). Although the abundance and composition of bacteria were very similar in both databases, some differences can be observed for Parcubacteria (0.18%, found only through RDP) and Patescibacteria (0.38%, found only in SILVA). This proportion of heterotrophic bacteria is only presented as a comparison to the proportion of cyanobacteria present in Lake Cajititlán in the different databases. The highest proportion of reads classified as cyanobacteria were found in the RDP database (0.52%); therefore, for subsequent bioinformatic analysis, only these cyanobacteria data were used.

Figure 8. Bacteria and eukaryotic phyla relative read abundance from different databases. A: Relative read abundance of bacteria phyla from different databases (RDP and SILVA); B: Relative read abundance of eukaryotes from PR2 database.

Table 3. Percentage of reads classified as bacterial phyla > 0.1% using SILVA version 132 and RDP version 11 databases. * The Parcubacteria phylum was only found through RDP and the Patescibacteria phylum was only found in the SILVA database.

Phyla >0.1%	SILVA %	RDP %
Actinobacteria	9.54	9.62
Bacteroidetes	34.42	33.92
Chlamydiae	0.18	0.17
Chloroflexi	0.37	0.36
Cyanobacteria	0.45	0.53
Firmicutes	4.90	4.61
*Patescibacteria/Parcubacteria	0.38	0.18
Planctomycetes	2.32	2.30
Proteobacteria	44.79	44.89
Tenericutes	0.12	0.11
Verrucomicrobia	2.22	2.21
Un Bacteria	0.29	1.10

The analysis of relative read abundance of eukaryotes shows that Archaeplastida (42.20%), Opisthokonta (22.08%) and Stramenopiles (19.17%) phyla were the most abundant in Lake Cajititlán during this study, which contain some taxonomic groups of microalgae (Table 4). Some microalgae can also be grouped in the less abundant eukaryotic phyla, such as Aleovata (1.29%) and Hacrobia (0.28%) (Fig. 8B, Table 4). The rarefaction curve shows that samples reached an asymptote (Fig. 9).

Table 4. Percentage of reads classified as classes of eukaryotes > 0.1% using the PR² version 4.12.0 database.

Phyla >0.1%	PR² %
Alveolata	1.29
Amoebozoa	0.23
Archaeplastida	42.20
Hacrobia	0.28
Opisthokonta	22.08
Rhizaria	0.15
Stramenopiles	19.17
Un Eukaryota	14.59

Figure 9. Rarefaction curve of 16S and 18S rRNA gene samples.

D.3. Spatial and temporal variations of the diversity and abundance of phytoplankton communities

Richness and diversity of cyanobacterial and microalgal communities at different sites and sampling months were assessed using the Chao1, Simpson and Shannon-Weaver indices (Wu *et al.*, 2019; Carey *et al.*, 2013) (Fig. 10). The richness estimated by Chao1 and the diversity indicated by the Shannon index showed significant increases in the cyanobacterial communities during the study period (from July to September), whereas no differences were shown by the Simpson index (Fig. 10A, Table 5). Microalgae richness also significantly increased from July to September; however, diversity remained unchanged (Fig. 10B, Table 7). Changes in precipitation and increased nutrient runoff were observed, as reported for other tropical subtropical lakes (Moss *et al.*, 2011; Havens and Jeppesen, 2018). There were no significant spatial variations for cyanobacteria or microalgae communities (Fig. 10C and 10D; Table 6 and 8). Shallow lakes regularly display a polymictic character with complete mixing events during summer, mainly due to precipitation and wind, which results in destratification and complete mixing of the water column (Kerimoglu and Rinke, 2013; Cavicchioli *et al.*, 2019; Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2020a; do Nascimento-Moura *et al.*, 2012).

Figure 10. Box plots for diversity and richness indices of the cyanobacterial and microalgal communities in different months and sampling sites. A: cyanobacterial communities by sampling month; B: microalgal communities by sampling month; C: cyanobacterial communities by sampling site; D: microalgal communities by sampling site.

Table 5. ANOVA results for cyanobacteria diversity indices by sampling month.

Diversity index	Sum of squares	Mean squares	P-value
Shannon	2.55	1.27	0.002
Chao1	70.36	35.18	0.00004
Simpson	0.67	0.33	0.141

Table 6. ANOVA results for cyanobacteria diversity indices by sampling site.

Diversity index	Sum of squares	Mean squares	P-value
Shannon	0.38	0.09	0.78
Chao1	2.9	0.71	0.94
Simpson	0.834	0.20	0.30

Table 7. ANOVA results for microalgae diversity indices by sampling month.

Diversity index	Sum of squares	Mean squares	P-value
Shannon	0.16	0.08	0.50
Chao1	24.67	12.33	0.01
Simpson	0.05	0.02	0.44

Table 8. ANOVA results for microalgae diversity indices by sampling site.

Diversity index	Sum of squares	Mean squares	P-value
Shannon	0.51	0.12	0.37
Chao1	7.26	1.81	0.69
Simpson	0.13	0.03	0.36

According to relative read abundance, *Planktothrix* and *Cylindropermopsis* were consistently the most abundant cyanobacterial genera across all sampling sites (58.01% and 24.43%, respectively) and months (47.37% and 37.80%, respectively) of this study, which have been dominant in other tropical or subtropical lakes studies (Fig. 11A and 11B; Table 9 and 10) (Barros *et al.*, 2017; Guellati *et al.*, 2017; Gallina *et al.*, 2011; Jöhnk *et al.*, 2008; Michalak, 2016). Other groups that

were not able to be classified at the genus level were Un. Gastranaerophilales and Un. Nostocaceae. Any groups of cyanobacteria with less than 0.01% relative read abundance were classified as “others”.

Figure 11. Relative read abundance of cyanobacterial and microalgae communities by month and sampling point. A: cyanobacteria genera relative read abundance by sampling month; B: cyanobacteria genera relative read abundance by sampling point; C: microalgae classes relative read abundance by sampling month; D: microalgae classes relative read abundance by sampling point.

Table 9. Percentage of relative abundance of the two most abundant genera of cyanobacteria by sampling site.

Cyanobacteria	CEA-1	CEA-2	CEA-3	CEA-4	CEA-5	Mean of all sites
<i>Planktothrix</i>	66.11%	35.44%	71.93%	77.85%	38.76%	58.01%

<i>Cylindrospermopsis</i>	16.48%	51.76%	4.26%	1.20%	48.45%	24.43%
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Table 10. Percentage of relative abundance of the two most abundant genera of cyanobacteria by sampling month.

Cyanobacteria	July	August	September	Mean of all months
<i>Planktothrix</i>	20.57%	73.89%	47.67%	47.37%
<i>Cylindrospermopsis</i>	62.59%	10.05%	37.80%	37.80%

For microalgae communities, it was not possible to classify the reads at the genus level, and therefore, they were analyzed at the class level. The top two most abundant microalgae classes were Chlorophyceae and Chrysophyceae. Chlorophyceae was the most abundant at all sampling sites and months (57% and 57.12% respectively), except for the month of August, when Chrysophyceae was the dominant class (51.55%) (Fig. 11C, 11D; Table 11 and Table 12). Chlorophyceae is a dominant class in tropical eutrophic shallow lakes, whereas Chrysophyceae is considered characteristic of oligotrophic and mesotrophic waters (Silva *et al.*, 2014; Chellappa *et al.*, 2008; Kristiansen, 1985). However, its dominance in subtropical and eutrophic water bodies has been detected during the summer season, with its presence being associated with the addition of allochthonous nutrients (Munch, 1980; Shi *et al.*, 2019).

Table 11. Percentage of relative abundance of the two most abundant class of microalgae by sampling site.

Microalgae	CEA-1	CEA-2	CEA-3	CEA-4	CEA-5	Mean of all sites
Chlorophyceae	34.90%	58.50%	75.71%	63.26%	52.66%	57%
Chrysophyceae	50.19%	16.39%	<0.01%	13.06%	15.40%	19.01%

Table 12. Percentage of relative abundance of the two most abundant class of microalgae by sampling month.

Microalgae	July	August	September	Mean of all months
Chlorophyceae	64.04%	35.02%	72.32%	57.12%
Chrysophyceae	5.7%	51.55%	<0.01%	19.08%

To analyze spatial and temporal changes in the composition of cyanobacteria and microalgae communities, a principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) was performed based on Bray-Curtis distances (Fig. 12). The temporal analysis of cyanobacteria (ANOSIM $R = 0.0931$, $P=0.005$) and microalgae (ANOSIM $R= 0.1209$, $P= 0.001$) reflected a temporary transition between the months of July and September (Fig. 12A, 12C) (Table 13). In tropical regions, this behavior reflects the seasonal climatic changes, which alters rainfall and the biogeochemical processes that makes nutrients available to a greater extent for these communities (Sarmiento *et al.*, 2013; Steffen *et al.*, 2015; Greaver *et al.*, 2016). Similar community compositions of cyanobacteria (ANOSIM $R= -0.02209$, $P= 0.249$) and microalgae (ANOSIM $R= -0.01543$, $P=0.280$) were observed at all sampling points (Fig. 12B, 12D) (Table 13).

Figure 12. Principal coordinates analysis (PCoA) of the dissimilarities among microbial communities by month and sampling point using the Bray-Curtis distances. A: PCoA of cyanobacterial communities by sampling month; B: PCoA of cyanobacterial communities by sampling point; C: PCoA of microalgae communities by sampling month; D: PCoA of microalgae communities by sampling point.

Table 13. PerMANOVA and ANOSIM analysis of the composition of cyanobacteria and microalgae at different months and sampling sites. * Represents statistical significance ($P < 0.05$).

Microorganism	ANOSIM R	P-Value
Cyanobacteria	Month: 0.0931	Month: 0.005*
	Sampling Point: -0.0221	Sampling Point: 0.249
Microalgae	Month: 0.1209	Month: 0.001*
	Sampling Point: -0.0154	Sampling Point: 0.266

To analyze the spatial and temporal changes in the composition of the cyanobacterial and microalgal communities, a principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) based on the Bray-Curtis distances was performed (Fig. 12). The temporal analysis of cyanobacteria (ANOSIM $R = 0.0931$, $P = 0.005$) and microalgae (ANOSIM $R = 0.1209$, $P = 0.001$) revealed a temporal transition between the months of July and September with 55.67% of the variance total explained by the three main eigenvalues for cyanobacteria and 35.1% for microalgae (Table 13, 14 and 15). In cyanobacteria, the first two eigenvalues explained 24.10% and 22% of the total variation in the data during the sampling months, while in microalgae, the first two eigenvalues explained 18.36% and 10.79% of the total variation (Fig. 12 and 12C). In tropical regions, this behavior reflects seasonal climate changes, which alter rainfall and biogeochemical processes that make nutrients more available to these communities (Sarmiento *et al.*, 2013; Steffen *et al.*, 2015; Greaver *et al.*, 2016). Similar community compositions of cyanobacteria (ANOSIM $R = -0.02209$, $P = 0.249$) and microalgae (ANOSIM $R = -0.01543$, $P = 0.280$) were observed at all sampling points (Fig. 12B and 12D; Table 13).

Table 14. Eigenvalue percentage for principal components of PCoA of cyanobacteria by sampling month.

Principal components	% Eigenvalue
PC1	24.10
PC2	22.00
PC3	9.57
PC3	6.69
PC5	4.77
PC6	3.14

Table 15. Eigenvalue percentage for principal components of PCoA of microalgae by sampling month.

Principal components	% Eigenvalue
PC1	18.36
PC2	10.79
PC3	5.95
PC3	5.52
PC5	4.89
PC6	4.17

D.4. Quantification of total microcystin concentration

The total microcystin content in the lake water samples is shown in Table 16. The lowest concentrations of this toxin (<0.15 µg/L) corresponded to the following sampling sites and depths: CEA-2 (1.9 m) and CEA-4 (2.9 m). Conversely, the highest concentrations of this toxin 0.880 µg/L and 0.750 µg/L corresponded to sampling sites CEA-1 (30 cm) and CEA-5 (30 cm), respectively. Moreover, the highest concentrations were detected on the surface of the lake, where one would expect to find the highest concentration of cyanobacteria, forming part of the algal blooms in Lake Cajititlán. One-way ANOVAs ($\alpha = 0.05$) were performed to observe the difference in total microcystin concentration by site and sampling depth, both of which showed no significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

Table 16. Total microcystin concentration in water samples from Lake Cajititlán. P-value by sampling depth was 0.05, P-value by sampling site was 0.39.

Sampling site	Mean concentration of total microcystin at 30 cm depth (µg/L)	Mean concentration of total microcystin at maximum depth (µg/L)
CEA-1	0.880	0.459 (1.4 m)
CEA-2	0.683	< 0.15 (1.9 m)
CEA-3	0.210	< 0.15 (3 m)
CEA-4	0.315	< 0.15 (2.9 m)
CEA-5	0.750	0.330 (2.7 m)

E. Discussion

E.1. Climatological and water quality characteristics of Lake Cajititlán

The present study revealed that the composition of the phytoplankton community in Lake Cajititlán displayed significant temporal changes during the study period caused by the rainy season (Fig. 12 and 10). Additionally, the findings of this study suggest that significant rainfall variations cause extreme seasonal surface runoff and rapid changes in the water quality (Chlorophyll-*a*, DO, NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻) of this subtropical lake, as well as rapid variations in the phytoplankton community (Fig. 6, 7, 10 and 12). Studies on the temporal variations in the phytoplankton community have been carried out in temperate regions, but only a few have been reported in tropical or subtropical regions, such as Lake Cajititlán (Limón Macías *et al.*, 1983; Quevedo-Castro *et al.*, 2019; Li *et al.*, 2018; Riediger *et al.*, 2015; Ma *et al.*, 2019; Umaña-Villalobos, 2010). The wet season in tropical and subtropical areas exacerbates the cultural eutrophication of surface water bodies when there is intensive agricultural activity in their basin (Cunha *et al.*, 2013; Barbosa, 2009). Tropical and subtropical water bodies are also susceptible to other anthropogenic sources of pollutants from urban areas (e.g., wastewater effluents) due to less efficient wastewater treatment facilities. Some causes of inadequate wastewater treatment in developing countries in tropical or subtropical regions are the lack of funds, restricted local budgets, and the lack of local expertise, leading to a deficit in the construction and satisfactory operation of treatment facilities (Paraskevas *et al.*, 2002). These results coincide with the behavior of the TN:TP ratio and the water quality parameters (Chlorophyll-*a*, DO, NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻), which presented greater variation during the rainy season, and which directly affect the water quality index of the Cajititlán Lake.

Tropical and subtropical bodies of water show major changes in their water quality and biotic communities in response to eutrophication (Gillett *et al.*, 2016). The pronounced wet season in these regions causes modifications in the physical and chemical characteristics of the water and highly influences phytoplankton dynamics (Figueredo and Giani, 2009). Furthermore, as a result of tropical and subtropical climatic conditions, the biomass production potential of phytoplankton, on a given nutrient basis, can be expected to be higher in tropical lakes than in temperate lakes (Lewis, 1974). Specifically, in lake Cajititlán, rainfall has been reported to cause significant changes in the concentrations of the main forms of dissolved inorganic nitrogen, such

as NH_4^+ and NO_3^- . These nitrogenous compounds increase at the beginning of the wet season due to the surficial runoff containing high loads of nutrients, later to generate a dilution effect as the water level increases throughout the wet season (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2020b). This is consistent with the results of the current study, as the concentrations of NH_4^+ and NO_3^- were higher in the first sampling (July) (Fig. 7A) and decreased through the rainy season (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2020b). In this study and as reported by de Anda *et al.* (2019b), a high content of BGA-PC and Chlorophyll-*a* was detected (Fig. 7).

Both phosphorus and nitrogen are essential elements for the growth of phytoplankton and for primary production (Carpenter *et al.*, 1998). Phosphorus has been considered the most important nutrient in the control of phytoplankton in lakes at high latitudes, but in the case of tropical and subtropical regions, it has been suggested that nitrogen is the limiting nutrient in some cases (Vincent *et al.*, 1984; Ramos-Higuera *et al.*, 2008). This is expected as natural sources of phosphorus can be traced to the chemical weathering of rock, which is a thermally sensitive process that occurs at considerably higher rates where the temperature is higher (Meybeck 1979). However, historically, Lake Cajititlán was more phosphorus-limited at the beginning (June-July) and at the end of the rainy season (September) and in the intermediate time (August), it appeared to be more nitrogen-limited (Fig. 7F). In July, after the onset of the rainy season, there are many nitrogen sources of pollution that are carried to the lake by runoff. Rain episodes can be very intense in tropical or subtropical regions and result in heavy runoff of nitrogenous compounds into water bodies (Cunha *et al.*, 2013). However, in August these forms of nitrogen decrease rapidly as there is an increase in the community of phytoplankton than consume these compounds (Fig. 7A). This indicates the intensification of the nitrification and denitrification processes. After cyanobacteria fix molecular nitrogen (N_2), $\text{NH}_4^+/\text{NH}_3$ are converted into nitrites (NO_2^-) by a group of bacteria of the *Nitrosomes* genus, to be later converted to NO_3^- by bacteria of the genus *Nitrobacter*, which are further metabolized by aquatic plants and algae (Hem, 1985; Raven *et al.*, 1992; Cabello *et al.*, 2009; Prangnell *et al.*, 2019).

Cyanobacteria not only have the ability to fix N_2 but also have the ability to assimilate nitrogen from a number of N-containing compounds, such as NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , NO_2^- and urea. In fact, several experimental and *in situ* studies have shown that cyanobacteria appear to outcompete other

phytoplankton species for reduced forms of N (Flores and Herrero, 2005; Cronberg and Annadotter, 2006; Blomqvist *et al.*, 1994; Ferber *et al.*, 2004; McCarthy *et al.*, 2009). This information is consistent with the large increase of cyanobacteria compared to microalgae observed in this study (Fig. 10A and 10B). One of the symptoms of degraded water quality is the increase of phytoplankton biomass as measured by the concentration of Chlorophyll-*a*. Chlorophyll-*a* concentrations are often higher after rainfall, particularly if the rain has flushed nutrients into the water. Receiving waters with high levels of nutrients from fertilizers, septic systems, sewage treatment plants and urban runoff may have high concentrations of Chlorophyll-*a* and high amounts of phytoplankton (Wellman *et al.*, 2002; Ward *et al.*, 1998; Monbet, 1992; Nixon, 1992; Brando *et al.*, 2006; Scanes *et al.*, 2007; Hinga *et al.*, 1995). In this study, an increase of Chlorophyll-*a* was observed (July to September), indicative of nutrients being flushed into the lake during the rainy season (Fig. 10A).

In addition to being aesthetically unpleasant, cyanobacterial blooms manifest as a reduction in water transparency that can inhibit the growth of aquatic macrophytes due to limited light accessibility; this subsequently disrupts invertebrate and fish habitats (Paerl *et al.*, 2001; Pick, 2016). (Li, 1998; Scheffer *et al.*, 1993). Furthermore, combined wastewater/rainfall enters Lake Cajititlán without any treatment, because WWTPs do not have separate pipes for wastewater *vs.* rainfall water (de Anda *et al.* 2019b; Gradilla-Hernández *et al.* 2020a). This is reflected in the results of the Secchi depth measurements and in the higher values of NH_4^+ and NO_3^- in July (Table 1, Fig. 7A). In August, the water transparency of Lake Cajititlán improved, probably due to the dilution effect generated by the rains (Martínez-Urtaza *et al.* 2004). However, the Secchi depth decreased again in September, which could indicate that due to the high availability of nutrients in the lake, growth of the phytoplankton community may be triggered, as observed in the increase in Chlorophyll-*a* throughout the study (Fig. 7).

E.2. Spatial stability of the phytoplankton community

A previous study on Lake Cajititlán reported spatial variations for these physicochemical parameters - pH, NO_3^- and NO_2^- (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2020a). The authors correlated these variations with the configuration of the lake, since CEA-2 to CEA-4 are at the center of the lake, while CEA-1 and CEA-5 are at the west and east sides, respectively. This current study is

consistent with the results of that previous study, as only a few parameters, BGA-PC, NH_4^+ and WT, gave the most significant variations, which were mainly found at the CEA-1 sampling site (Fig. 7B). This sampling site is the closest to the San Miguel Cuyutlán WWTP (Fig. 5), which is the plant with the highest capacity (60 L/s) and processes the largest volume of municipal wastewater, which it discharges directly into the lake without tertiary treatment (Gobierno del Estado de Jalisco, 2014; de Anda *et al.*, 2019). Likewise, in the CEA-1 sampling site, a higher dilution range of BGA-PC was found, which suggests that the WWTP point-source pollution favored the development of this population. Municipal wastewater can contain nitrogen and phosphorus compounds from human waste as well as from soaps and detergents. This condition can facilitate the growth of cyanobacteria in water bodies if these nutrients are not properly eliminated (Gomes de Quevedo and Da Silva, 2016; Rapala and Sivonen, 1998).

E.3. Dynamics and abundance of the dominant taxa of Lake Cajititlán

The genera *Planktothrix* and *Cylindrospermopsis* were the dominant groups of cyanobacteria (Fig. 11). This finding is similar to the results found in other freshwater studies, which report the dominance of any of these two genera (Barros *et al.*, 2017; Bonilla *et al.*, 2012; Lira *et al.*, 2011; Guellati *et al.*, 2017). *Planktothrix* is one of the most important microcystin-producing genera in temperate lakes (Fastner *et al.*, 1999; Vasas *et al.*, 2013). However, very few articles have reported *Planktothrix* as a predominant genus for tropical and subtropical areas (Guellati *et al.*, 2017; Reynolds *et al.*, 2002; Gallina *et al.*, 2011; Jöhnk *et al.*, 2008; Michalak, 2016; Barros *et al.*, 2017).

Within the *Planktothrix* genus, it is frequently the *P. agardhii* and *P. rubescens* species that dominate the phytoplankton community in the water column (Kurmayer *et al.*, 2016). *P. agardhii* and *P. rubescens* are known to be the most efficient light harvesters within the phytoplankton community, which is, in part, due to their possession of specific accessory pigments, namely the phycobilins (phycoerythrin, phycocyanin (BGA-PC) and allophycocyanin) (Kurmayer *et al.*, 2016). The red-pigmented phycoerythrin (PE)-rich genotypes are found in *P. rubescens*, while the green-pigmented phycocyanin (PC)-rich genotypes are frequently found in *P. agardhii* (Komárek and Komárková, 2004). In this study, only the BGA-PC phycobilin was analyzed (Fig. 7A), and it was mainly found to be associated with the *P. agardhii* species, since *Planktothrix* was the most

abundant genus. In addition, Lake Cajititlán is located in a subtropical region, which contains environmental conditions that are advantageous for *P. agardhii*, since it has been reported in shallow and subtropical lakes (Suda *et al.*, 2002; Kruk *et al.*, 2002; Bouchamma *et al.*, 2004; Baker and Humpage, 1994).

The genus *Cylindrospermopsis* was the second most abundant in this study, and the most abundant during August (Fig. 11A). This genus was originally found only in tropical and subtropical regions, but it has now expanded into temperate areas (Haande *et al.*, 2008). In México there are few reports of this cyanobacteria. *C. raciborskii* is one species that has been identified (Komárek and Komárkova-Legnerová, 2002; Valadez *et al.*, 2005). Most of the studies on *C. raciborskii* have been carried out on reservoirs used for agriculture or recreation, and in some cases on drinking water sources (Lei *et al.*, 2014; Menezes *et al.*, 2020). Agriculture is one of the main activities in Lake Cajititlán, so it is possible that the abundance of this bacterium is associated with the increase in the concentration of nutrients from fertilizers, mainly during the rainy season, which enhances the runoff of nutrients to the lake. This effect has been observed in several subtropical studies (Li *et al.*, 2010; Munch, 1980; Shy *et al.*, 2019).

In this study, Chlorophyceae (54.02%), Chrysophyceae (23.42%) and Trebouxiophyceae (13.24%) were the most representative microalgal taxonomic classes, suggesting that these microalgae families could be participating in the algal blooms observed in Lake Cajititlán. Andrade and Giroldo (2014), reported similar results in a shallow subtropical lake, where they found Chlorophyceae (30.8%) and Bacillariophyceae (24.8%), followed by Cyanophyceae (13.6%), Chrysophyceae (9.3%), Euglenophyceae (7.0%) and Zygnematophyceae (6.5%) to be the most represented taxonomic classes in terms of richness. In some lakes of volcanic origin in Mexico, the presence of Trebouxiophyceae has been reported; these lakes are also endorheic, and they are located in regions where the rainy season runs from June to September (Instituto de Geografía, 1990; Godínez-Ortega *et al.*, 2017).

Shallow lakes such as Lake Cajititlán, generally exhibit fluctuations between various phytoplankton states (Nixdorf *et al.*, 2003). A phytoplankton community is considered to be in steady state when (i): one, two or three species contribute more than 80% of the biomass; (ii) their

existence or coexistence persists for more than two weeks; and (iii) the total biomass does not increase significantly during the period analyzed (Sommer *et al.*, 1993). In this study, a clear steady state was observed in the cyanobacteria community. The most abundant genera found in this study, *Planktothrix* and *Cylindrospermopsis* (at 80.58%), persisted and coexisted throughout the study period (Fig. 11A). Some studies have shown that an equilibrium condition with cyanobacterial dominance could be expected in some steady state environments. However, several factors can influence the prevalence of cyanobacteria in phytoplankton communities, such as the water temperature, the mixing of the water column, the rainfall and the limiting nutrients, among others (Figueredo and Giani, 2009). Similarly, Nixdor *et al.* (2003) reported a steady state condition dominated by *Planktothrix* in shallow eutrophic lakes. Regarding the microalgae classes, a steady state could not be established because these classes were not constant in abundance during the study (Fig. 11C).

The TN:TP ratio can be used to understand the dynamics of N and P in the aquatic system, and it can likewise be employed as a diagnostic criterion to assess the type of phytoplankton found under different nutrient, namely nitrogen and phosphorus, concentrations (Gržetić and Camprag, 2010; Smith, 1983). The trend in the relative abundance of *Planktothrix* and *Cylindrospermopsis* (Fig. 11A) contrasted with the trend of the TN:TP ratio (Fig. 6E), uncovering possible relationships between the TN:TP ratio and the relative abundances of specific cyanobacteria populations. When phosphorus was found to be the limiting nutrient (July and September), the abundance of the *Planktothrix* genus was higher, and when the limiting nutrient was nitrogen, *Cylindrospermopsis* presented a higher abundance. Interestingly, *Cylindrospermopsis* is known to be found in higher abundances in tropical lakes, where nitrogen is commonly the limiting nutrient (Haande *et al.*, 2008; Talling and Lemoalle, 1998) and *Planktothrix* is frequently found in temperate and mesotrophic lakes where phosphorus limitation is common (Welch and Naczk, 1992; Fastner *et al.*, 1999; Vasas *et al.*, 2013; Orr and Jones, 1998).

E.4. Fish mortality in Lake Cajititlán

Based on Lake Cajititlán's seasonal characterization and water quality characteristics presented herein and in previous reports (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2018, 2020a, 2020b; de Anda *et al.*, 2019a, 2019b), the problem of fish kills is attributable to the eutrophication problem of this

reservoir. Eutrophication is enhanced during the rainy season, due to an increase in the concentration of nutrients from fertilizers, sewage treatment plants and urban runoff, triggering a surge in the growth of phytoplankton communities (Fig. 10). In this study, the lowest DO concentrations were recorded during August when concentrations below 2 mg/L⁻¹ were measured. These low DO concentrations may be related to wastewater discharge from the WWTPs or to the enrichment of nutrients of the lake through surficial runoff. This is consistent with the fact that July and August displayed the highest levels of nutrients (NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻), which could favor the growth of phytoplankton populations (Fig. 7A). DO concentrations of 5 mg/L or more are suitable for most aquatic organisms, and concentrations below 2 mg/L are considered hypoxic (Wu, 2009). Possible signs of a fish kill due to oxygen depletion are sluggish fish movements, fish gasping at the surface, larger fish dying earlier than smaller fish of the same species, and episodes occurring at night or in the early morning, as DO varies significantly between day and night in eutrophic water bodies (Helfrich and Smith, 2010; Nguyen *et al.*, 2016). This diurnal phenomenon commonly occurs in eutrophic lakes, because, during the day, the intensity of radiation increases photosynthetic activity, while at night, DO is reduced significantly through respiration of the phytoplankton community, and release of carbon dioxide (CO₂). When the CO₂ levels in water become too high, fish have difficulty obtaining sufficient oxygen from the water, resulting in suffocation and death (Mallya and Thorarensen, 2007; Nguyen *et al.* 2016). This process was reported by Gradilla-Hernández *et al.* (2020a) for Lake Cajititlán, where significantly lower values of dissolved oxygen were found during nocturnal monitoring. During the sampling process of the present study, fish were observed gasping at the surface and dead fish were also seen floating (Fig. 13). These events were documented at 7 a.m. on July 15, 2019. Therefore, the results found in this study are consistent with what had been previously established: that fish kills in Lake Cajititlán during the rainy season could be related to a decrease in water quality, resulting in an increase in phytoplankton communities, leading to the depletion of DO in the water.

Figure 13. A fish death event that was observed during sampling in June 2018, at 7:00 AM.

Although there is strong evidence to suggest that the fish kills in Lake Cajititlán have resulted mainly from anoxia, in this study, we investigated the microcystin concentration as another factor that could be associated with these events. Two of the main genera of microcystin-producing cyanobacteria (*Microcystis* spp., and *Planktothrix* spp.) were detected (Kaebernick and Neilan, 2001; Gupta *et al.*, 2003). The highest concentration of microcystin detected in Lake Cajititlán was 0.880 $\mu\text{g/L}$. Concentrations <1 $\mu\text{g/L}$ have may not stress fish but could influence their behavior and could impair development (Bury *et al.*, 1996; Baganz *et al.*, 1998; Wiegand *et al.*, 1999). However, there are studies that report harmful effects (including mortalities) in fish at different life stages at microcystin concentrations ranging from 0.08 $\mu\text{g/L}$ to 500 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (Ernst *et al.*, 2001; Liu *et al.*, 2000; Oberemm *et al.*, 1999 and 1997). Additionally, several researchers have analyzed the content of microcystin in fish tissues and have reported that there is accumulation of microcystin in different tissues, which can cause reduction in the embryonic development of fish, as well as pathophysiological, histological, and ultrastructural damage (Papadimitriou *et al.*, 2012; Zhang *et al.*, 2007; Atencio *et al.*, 2008; Jos *et al.*, 2005; Prieto *et al.*,

2006; Bury *et al.*, 1997). Unfortunately, the content of this toxin in fish tissues was not analyzed, so it is necessary to carry out further studies to determine if there is bioaccumulation and possible toxicological effects.

Fish kills can severely reduce the productivity of recreational and commercial fisheries, and as a result, economic loss can be substantial. The eutrophication problem in Lake Cajititlán has affected fishing activity with the death of thousands of fish in recent years (Alatorre, 2015). The local fishermen have limited economic opportunities without this activity (Velázquez-López *et al.*, 2012).

F. Conclusions

This study revealed that the composition of the phytoplankton community in Lake Cajititlán changed rapidly, and that the population increased throughout the study period. These trends were the result of the rainy season, which causes high seasonal surface runoff and therefore rapid changes in the water quality (Chlorophyll-*a*, DO, NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻). Within the cyanobacterial community, it was found that *Planktothrix* and *Cylindrospermopsis* were the dominant genera of the cyanobacterial community, while the Chlorophyceae, Chrysophyceae and Trebouxiophyceae classes were the most abundant within the microalgae community. Some species of the genus *Planktothrix* are considered potentially toxic because they have the capacity to produce microcystins, which were detected in this study between 0.210-0.880 ug/L⁻¹. Finally, the TN:TP ratio presented an alternating trend indicating that Lake Cajititlán is limited by phosphorus at the onset and at the end (July and September, respectively) of the rainy season, and more nitrogen-limited during the intermediate month (August) of this season. The trend observed in the relative abundance of *Planktothrix* and *Cylindrospermopsis* (Fig. 11A) contrasted with the trend of TN:TP ratio (Fig. 6E), uncovering possible relationships between the TN:TP ratio and the relative abundances of specific cyanobacteria populations.

The evidence presented in this study showed that the death of fish in Lake Cajititlán could be related mainly by anoxia, caused by the rapid changes in DO levels as a result of phytoplankton blooms. These blooms were the result of nutrients entering the lake through runoff during the rainy season. Special attention should be given to small and shallow endorheic lakes located in

subtropical areas. In these systems, seasonal rainfall events result in large inputs of pollutants into freshwater systems, which in turn rapidly affect the phytoplankton community.

Although monthly sampling revealed relevant trends and patterns in the joint behavior of the TN:TP ratio, the climatic conditions, and the phytoplankton abundance data during the rainy season (especially when analyzing the relative abundance of *Planktothix* and *Cylindrospermopsis*), future studies are warranted to confirm and deepen the understanding of the dynamics of these communities through weekly sampling. More frequent sampling of both abundance and of water quality, in addition to daily or weekly measurements of climatic variables would strengthen what is known regarding the changing behavior of subtropical water bodies during the rainy season, specifically those that are strongly affected by anthropogenic activity. To improve the characterization of microbial taxonomic level, future studies will be carried out by shotgun sequencing of selected samples. This will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the microbial communities in Lake Cajititlán, thus shedding light onto the metabolic changes that may be occurring, which allow these microorganisms to adapt to their environment.

**CHAPTER III: BACTERIAL DYNAMICS
AND THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE
BIOGEOCHEMICAL CYCLES**

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Chapter III presents an investigation of the temporal dynamics of bacterial communities within Lake Cajititlán and their genes associated with the nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and carbon biogeochemical cycles during the rainy season using high-throughput 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing and a functional inference approach (PICRUSt). Furthermore, the influence of physicochemical and environmental variables on these microbial dynamics was also analyzed. The chapter's conclusions were that temporal variations in the structure and abundance of Lake Cajititlán's bacterial communities were observed; these variations are attributed to high susceptibility of these communities to nutrient loads that reach via surface runoff to this reservoir and increase during the rainy season. In addition, these nutrient inputs could cause the bacterial communities to have a higher relative read abundance of genes associated with different metabolic pathways of the nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur cycles. The provided findings contribute to a better understanding of the bidirectional relationships between bacterial populations and the main biogeochemical processes in eutrophic subtropical lakes.

Original Research

Bacterial Dynamics and Their Influence on the Biogeochemical Cycles in a Subtropical Hypereutrophic Lake During the Rainy Season

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A. Summary

Lakes in subtropical regions are highly susceptible to eutrophication due to the heavy rainfall, which causes significant runoff of pollutants (e.g., nutrients) to reach surface waters, altering the water quality and influencing the microbial communities that regulate the biogeochemical cycles within these ecosystems. Lake Cajititlán is a shallow, subtropical, and endorheic lake in western Mexico. Nutrient pollution from agricultural activity and wastewater discharge have affected the lake's water quality, leading the reservoir to a hypereutrophic state, resulting in episodes of fish mortality during the rainy season. This study investigated the temporal dynamics of bacterial communities within Lake Cajititlán and their genes associated with the nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and carbon biogeochemical cycles during the rainy season, as well as the influences of physicochemical and environmental variables on such dynamics. Significant temporal variations were observed in the composition of bacterial communities, of which *Flavobacterium* and

Pseudomonas were the dominant genera. The climatological parameters that were most correlated with the bacterial communities and their functional profiles were pH, DO, ORP, turbidity, TN, EC, NH_4^+ , and NO_3^- . The bacterial communities displayed variations in their functional composition for nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur metabolisms during the sampling months. The bacterial communities within the lake are highly susceptible to nutrient loads and low DO levels during the rainy season. Bacterial communities had a higher relative abundance of genes associated with denitrification, nitrogen fixation, assimilatory sulfate reduction, cysteine, SOX system, and all phosphorus metabolic pathways. The results obtained here enrich our understanding of the bidirectional interactions between bacterial communities and major biogeochemical processes in eutrophic subtropical lakes.

B. Introduction

One of the most important climatological attributes of tropical and subtropical regions is their heavy rainfall, which causes significant nutrient runoff from agricultural areas to surface waters. Additionally, the high temperatures and primary productivity that occur in these areas throughout the year make the superficial water sources highly susceptible to cultural eutrophication in comparison to temperate environments, where spring and summer are the more productive seasons (Cunha *et al.*, 2013; Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2018, 2019, and 2020). While rainfall and temperature can significantly alter the physical, chemical, and biological features of lakes in these regions, their water quality is the result of a complex set of multidirectional interactions among several factors, such as the natural and anthropogenic inputs of pollutants, environmental conditions (e.g., temperature and rainfall), the lake's hydrodynamics, and *in-situ* biological and chemical processes (e.g., microbial metabolism), among others (Niencheski and Windom, 1994). Furthermore, changes in the water quality of lakes lead to alterations in the microbial communities that regulate the biogeochemical processes within them, such as the sulfur, nitrogen, phosphorus, and carbon cycles (Liu *et al.*, 2018; Wang *et al.*, 2018; Yao *et al.*, 2018); likewise, the metabolic activity of microorganisms greatly influences the water quality of lakes through different biochemical mechanisms (Nielsen *et al.*, 2006; Hupfer and Lewandowski, 2008).

The knowledge regarding the interactions between water quality and biogeochemical processes within lake ecosystems is still limited, particularly in subtropical lakes, which pose an even

greater challenge to understand the structure and activity of bacterial communities within them due to the rapid changes in their microbial communities, mainly caused by rainfall and superficial runoff (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). Thus, there is a need to deepen the understanding on how bacterial metabolism and metabolic interactions drive biogeochemical transformations at the ecosystem scale (Graham *et al.*, 2016; Newton *et al.*, 2011). Metagenomic approaches have developed rapidly and have proven to be powerful for investigating microbial ecology and for linking microbial dynamics to biogeochemical processes (Mackelprang *et al.*, 2011; Fierer *et al.*, 2012; Llorens-Marès *et al.*, 2015). Alternatively, phylogenetic analyses of communities by reconstruction of unobserved states (PICRUSt), employing 16S rRNA gene sequences and a reference genome database, have frequently been used to infer the functional profile of bacterial communities (Langille *et al.*, 2013; Wilkinson *et al.*, 2018). Lake Cajititlán is a small, endorheic, subtropical, shallow lake located in the municipality of Tlajomulco de Zúñiga in the state of Jalisco, Mexico (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). Agriculture is the main economic activity in the basin, and most of the agricultural production takes place during the rainy season (rainfed agriculture), using large amounts of fertilizers and causing nutrient enrichment of the lake via surface runoff (de Anda *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, wastewater is discharged from three wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) located along the reservoir's shoreline, contributing to the nutrient enrichment as these facilities do not provide tertiary treatment to remove nutrients (de Anda *et al.*, 2019). As a result of these sources of nutrient contamination, the lake's water quality and ecological integrity have been significantly affected, bringing the reservoir to a hypereutrophic state, which has manifested through several episodes of fish mortality during the rainy season due to oxygen depletion (hypoxia/anoxia) at night, from 2013 to date (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2018; Anda *et al.*, 2019a).

Understanding the biogeochemical processes in hypoxic and anoxic lakes, such as lake Cajititlán, will guide the efforts to improve water quality and to protect their aquatic life (Arora-Williams *et al.*, 2018). However, most of the previous studies have failed to analyze the relationship between the taxonomic and functional variations of the microbial communities and the physicochemical and environmental variables affecting the water quality of lakes. Additionally, most existing studies have been conducted in temperate and deep-water sources, with the majority focusing on one or two biogeochemical cycles (Staley *et al.*, 2014; Koo *et al.*, 2017; Ren *et al.*, 2017; Arora *et al.*

al., 2018; Kumar *et al.*, 2018; Wu *et al.*, 2019; Li *et al.*, 2020; Wilburn *et al.*, 2020; Oyewusi *et al.*, 2020; Ahmad *et al.*, 2021). Thus, the objective of this study was to analyze the dynamics of bacterial communities within Lake Cajititlán and their genes associated with the functional properties of the main biogeochemical cycles (nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and carbon), as well as the influences of physicochemical and environmental variables on the taxonomic and functional composition of these communities during the rainy season (July–September). Based on our literature review, this is the first study focusing on bacterial diversity and its influence on biogeochemical cycles in a subtropical hypereutrophic lake during the rainy season.

C. Experimental methods

C.1. Study area and field sampling

Lake Cajititlán is a subtropical endorreic lake located at an elevation of 1,550 m a.s.l in the central region of Jalisco, 25 km from the city of Guadalajara, which is the second largest metropolitan area in México (Limón-Macías *et al.*, 1983; Caro-Becerra *et al.*, 2017; Fig. 13). At maximum capacity, the surface area covers 1,744 hectares, the maximum storage volume is 70.89 Hm³, and the maximum depth is 5.4 m (de Anda *et al.*, 2019). The hot-dry season in the region occurs during the months of February to May, the wet season occurs during June to September, and the cold-dry season occurs during October to January (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2019). According to the monthly historical behavior (1998-2018; July–September) of precipitation, evaporation, and air temperature (AT) of Lake Cajititlán, July is the month which receives most rainfall (7.60 mm), followed by August (5.93 mm) and September (5.47 mm). Likewise, in July, the highest mean evaporation (5.39 mm) and the maximum temperature (26.51°C) were observed. The lowest mean minimum temperature was observed in August (12.84°C), followed by September (12.85°C) and July (13.26°C) (Table 17; CONAGUA, 2021). On the other hand, Díaz-Torres *et al.* (2021) reported an annual historical behavior (1998–2018) of TN: TP ratio and the ecosystem-specific water quality index (ES-WQI) for Lake Cajititlán, with July being the month that historically receives greater precipitation and, as a result, an intense runoff of pollutants from the lake, which annually reflects the lowest values of the ES-WQI observed during July as well as the greater variations in the TN: TP ratio observed during the season receiving rains.

Figure 13. Location of the sampling points in Lake Cajititlán.

Table 17. Physicochemical and environmental parameters. The asterisk symbol in the parameters denotes statistical significance among months at the $p < 0.05$ level. Water temperature (WT), dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, electrical conductivity (EC), ammonium (NH_4^+), nitrate (NO_3^-), turbidity, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), blue-green algae (BGA-PC), and air temperature (AT).

Parameters	July	August	September
	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD
DO (mg/L) *	2.83 \pm 0.61	3.25 \pm 1.87	4.32 \pm 1.77
pH*	10 \pm 0.05	9 \pm 0.05	9.28 \pm 0.19
WT ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	24.16 \pm 1.55	24.73 \pm 1.12	24.35 \pm 0.34
Turbidity (NTU)*	97.03 \pm 7.32	41.02 \pm 7.74	68.46 \pm 8.52
ORP (mV)*	47.90 \pm 12.36	66.18 \pm 19.30	101.78 \pm 7.04
NH_4^+ (mg/L) *	4.50 \pm 0.38	4.08 \pm 1.46	2.49 \pm 0.92
NO_3^- (mg/L) *	3.67 \pm 0.34	2.67 \pm 0.56	0.87 \pm 0.24
BGA-PC (cell/mL) *	275,129 \pm 5,551	167,662 \pm 79,268	268,078 \pm 3,996

Chlorophyll-<i>a</i> (µg/L) *	42.16 ± 5.20	42.83 ± 7.40	47.40 ± 9.36
TN (mg/L) *	11.46 ± 1.08	12.88 ± 2.52	9.85 ± 0.63
TP (mg/L) *	1.51 ± 0.06	1.52 ± 0.24	1.41 ± 0.10
EC (mS/cm) *	1.08 ± 0.003	1.21 ± 0.16	1.16 ± 0.12
AT (°C) 2018	22.37 ± 0.90	21.63 ± 1.70	22.19 ± 0.49
Max–Min	24.25-20.75	24-15.5	23-21
Evaporation (mm)			
2018	5.3 ± 1.91	4.77 ± 1.71	4.22 ± 1.76
Max–Min	12-2.1	10.1-0.9	12.1-0.9
Precipitation (mm)			
2018	5.77 ± 10.51	3.04 ± 5.35	3.97 ± 10.10
Max–Min	40–0	24–0	53.2–0
AT (°C) 1998–2018	19.88 ± 7.33	19.47 ± 7.43	19.33 ± 7.19
Max–Min	26.50-13.26	26.12-12.83	25.82-12.85
Evaporation (mm)			
1998–2018	5.39 ± 2.29	4.90 ± 2.01	4.49 ± 2.07
Precipitation (mm)			
1998–2018	7.60 ± 13.29	5.93 ± 10.89	5.47 ± 10.84

Sampling was conducted once a month during the rainy season (July–September) of 2018, as this study focuses on the changes in bacterial composition and functional composition during the rapid changes in rainfall and temperature that occur during this season. Water samples were collected from Lake Cajititlán at five sampling stations (CEA-1, CEA-2, CEA-3, CEA-4, and CEA-5) and at two monitoring depths (80 cm and interstitial) (Fig. 13), using a Van Dorn water sampler, and placed in disinfected and washed 1-liter plastic containers. Two replicates of each sample were obtained (2 L per sample), resulting in a total of 60 samples across all 3 months of the sampling period. Furthermore, water temperature (WT), dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, electrical conductivity (EC), ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrate (NO₃⁻), turbidity, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), blue-green algae (BGA-PC), and chlorophyll-*a* were measured once per month *in situ* at each site and sampling depth, using two multiparameter probes (6600 and 6829 V2 YSI® a xylem brand, OH, USA) (YSI, 2009). The monthly EV, PREC, and AT data measured at the study site were retrieved from The National Water Commission of Mexico (CONAGUA by

its Spanish acronym). The State's Water Commission (CEA by its Spanish acronym) provided monthly data for total nitrogen (TN) and total phosphorus (TP); these measurements were made at the same sampling points and months as the other parameters, at a depth of 0.8 m. No variations were expected in the water quality parameters as Lake Cajititlán is a well-mixed lake due to the shear stress caused by the wind on the water surface (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2019; Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021).

The samples were sequentially filtered using 20–25-mm and 0.45-mm cellulose nitrate membranes (Whatman, UK). Each replicate was initially filtered through a 20–25-mm pore size membrane. The filtrate was then passed through a 0.45-mm membrane, and the filters were immediately placed at -20°C until subsequent analyses.

C.2. DNA extraction, PCR, and sequencing

Genomic DNA was extracted from both filters (100 mg) using the FastDNA Spin Kit for Soil (MP Biomedicals, OH, USA), following the manufacturer's protocol. The extracted DNA samples were quantified using a NanoDrop ND-1000 UV-Vis spectrophotometer (NanoDrop Technologies, Wilmington, DE). The 16S rDNA regions V3-V4 (~550 bp, including indices and adapters) were amplified following the Illumina protocol for 16S Metagenomic Sequencing Library Preparation (Amplicon *et al.*, 2013).

The amplified DNA was verified by 1.0% agarose gel electrophoresis in 1X TAE buffer. Sequencing libraries were cleaned using magnetic beads from the AM Pure XP kit (Beckman Coulter, IN, USA) and quantified with a Qubit 2.0 fluorometer (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA). Finally, 96 samples were loaded onto the Illumina® MiSeq sequencer (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) for 300-bp paired-end sequencing at the facilities of Tecnológico de Monterrey, Campus Monterrey.

C.3. Sequence analysis and functional gene prediction

We used QIIME 2.0 v.2021.8 (Quantitative Insights into Microbial Ecology) to process raw 16S rRNA gene sequence data (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019). Using DADA2 (p-trim-left 0, p-trunc-len 440 nts), chimeric, marginal sequence errors, and noisy sequences were filtered out while choosing

amplicon sequence variations (ASVs) (Callahan *et al.*, 2016). Following that, two characteristic tables [FeatureData(Sequence) and FeatureData(Taxonomy)] were generated with an identity level of 99% against the SILVA database version 138.1 for the 16S rRNA gene (Quast *et al.*, 2013; Yilmaz *et al.*, 2014). The q2-feature-classifier plugin was then used to assign taxonomy to representative sequences, using a trained Nave Bayes classifier (SILVA 138.1) for the 16S rRNA V3-V4 hypervariable region. Finally, using classify-sklearn, taxonomy classification was performed, and the designated sequences were archived using the trained classifier (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019). To attach the corresponding taxonomy to the ASV table, taxon bar charts were created and downloaded in CVS format from view.qiime2.org.

The software PICRUSt 2.0 v. 2.4.1 was used for the predictive functional analysis of bacterial communities (Douglas *et al.*, 2020). Representative sequences were first aligned with HMMER to determine functions (Eddy, 2011), and the alignment was placed in a reference tree (Czech *et al.*, 2020) using SEPP and gappa. Then, using Castor, a hidden state prediction method, multiple copies of the 16S rRNA gene were normalized, and gene families were inferred (Louca and Doebeli, 2017). The MinPath was used to collapse the predicted gene families into MetaCyc pathways (Ye and Doak, 2009). Finally, the predicted metagenomes were classified into KEGG KOs. The KEGG database was used to identify KOs involved in carbon, nitrogen, and sulfur metabolism, as well as phosphorus cycling (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2015 and 2016) (<https://www.genome.jp/kegg/ko.html>).

C.4. Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were carried out using the R v. 3.5.3 software unless otherwise stated (R Core Team, 2020). All bar graphs and line diagrams were built using the ggplot2 package (Wickham, 2009). The sequencing depth of the 16S rRNA genes was represented by a rarefaction curve generated using the rarefy function of the vegan package of the R software, which is based on Hurlbert's (1971) formulation. The Heck *et al.* (1975) method was also used to calculate the standard errors (Oksanen *et al.*, 2017). The DESeq2 package (Anders and Huber, 2010) was applied to normalize the number of reads obtained from 16S rRNA gene sequences. The Scale package was used to create bar graphs of the relative abundance of reads to examine and compare the information collected from reads at different months and sampling sites. Unclassified bacterial

genera were labeled with "Un", and the taxonomic level above was identified; taxa with proportions less than 0.01% were grouped as "other".

Principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) was performed to observe microbial community differences (β -diversity) and to reveal functional differences in the metabolism of the biogeochemical cycles (carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur) between sampling points and months. Distances were based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities using the vegan package and the cmdscale function. Additionally, an analysis of variance was performed using distance matrices (ADONIS) through the vegan package and the Adonis pairwise function to test the significance of spatial and temporal differences in the composition of the bacterial communities of Lake Cajititlán (Clarke, 1993; Anderson, 2001 Anderson *et al.*, 2006).

Bar charts of relative abundance based on the metagenomic compositions of the KOs (relative abundance KOs) were made using the phyloseq and vegan packages (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013). To understand how environmental and physicochemical parameters influenced the abundance/composition of bacterial communities and their genes associated with biogeochemical cycle pathways, a table with the mean and standard deviation of each physicochemical and environmental variable by month of sampling was first created, followed by a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Then, two redundancy analyses (RDA) were performed using the vegan package and ggor, a package for creating ordination plots (Beck, 2017). The first one examined the correlation between microbial community variations and physicochemical and environmental parameters, whereas the second one related the functional composition of biogeochemical cycles and the physicochemical environmental parameters (Friedman, 1989; Press *et al.*, 1992; Oksanen *et al.*, 2017).

Finally, using the 'corrplot' package, Mantel tests based on Spearman's correlation between the abundant taxa of bacteria and the physicochemical and environmental factors were performed, and another correlation matrix was created to evaluate the relationships between the physicochemical and environmental factors with the metabolism (set of metabolic pathways) of the biogeochemical processes analyzed (Wei and Simko, 2021).

D. Results

D.1. Water quality and climatological characteristics of Lake Cajititlán

The heavy rainfall during the wet season causes rapid and significant variations in the water quality parameters in Lake Cajititlán (Gradilla-Hernandez *et al.*, 2019; Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). The results of this study, which was conducted during the rainy season (July–September), revealed that most of the physicochemical parameters monitored showed significant temporal fluctuations when comparing the values reported for the three different months of the rainy season (Table 17). The concentrations of NH_4^+ and NO_3^- decreased over time (from July to September) whereas those of DO, ORP, and chlorophyll-*a* increased, indicating an increase in photosynthetic activity in phytoplankton communities (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). Nutrient values (NH_4^+ and NO_3^-) were highest in July because of nutrient runoff from the agricultural lands surrounding the lake, where significant amounts of nutrients accumulated in the fields are washed off after the onset of the rainy season and as a result of the high evaporation rates (mean ~ 9 mm) throughout the hot-dry season (February to May; Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). The decrease in nutrient concentrations throughout the study period (July to September) could be the consequence of a dilution process throughout the rainy season. Additionally, pH, turbidity, and BGA-PC all displayed similar and significant temporal patterns, with the highest levels observed in July, followed by a decrease in concentration in August and, finally, an increase in the last month. Ultimately, WT and CE presented similar temporal patterns, with the lowest values in July, an increase in August, and a decrease in September; however, only the differences observed for EC were statistically significant (Table 17).

No significant differences were observed in the environmental parameters (EV, PREC, and AT) analyzed during the study period. However, the climatological parameter that displayed the greatest variation was PREC, and July was the month that displayed the highest amount of rain (Table 17). Because in tropical and subtropical areas, the rainy season is intense, lakes in these areas are more vulnerable to excessive pollutant runoff, and changes in water quality indicators are reflected rapidly in shallow and small lakes (Nobre *et al.*, 2020). Similarly, the highest EV and AT values were observed in July (immediately after the hot-dry season) (Table 17).

D.2. Bacterial community composition

The rarefaction curve of the 16S rRNA gene reads consistently reached their asymptotes, indicating sufficient sampling (Fig. 14). A total of 6,075,574 raw reads were obtained from all samples. Using the SILVA 138.1 reference database, 4,135,845 reads (68%) were classified as bacteria. The composition of the bacterial communities was compared at the genus level to test for differences among sampling months (Jul, Aug, Sep) and sampling points (CEA-1, CEA-2, CEA-3, CEA-4, CEA-5). The genera *Flavobacterium* and *Pseudomonas* were most abundant in all months and at all sampling points. Similarly, the groups Un. Oxyphotobacteria and Un. Cyanobacteria presented high abundances; however, these could not be classified to the genus level (Fig. 15A and 15B). Significant temporal variations (ANOSIM R = 0.1233, P = 0.001) in the composition of bacterial communities were found over the study period when comparing the bacterial compositions within the samples taken during the different sampling months (ANOSIM R = 0.0024, P = 0.408; Fig. 15C and Table 18). However, spatial analysis showed that the composition of the bacterial communities was highly similar among all sampling sites as no significant differences were found ($p > 0.05$) (Fig. 15B and Table 19).

Figure 14. Rarefaction curve of 16S rRNA gene samples.

Figure 15. (A) Relative read abundance levels of bacterial genera by sampling month. (B) Relative read abundance levels of bacterial genera by sampling site. (C) PCoA of the bacterial communities to compare sampling months. (D) PCoA of the bacterial communities to compare sampling sites.

Table 18. Pairwise dissimilarity tests of bacterial composition for the different months using ADONIS. The numbers outside the parentheses are “R².” P-values are in parentheses. Bold values denote statistical significance at the $p < 0.05$ level.

Bacterial composition	Adonis statistical comparisons
All	0.001(0.001)
Jul vs. Aug	0.003(0.007)
Jul vs. Sep	0.001(0.001)
Aug vs. Sep	0.007(0.001)

Table 19. Pairwise dissimilarity tests of bacterial composition for the different sampling sites using ADONIS. The numbers outside the parentheses are “R².” P-values are in parentheses.

Bacterial composition	Adonis statistical comparisons
All	0.263(0.41)
CEA-1 vs. CEA-2	0.7(0.702)
CEA-1 vs. CEA-3	0.524(0.285)
CEA-1 vs. CEA-4	0.223(0.182)
CEA-1 vs. CEA-5	0.234(0.157)
CEA-2 vs. CEA-3	0.929(0.891)
CEA-2 vs. CEA-4	0.552(0.808)
CEA-2 vs. CEA-5	0.245(0.233)
CEA-3 vs. CEA-4	0.232(0.343)
CEA-3 vs. CEA-5	0.176(0.107)
CEA-4 vs. CEA-5	0.788(0.674)

D.3. Influence of bacterial communities on biogeochemical cycles

In total, 1,416 KOs were detected within the bacterial communities of Lake Cajititlán, of which 26.84% (380 KOs) were related to the nitrogen, carbon, sulfur, and phosphorus biogeochemical cycles. The functional composition of the bacterial communities related to nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur metabolism was highly different among the sampling months and particularly different for the month of July (ANOSIM $R = 0.003$, $P = 0.008$; Figs. 16A, 17, Table 20). Regarding the

functional composition in terms of carbon metabolism, no temporal differences were observed (ANOSIM $R = 0.0054$, $P = 0.29$; Figs. 16A, 17C, Table 20). Moreover, no spatial variations in functional attributes were found regarding all biochemical cycles when comparing sampling sites, which was also the case for bacterial composition (Fig. 16B and Table 21).

Because there were no spatial significant differences in bacterial composition or functional attributes of biogeochemical cycling, specific metabolic pathways were only analyzed by sampling month and not by sampling site. A principal coordinate analysis (PCoA), based on the Bray-Curtis distances (Fig. 17), was performed to examine the temporal behavior of the nitrogen and phosphorus metabolism. It revealed a temporal transition from the month of July to September, as the functional composition was significantly different between the month of July and the months of August and September (Fig. 17A and 17C; Nitrogen: ANOSIM $R = 0.001$, $P = 0.001$, Phosphorus: ANOSIM $R = 0.001$, $P = 0.001$; Table 20). The functional composition of the carbon and sulfur metabolism displayed a more stable behavior throughout the study period (Fig. 17B and 17C). However, statistically significant temporal changes in the metabolic pathways of sulfur were observed (ANOSIM $R = 0.022$, $P = 0.045$), whereas no differences between the metabolic pathways were detected for carbon (ANOSIM $R = 0.552$, $P = 0.067$; Table 20).

Figure 16. (A) PCoA of potential functions of all biogeochemical cycles by sampling month. (B) PCoA of potential functions of all biogeochemical cycles by sampling site.

Figure 17. (A) Functional differences during July, August, and September. PCoA of potential function composition in terms of overall functions for (A) nitrogen metabolism, (B) sulfur metabolism, (C) carbon metabolism, and (D) phosphorus cycle.

Table 20. Pairwise dissimilarity tests of functional composition for the different months using ADONIS. The numbers outside the parentheses are “R².” P-values are in parentheses. Bold values denote statistical significance at the $p < 0.05$ level.

Adonis statistical comparisons					
Functional composition	All	N	P	C	S
All	0.003(0.008)	0.001(0.001)	0.001(0.001)	0.552(0.067)	0.022(0.045)
Jul vs. Aug	0.001(0.001)	0.001(0.001)	0.001(0.001)	0.315(0.08)	0.02(0.089)
Jul vs. Sep	0.012(0.002)	0.001(0.001)	0.001(0.001)	0.054(0.084)	0.06(0.088)
Aug vs. Sep	0.161(0.022)	0.289(0.134)	0.41(0.498)	0.082(0.322)	0.138(0.121)

Table 21. Pairwise dissimilarity tests of functional composition for the different sampling sites using ADONIS. The numbers outside the parentheses are “R².” P-values are in parenthesis. Bold values denote statistical significance at the $p < 0.05$ level.

Adonis statistical comparisons					
Functional composition	All	N	P	C	S
All	0.161(0.268)	0.372(0.635)	0.470(0.924)	0.171(0.254)	0.389(0.645)
CEA-1 vs. CEA-2	0.572(0.551)	0.521(0.807)	0.852(0.285)	0.108(0.117)	0.264(0.222)
CEA-1 vs. CEA-3	0.662(0.605)	0.777(0.661)	0.371(0.054)	0.346(0.498)	0.391(0.283)
CEA-1 vs. CEA-4	0.607(0.516)	0.255(0.179)	0.714(0.266)	0.967(0.948)	0.312(0.695)
CEA-1 vs. CEA-5	0.816(0.762)	0.828(0.729)	0.615(0.289)	0.557(0.723)	0.38(0.648)
CEA-2 vs. CEA-3	0.908(0.892)	0.85(0.707)	0.675(0.672)	0.06(0.255)	0.693(0.866)
CEA-2 vs. CEA-4	0.528(0.639)	0.313(0.376)	0.875(0.9)	0.042(0.007)	0.062(0.824)
CEA-2 vs. CEA-5	0.798(0.871)	0.592(0.747)	0.953(0.817)	0.721(0.53)	0.391(0.529)
CEA-3 vs. CEA-4	0.55(0.465)	0.263(0.128)	0.628(0.595)	0.136(0.174)	0.266(0.507)
CEA-3 vs. CEA-5	0.834(0.8)	0.706(0.333)	0.977(0.602)	0.129(.479)	0.803(0.484)

Regarding the functional composition for nitrogen metabolism, 36 KOs were detected (ko00910 in the KEGG database). In this case, the bacterial functional composition displayed a significantly higher relative abundance of genes associated with the denitrification and the nitrogen fixation pathways, and July was the month with the highest gene abundance related to these pathways. Commamox and anammox were also slightly higher in July (compared to August and September), although these differences were not significant. The gene abundance levels related to dissimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonia (DNRA), assimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonia (ANRA), and nitrification processes were similar among the sampling months. Within these metabolic pathways, DNRA displayed the highest gene abundance during all sampling months (Fig. 18A).

We found 23 KOs related to sulfur metabolism (ko00920 in the KEGG database). In July, all metabolic pathways displayed a higher relative gene abundance, with the assimilatory sulfate reduction (ASR) pathway displaying the highest gene abundance, followed by the cysteine, the sulfur oxidation system (SOX system), and the dissimilatory sulfate reduction (DSR) pathways. All metabolic pathways displayed similar abundance proportions in August and September, except for the SOX system, which was greatest in August (Fig. 18B). According to the KEGG database, 287 KOs were related to the central carbon pathways in the analyzed samples (ko01200). The genes related to all bacterial carbon metabolic pathways displayed stable abundances during all sampling months, with carbohydrate metabolism being the most abundant one throughout the rainy season, followed by carbon fixation pathways in prokaryotes (CFPP), methane metabolism, carbon fixation in photosynthetic organisms (CFPO), and lipid metabolism (Fig. 18C).

Overall, 34 KOs were found to be related to the phosphorus cycle. All phosphorus pathways examined were most abundant during July. The organic P-mineralization (OPM) pathway was the most abundant pathway, followed by P-starvation response regulation (PSRR), (PUT), and inorganic P-solubilization (IPS). Similar fractions were found between August and September for all metabolic pathways (Fig. 18D).

Figure 18. Relative abundance levels of genes associated with major pathways in (A) nitrogen metabolism, DNRA: dissimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonia, ANRA: assimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonia. (B) Sulfur metabolism, ASR: assimilatory sulfate reduction, DSR: dissimilatory sulfate reduction, SOX system: sulfur oxidation system. (C) Central carbon metabolism, CFPP: carbon fixation pathways in prokaryotes, CFPO: carbon fixation in photosynthetic organisms. (D) Phosphorus cycle, PUT: P-uptake and transport, OPM: organic P-mineralization, IPS: inorganic P-Solubilization, PSRR: P-starvation response regulation.

D.4. Physicochemical and environmental influences

Physicochemical and environmental factors are important determinants of microbial communities and their functional composition in Lake Cajititlán. The data matrix of the physicochemical and environmental parameters generated was used to explore the influence of these parameters on the bacterial communities' functional composition during the study period (July, August, and September). Table 17 shows the mean and standard deviations of the analyzed factors.

The RDA indicated that the physicochemical parameters that were most correlated with the taxonomic composition during July and August were ORP, NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , TN, pH, and WT, whereas chlorophyll-*a* was most correlated with the taxonomic composition in September (Fig. 19A). The first three redundancy components explained 72.2% (RDA 1: 28.9%; RDA 2: 43.9%; RDA 3: 72.2%) of the overall variability of the physicochemical factors that influenced the temporal dynamics of the bacterial communities (Table 22). The parameters that accounted for most of the bacterial variation in the first RDA component were pH, ORP, NH_4^+ , and NO_3^- , and all of them were negatively correlated with this component (Table 23). The second component was highly correlated with DO (positive correlation) and turbidity (negative correlation), whereas pH (negative correlation) and TN (positive correlation) were the parameters most correlated with the third component (Table 23). Positive correlations may suggest that microorganisms thrive under higher values of these (DO and TN) physicochemical parameters; on the other hand, the negative correlations (pH, ORP, NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , Turbidity) imply that higher values of these parameters negatively affect the prevalence of the bacterial populations over the research period (Lemian *et al.*, 2014).

Table 22. Redundancy analysis (RDA) of bacterial communities. Eigenvalues, proportion explained, and cumulative proportion by eight RDA axes are shown.

Component	Eigenvalue	Proportion explained	Cumulative proportion
RD1	2.86	0.289	0.289
RD2	1.47	0.150	0.439
RD3	2.81	0.283	0.722
RD4	0.88	0.092	0.814

RD5	0.73	0.078	0.892
RD6	0.58	0.062	0.954
RD7	0.28	0.033	0.987
RD8	0.10	0.013	1

Table 23. Eigenvalues of the physicochemical variables in the RDA of bacterial communities. Water temperature (WT), dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, electrical conductivity (EC), ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrate (NO₃⁻), turbidity, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), blue-green algae (BGA-PC).

Variable	RDA1	RDA2	RDA3	RDA4
DO	0.209	0.417	-0.051	0.116
pH	-0.632	-0.326	-0.466	0.013
WT	-0.315	0.314	-0.106	-0.378
Turbidity	-0.444	-0.486	-0.289	0.037
ORP	-0.776	0.075	-0.093	0.185
NH ₄ ⁺	-0.771	0.036	-0.046	0.094
NO ₃ ⁻	-0.927	0.070	-0.105	0.193
BGA-PC	0.079	-0.190	-0.269	-0.017
Chlorophyll- <i>a</i>	0.213	-0.123	0.077	-0.311
EC	0.189	0.089	0.225	-0.633
TN	-0.509	0.167	0.426	-0.060
TP	-0.424	0.105	-0.150	0.033

According to the RDA results, the physicochemical parameters that were most correlated with the functional composition of the bacterial communities of July were ORP, NH₄⁺, NO₃⁻, and pH, whereas TN, DO, WT, and chlorophyll-*a* were most correlated with the functional compositions for August and September (Fig. 19B). The first three components explained 95.5% of the variability of functional composition (RDA 1: 89%; RDA 2: 92.6%, RDA 3: 95.5%; Table 24); pH, ORP, and turbidity were the most correlated parameters with the first component, all of which displayed negative correlations. Turbidity was the variable that explained most of the variation in the second component, displaying a positive correlation. Finally, in the third component, NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻ were the parameters that were most (positively) correlated with the

genes of the bacterial communities involved in biogeochemical cycling (Table 25). Positive correlations (NH_4^+ and NO_3^-) suggest that biogeochemical cycling activities are enhanced under these higher concentrations, whereas negatively correlated parameters (pH, ORP, and turbidity) may hinder biochemical cycling.

Figure 19. Biplot of the results of the redundancy analysis (RDA). (A) RDA regarding bacterial composition and physicochemical variables by sampling month. (B) RDA regarding functional composition and physicochemical variables by sampling month. Water temperature (WT), dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, electrical conductivity (EC), ammonium (NH_4^+), nitrate (NO_3^-), turbidity, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), blue-green algae (BGA-PC).

Table 24. Redundancy analysis (RDA) of functional composition. Eigenvalues, proportion explained, and cumulative proportion by 12 RDA axes are shown.

Component	Eigenvalue	Proportion explained	Cumulative proportion
RD1	8.64	0.890	0.890
RD2	0.351	0.036	0.926

RD3	0.283	0.029	0.955
RD4	0.159	0.016	0.971
RD5	0.098	0.010	0.981
RD6	0.062	0.006	0.987
RD7	0.051	0.005	0.992
RD8	0.023	0.002	0.994
RD9	0.020	0.002	0.996
RD10	0.020	0.002	0.998
RD11	0.010	0.001	0.999
RD12	0.010	0.001	1

Table 25. Eigenvalues of the physicochemical variables in the RDA of functional composition. Water temperature (WT), dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, electrical conductivity (EC), ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrate (NO₃⁻), turbidity, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), blue-green algae (BGA-PC).

Variable	RDA1	RDA2	RDA3	RDA4
DO	0.304	0.211	0.220	0.211
pH	-0.933	-0.010	-0.053	-0.054
WT	0.061	-0.189	0.508	-0.319
Turbidity	-0.833	0.330	-0.172	0.153
ORP	-0.811	-0.070	0.305	0.073
NH ₄ ⁺	-0.448	-0.163	0.547	-0.470
NO ₃ ⁻	-0.741	-0.136	0.497	-0.106
BGA-PC	-0.415	0.157	-0.361	0.479
Chlorophyll- <i>a</i>	0.182	-0.256	-0.011	-0.612
EC	0.413	-0.273	-0.156	0.123
TN	-0.026	0.234	0.434	-0.126

TP	-0.131	-0.249	0.467	-0.480
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Mantel tests (Fig. 20A) revealed that the composition and abundance of the genus *Flavobacterium* and the group Un. Oxyphotobacteria were positively correlated to OD, whereas the *Pseudomonas* genus was positively correlated to chlorophyll-*a* and all environmental variables (AT, EV, and PREC) but negatively correlated to ORP, NO₃⁻, and TN, and the groups Un. Oxyphotobacteria and Un. Cyanobacteria were negatively correlated with TN. The correlation matrix between the biogeochemical metabolisms and the physicochemical and environmental variables (Fig. 20B) show that nitrogen and phosphorus metabolisms were positively correlated with pH, turbidity, ORP, NH₄⁺, NO₃⁻, and BGA-PC and negatively with EC and all environmental parameters. Sulfur metabolism was significantly correlated with pH, turbidity, ORP, NO₃⁻, and all environmental parameters. Finally, carbon metabolism was negatively correlated only with TN.

Figure 20. (A) Mantel tests based on Spearman correlations between most abundant taxa of bacteria and physicochemical factors. (B) Biogeochemical metabolism and physicochemical variables. Significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) are marked with an asterisk. Water temperature (WT), dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, electrical conductivity (EC), ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrate (NO₃⁻), turbidity, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), blue-green algae (BGA-PC), and air temperature (AT).

E. Discussion

E.1. Dynamics and abundance of the dominant bacterial taxa and their environmental and physicochemical influences

In recent decades, research on the dynamics of phytoplankton in lakes has increased, but there is still little knowledge regarding bacterial dynamics in such ecosystems, especially those in subtropical latitudes, despite the fact that many non-cultivable widely disseminated bacterial taxa have been discovered in freshwater environments (Eiler and Bertilsson, 2007; Lira *et al.*, 2011; Bonilla *et al.*, 2012; Yang *et al.*, 2013; Malki *et al.*, 2015; Sible *et al.*, 2015; Barros *et al.*, 2017;

Guellati *et al.*, 2017; Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). The study of bacterial communities within tropical and subtropical lakes represents a greater challenge due to the rapid changes that occur in physicochemical and environmental factors because of the heavy rainfall and increased flow events, which lead to increased runoff of allochthonous dissolved organic and inorganic matter as well as nutrients (Weyhenmeyer *et al.*, 2004; Sadro and Melack, 2012; Stockwell *et al.*, 2020; Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, variations in organic matter, dissolved solids, and nutrient concentrations can lead to alterations in the spatio-temporal dynamics of bacterial communities (Allgaier and Grossart, 2006; Rösel *et al.*, 2012; Grossart, 2010).

In this study, no spatial differences were observed in the taxonomic composition of the bacterial community within Lake Cajititlán (Fig. 15B). Shallow subtropical lakes, such as Lake Cajititlán, frequently exhibit a polymictic nature, with the total mixing of the water column occurring throughout the summer, mostly driven by precipitation and wind (do Nascimento-Moura *et al.*, 2012; Kerimoglu and Rinke, 2013; Cavicchioli *et al.*, 2019; Gradilla Hernández *et al.*, 2019). However, there were significant temporal variations in the composition of the bacterial communities among the sampling months (Fig. 15A), which is consistent with a previous study focusing on the phytoplankton communities of Lake Cajititlán, which were found to be temporally, but not spatially, different (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). This implies that bacterial communities may be influenced by phytoplankton diversity and abundance, as has been observed for other lakes, where changes in phytoplankton communities and environmental variables have been reported to influence the composition of bacterial communities and, together, phytoplankton and bacteria influence ecosystem-wide changes (Woodhouse *et al.*, 2016; Niu *et al.*, 2011; Kent *et al.*, 2007; Rishiram *et al.*, 2016).

The dominant bacterial genera found in Cajititlán were *Flavobacterium* and *Pseudomonas*, which were also predominant in prior investigations on bacterial communities in freshwater systems (Michaud *et al.*, 2012; Shao *et al.*, 2021). *Flavobacterium*, which is ubiquitous in freshwater environments (Groff and LaPatra, 2001), was most abundant during all sampling months and at all points (Fig. 15A and 15B). This genus has previously been found in high abundance in eutrophic and hypereutrophic freshwater ecosystems, such as Lake Cajititlán (Shao *et al.*, 2021; Roth *et al.*, 2008; Drury *et al.*, 2013). It comprises over 30 species, of which *F. psychrophilum*, *F.*

columnare, and *F. branchiophilum* can cause major diseases in fish populations within freshwater (Ilardi *et al.*, 2009; Ilardi *et al.*, 2010). Specifically, *F. columnare* is the cause of columnaris disease, a serious condition affecting numerous freshwater fish species worldwide (Starliper, 2011). Regarding Lake Cajititlán, there is substantial evidence that the massive events of fish death that occur yearly at the end of the wet season are a consequence of the lake's eutrophication problem. Additionally, the production of microcystins by cyanobacteria has also been reported as a possible cause of the mass mortality of the fish in this lake (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, during the sampling process for the present study, fish gasping at the surface and dead fish were observed floating on the surface. Therefore, the findings of the present study suggest that pathogenic *Flavobacterium* species may be associated with the occurrence of massive fish death events in Lake Cajititlán, since it was the most abundant genus during the study period. However, pathological studies of fish are required to determine the causes of death and for a better characterization and taxonomic classification of the genus *Flavobacterium*, with the aim to determine which species of this group are present and whether they are pathogenic.

Pseudomonas was the second most dominant genus in Lake Cajititlán (Fig. 15A and 15B). It is considered a cosmopolitan genus that has been found in a variety of habitats, including freshwater and terrestrial environments (Pearce *et al.*, 2003; Saul *et al.*, 2005), and includes opportunistic pathogens affecting humans, fish, and plants (Ferguson *et al.*, 2004; Bleves *et al.*, 2010). *Pseudomonas* is thought to promote the growth of the cyanobacteria that produce cyanotoxins by altering the phosphate exchange in their mucilage capsules (Jian *et al.*, 2007; Berg *et al.*, 2009). Furthermore, in this study, the abundance of *Pseudomonas* was proportional to that of *Cylindrospermopsis* (Fig. 15A), which are known to produce cyanotoxins (cylindrospermopsin, microcystin, and saxitoxin) and to have severe effects on water quality and aquatic ecology (Yilmaz and Philips *et al.*, 2011). A prior study on lake Cajititlán reported the presence of the toxin microcystin (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021), which has been suggested to give cyanotoxin degraders, such as *Pseudomonas*, a competitive edge by acting as a nutritional supplement (Mou *et al.*, 2013; Kormas and Lymperopoulou, 2013; Zhu *et al.*, 2014). Consequently, this toxin may contribute to the population growth of *Pseudomonas* in lake Cajititlán. This association has previously been reported for the eutrophic Lake Akersvannet in south Norway, where the highest concentration of cyanotoxins coincided with the highest

diversity of potentially cyanotoxin-degrading species such as *Caulobacter*, *Novosphigobium*, *Sphingorhabdus*, *Paucibacter*, and *Pseudomonas* (Parulekar *et al.*, 2017).

According to the RDA and mantel test, the parameters that were most correlated with the prevalence of bacterial communities during the study period were ORP, NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , DO, turbidity, TN, and pH (Figs. 19A, 20A, Table 23). While ORP is a nonspecific measurement reflective of all dissolved species in the medium, values ranging from +100 to +350 mV indicate a higher potential for the nitrification process, values ranging from +50 to +250 mV indicate higher values for carbonaceous biochemical oxygen demand, values ranging from +25 to +250 mV indicate higher biological phosphorus removal, and values ranging from +50 to -50 mV indicate a higher denitrification potential (YSI, 2009). In this study, the mean ORP values during July, August, and September were 47.90, 66.18, and 101.78 mV, respectively (Table 17). Therefore, all these processes may be enhanced in the lake during the different study months (July, August, and September) since the ORP values were measured within all these ranges.

The parameters TN, NH_4^+ , and NO_3^- are crucial water quality parameters that drive the distribution of bacterial communities. Bacteria require a large amount of nitrogen for the synthesis of their main components, such as amino acids, pyrimidines and purines, NAD, and amino sugars. Furthermore, these organisms and archaea are the primary drivers responsible for converting different forms of N into chemical forms used by plants (NH_4^+ and NO_3^-) (Wang *et al.*, 2018; Reitzer, 1996). Some species of the genera *Pseudomona* and *Cylindrospermopsis* observed in this study, as well as some species of the phylum Cyanobacteria (Fig. 15A), could be involved in the nitrogen cycle pathways (Crovadore *et al.*, 2015; Howarth *et al.*, 1988; Paerl, 2017). The DO influences the abundances of functional genes involved in nitrogen and phosphorus cycling as well as redox reaction directions (Güven *et al.*, 2005); it also has an impact on the growth of bacteria and the efficiency with which substances are degraded by them (Larson *et al.*, 1981).

Alkaline pH levels (mean pH of 9.5) have already been reported to be caused by the natural geological conditions of the lake's basin (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2020). The pH plays a prominent role in determining the metabolisms that appear in bacterial communities within specific ecological systems; it also influences the composition of bacterial communities

Flavobacterium is strongly positively correlated with this parameter, as shown in this study (Fig. 20A) and as reported previously (Garcia *et al.*, 2013; Wang *et al.*, 2021; Li *et al.*, 2019;). Finally, turbidity was another important variable correlated with the bacterial communities of Lake Cajititlán; this parameter is seasonally dependent and influenced by factors such as the presence of phytoplankton, suspended sediments, and effluent discharges. Therefore, the bacterial communities within the phytoplankton are reflected by this parameter and/or the nutrients that are part of the suspended materials that affect the prevalence of photosynthetic bacteria within the lake (Myint and Walker, 2002; Harsha and Malammanavar *et al.*, 2004).

E.2. Biogeochemical cycles linked to bacterial communities and their environmental and physicochemical influences

Previous research on eutrophic freshwater lakes has focused on the dynamics of phosphorus in shallow lake sediments. Based on the results, in the sediment of shallow lakes, numerous highly dynamic processes with substantial effects on the total phosphorus budget and lake water quality occur (Søndergaard *et al.*, 2003). Additionally, other studies have reported that human activities influence nitrogen removal from lakes, the vertical distribution of phosphorus in shallow estuaries, and the retention and internal loading of phosphorus in shallow and eutrophic lakes; however, few studies have focused on the spatial and temporal variations of nutrients in water of a shallow, eutrophic, and subtropical lakes (Søndergaard *et al.*, 2001; Zhang *et al.*, 2007; Lukkari *et al.*, 2008; Finlay *et al.*, 2013; Hayakawa *et al.*, 2015). According to our literature review, no studies have focused on the temporal dynamics of the functional composition of bacterial communities related with the main biogeochemical cycles (nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and carbon) in shallow eutrophic subtropical lakes during the rainy season. In the case of Lake Cajititlán, the water quality and the composition of the phytoplankton community shift significantly during the wet season (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2019; Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021), making it crucial to understand the contribution of bacterial communities to the larger-scale ecological biogeochemical processes as well as the mechanisms that lead to the assembly of bacterial communities during the rainy season in such ecosystems (Wu *et al.*, 2019).

According to the RDA and the mantel test results, the physicochemical and environmental parameters that were most correlated with the functional composition of the bacterial

communities were pH, ORP, turbidity, TN, EC, NH_4^+ , and NO_3^- (Figs. 19B, 20B and Table 25). Except for EC, all these variables were also the most correlated with the prevalence of bacterial communities over the research period. The EC is a multifactorial parameter influenced by several factors such as the geology of the basin, wastewater discharges, runoff from diffuse sources, atmospheric inputs, evaporation rates, some types of bacterial metabolism, among others (Pal *et al.*, 2015). In Lake Cajititlán, the high concentration of ions can largely be explained by anthropogenic contamination, which can be somewhat beneficial to bacterial growth (de Anda *et al.*, 2019; Torres *et al.*, 2008). As previously stated, the bacteria most prevalent in this study influenced the biogeochemical cycles analyzed, as evidenced by their correlation with the majority of the physicochemical parameters observed in both correlation analyses (taxonomy and functional).

E.3. Nitrogen metabolism

Nitrogen exists in a variety of chemical forms, such as NO_3^- and NH_3^+ , which are cycled through several biogeochemical processes (Ollivier *et al.*, 2011), including four reduction pathways (DNRA, denitrification, ANRA, and nitrogen fixation) and three oxidation pathways (anammox, nitrification, and commamox) (Lamba *et al.*, 2017; Mehrani *et al.*, 2021). Denitrification and anammox are processes that remove nitrogen from aquatic habitats (Ward *et al.*, 2009). Denitrification is the principal biological process in aquatic ecosystems through which nitrate is converted into dinitrogen and nitrous oxide (Bernhard, 2010), whereas anammox is a key pathway for converting nitrite and ammonia to dinitrogen (Kuypers *et al.*, 2005). In this study, the denitrification pathway displayed the highest abundance of genes during July, indicating a significant potential for nitrogen removal, which is consistent with the highest levels of NO_3^- as well as the lowest levels of ORP observed in the same month which could enhanced denitrification process in Lake Cajititlán (Vizcaíno *et al.*, 2018; Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021; Sigman *et al.*, 2001; Wodarczyk *et al.*, 2003; Higgins, 2013; Fig. 18; Table 17). These water quality features interact with microorganisms in a complex way on a microscale level, resulting in spatial and temporal variability in the denitrification rates (Parkin *et al.*, 1987; Svensson *et al.*, 1991; Wodarczyk *et al.*, 2000). It has also been reported that microbial respiration within the sediments can cause anoxic environments, further promoting denitrification (Lv *et al.*, 2017). Thus, the

denitrification pathway was also enhanced by the extremely low DO levels (2.83 mg/L) displayed in July in Lake Cajititlán.

The functional composition also displayed a high abundance of genes associated with nitrogen fixation during July (Fig. 18A). Nitrogen fixation and denitrification can co-occur in sediments through heterotrophic nitrogen fixation (Newell *et al.*, 2016). However, nitrogen fixation is believed to occur predominantly at the surface of water bodies through the activity of diazotrophic phototrophs, such as cyanobacteria, which are the most important nitrogen fixers in aquatic environments (Zehr *et al.*, 2001; Montoya *et al.*, 2004; Capone *et al.*, 2005). Since no diazotrophic heterotrophic bacteria were found at high abundance in Lake Cajititlán, it may be assumed that nitrogen fixation was mostly performed by *Cylindrospermopsis* species, which are diazotrophic phototrophs (Howarth *et al.*, 1988; Paerl, 2017). Furthermore, it is likely that the nitrogen-fixing prokaryotic bacteria contributed to the massive algal blooms that have occurred in Lake Cajititlán in recent years due to the symbiotic relationship between nitrogen-fixing prokaryotic bacteria and algae, as the latter are incapable of fixing atmospheric nitrogen, which is required for their growth (Thompson *et al.*, 2012).

Regarding the remaining nitrogen metabolism pathways (commamox, DNRA, ANRA, anammox, nitrification), no temporal differences were observed. However, a higher relative abundance of DNRA-associated genes was observed during all months of the study in comparison with other pathways (Fig. 18A), suggesting a stable functionality of the bacterial communities in the water column to reduce nitrate to ammonia. The metabolic pathways ANRA, DNRA, and denitrification use nitrate. The first pathway is expected under aerobic conditions when reduced nitrogen is limited, whereas the other two dissimilatory pathways are expected when oxygen is limited (anaerobic conditions), and their respective reduced products (NH_4^+ and $\text{N}_2 + \text{N}_2\text{O}$, respectively) are produced in relatively greater quantities because these processes are linked to electron transport (Tiedje *et al.*, 1981; Henson *et al.*, 2017). Based on our OD measurements (Table 17), it can be inferred that the predominant nitrogen pathways in Lake Cajititlán are those that occur under anaerobic conditions (denitrification, nitrogen fixation, and DNRA), which is consistent with extensively reported massive phytoplankton blooms occurring in the lake (Gradilla-Hernandez *et al.*, 2019), which can produce high DO levels and biomass growth during the day

(coupled with a reduction in light penetration and photosynthetic activity) and anoxic or hypoxic conditions at night as a result of their respiration (Smith and Schindler, 2009).

E.4. Carbon metabolism

During the three sampling months, the functional composition related to the carbohydrate metabolism pathway was most abundant within all carbon metabolism pathways, followed by CFPP, methane metabolism, CFPO, and lipid metabolism. However, no temporal differences were observed among them (Fig. 18C).

Microorganisms play an important role in the production, transformation, and mineralization of organic matter (Powlson *et al.*, 2001; Amalfitano *et al.*, 2008). As a result, the functional composition of bacterial communities is largely determined by fluctuations in the organic matter composition of the water column as well as the bioavailability of the different chemical organic forms (Hoostal and Bouzat, 2008; Wang *et al.*, 2018). Organic matter comprises carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, lignins, and other compounds (Thurman, 2012). Besides the organic matter entering the lake through the WWTP effluents, organic matter is a heterogeneous mixture that contains allochthonous materials from terrestrial ecosystems, such as soil and plant litter, as well as autochthonous materials from primary producers (Finlay, 2001; Mosisch *et al.*, 2001; Carpenter *et al.*, 2005; Cole *et al.*, 2011; Solomon *et al.*, 2011). Thus, the high organic matter concentrations in the water column of Lake Cajititlán largely influence the most abundant pathway for carbon metabolism, which is carbohydrate metabolism (Fig. 18C; Vizcaíno *et al.*, 2018). The raw or partially treated wastewater discharged into Lake Cajititlán by three treatment facilities is a major source of energy for the reservoir's bacterial populations. Furthermore, especially during the rainy season, the organic matter pollution is exacerbated because the capacity of the treatment plants is surpassed as the raw wastewater is combined with rainfall and an overflow wastewater bypass is implemented at the treatment plants, discharging the wastewater and rainfall mixture directly into the lake (de Anda *et al.*, 2019; Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2019).

Both ORP and DO are critical water quality parameter for the carbon cycle, as reducing conditions and low DO levels can enhance methane synthesis, whereas methane-oxidizing and

sulfate-reducing bacteria contribute to carbon fixation (Itoh *et al.*, 2015; He *et al.*, 2015; Kellermann *et al.*, 2012). Sulfate-reducing bacteria (SRB) are anaerobic microorganisms that use sulfate as an electron acceptor during the dissimilatory sulfate reduction process (DSR) (Simon and Kroneck, 2013). In this research, it can be inferred that these bacteria could not influence the CFPO pathway (carbon fixation pathways in prokaryotes) since no differences were observed in the abundance of this pathway during the sampling months. In addition, the DSR pathway was least abundant in sulfur metabolism (Fig. 18B). In contrast, the functional abundance of the methane metabolism was enhanced with low DO levels (Fig. 18C, Table 17), which leads us to infer that the methane-oxidizing bacteria and/or archaea governed this pathway since the SRB bacterial activity would have been reflected by the DSR pathway. It is also widely reported that SRB can depend on methanogens that scavenge hydrogen and acetate to convert organic compounds to methane. Under low DO concentrations, SRB and methanogens do not compete and rather cooperate in the degradation of organic matter (Plugge *et al.*, 2011), which may occur in this lake during the rainy season.

E.5. Phosphorus cycle

Anthropogenic activities have altered the phosphorus cycle in aquatic environments (White and Metcalf, 2007; Kononova and Nesmeyanova, 2002). For example, the intensive use of highly water-soluble phosphorus fertilizers has contributed to the eutrophication, and hypoxic conditions, of surface waterways across the world (Haque, 2021). Organophosphates are widely used in the chemical industry as detergents, antifreeze compounds, and pesticides and can also be found in a wide variety of antibiotics of microbial origin, which are not generally treated properly in municipal WWTP and thus contribute to nutrient accumulation in water sources (Hayes *et al.*, 2000; White and Metcalf, 2007). Bacteria play an important role in phosphorus cycling in water sources, and in this study, the findings indicate that in July, all phosphorus metabolic pathways were more abundant compared to August and September. The most abundant pathway was organic OPM, followed by PSRR, PUT, and IPS (Fig. 18D). Plants and microorganisms obtain phosphorus from inorganic sources rather than organic ones, and the process by which organic phosphorus is converted into organic phosphate is called mineralization (Vance, 2001). Phosphate esters are the most abundant organophosphorus compounds in the biosphere and the easiest to mineralize due to the low energy demand in the production of the exoenzymes (phosphatases,

phosphonatases, and C-P lyases) required, which are produced by several microorganisms of the genera *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Azotobacter*, *Rhodococcus*, *Serratia*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Salmonella*, and *Thiobacillus*, among others (Kononova and Nesmeyanova, 2002; Kolowitz *et al.*, 2001; Postma *et al.*, 2010; Babalola and Glick, 2012; David *et al.*, 2014; Jahan *et al.*, 2013). In this research, *Pseudomonas* were the second most abundant bacterial genus and could significantly contribute to phosphorus mineralization in Lake Cajititlán (Fig. 15A) since it produces phosphatase under conditions of low P availability, providing it with an advantage over other phosphorus-mineralizing microorganisms (Babalola and Glick, 2012; Thaller *et al.*, 1995).

Phosphorous limitation triggers a P starvation response in aquatic environments, which can accelerate nutrient uptake by microorganisms and plants, resulting in a reduction in the TP content (Grossman and Aksoy, 2015; Slocombe *et al.*, 2020). A previous study reported the annual behavior of the TN: TP ratio within Lake Cajititlán over the past 21 years (1998-2019) and showed that nutrient limitation in this reservoir can shift during the rainy season. A 10-year data set study revealed that Lake Cajititlán is phosphorus limited during the beginning of the rainy season (June-July) and at the end of the rainy season (September) but nitrogen-limited in August (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021), and these shifts are driven by the rainy season. The authors of this study discussed how these variations in the limiting nutrient could be attributed to intensive fertilizer runoff at the start of the rainy season, which increases the TN:TP ratio during June and July, which is then decreased in August due to increased nitrogenous compound consumption by growing phytoplankton communities. These authors also explained these changes with the decrease in the abundance of the genus *Cylindrospermopsis* in the month of August. This implies that phosphorus is the primary nutrient limiting the productivity of this phytoplankton genus since its abundance increased in July and September (Hecky and Kilham, 1988, Howarth and Marino, 2006; Fig. 15A). Likewise, the findings of this study are consistent with the behavior of the PSRR phosphorus pathway in July observed in this study (Fig. 18D), which implies that the bacterial communities in the water column presented a higher state of P starvation than in the other months, because according to Díaz-Torres *et al.* (2021), phosphorus was the limiting nutrient in July.

E.6. Sulfur metabolism

Sulfur is required by all living organisms, including prokaryotes and eukaryotes, as it is essential for the synthesis of amino acids, proteins, and enzymes (Barton *et al.*, 2009). Sulfate reduction can occur through assimilatory and dissimilatory pathways (Barton *et al.*, 2009; Kushkevych *et al.*, 2019). In this research, the genes of the bacterial communities associated with the ASR pathway were more abundant than those associated with the DSR pathway (Fig. 18B). In a bacterial cell, DSR and ASR are two metabolic processes that metabolize sulfate in distinct ways. The former pathway uses sulfate as a terminal acceptor and is essential for ATP synthesis, with the terminal product of hydrogen sulfide, whereas the latter uses sulfate to form the amino acid cysteine (Kushkevych, 2016; Barton *et al.*, 2014). The ASR is a more complex pathway than the dissimilatory reduction as DSR only requires three enzymes because sulfate-reducing bacteria are strictly anaerobic organisms, whereas seven different enzymes are necessary for the assimilatory pathway as facultative anaerobic microorganisms must operate in both anaerobic and aerobic environments (Kushkevych *et al.*, 2020). During the sampling months, the abundance of genes related to the ASR pathway exhibited a similar pattern to that of the genes involved in the cysteine pathway, indicating that the ASR pathway's terminal product (cysteine) was produced simultaneously. Cysteine is primarily a protein precursor, but it is also a precursor for vitamins and antioxidants such as glutathione, which is crucial for maintaining the redox homeostasis in many eukaryotes and bacterial cells (Rausch and Wachter, 2005; Helbig *et al.*, 2008). Therefore, it is reasonable to hypothesize that the ASR pathway was the most abundant one in this study, and there were optimal sulfate concentrations for aerobic and anaerobic bacteria to metabolize. While sulfate concentrations were not measured in this study, significant loads of sulfur may enter the lake with wastewater discharge, which facilitates the ASR pathway (Holmer and Storkholm, 2001; de Anda *et al.*, 2019a).

F. Conclusions

This study provides valuable information on ecological interactions between water quality and bacterial taxonomic and functional composition in a subtropical and hypereutrophic lake during the rainy season. Results showed significant temporal variations over a short period of time, induced by the rainy season, causing high seasonal surface runoff and, therefore, significant changes in the physicochemical (pH, ORP, turbidity, TN, EC, NH_4^+ and NO_3^-) features of Lake

Cajititlán. The most abundant bacterial genera found were *Flavobacterium* and *Pseudomonas*. Bacterial communities displayed a higher relative abundance of genes associated with denitrification, nitrogen fixation, ASR, cysteine, SOX system, and all phosphorus pathways in July, whereas the remaining pathways and months showed similar patterns in abundance as bacterial communities are highly influenced by nutrient loads during the onset of the rainy season (July) and by low DO levels. A limitation of PICRUSt inferences is that they are based on evolutionary modeling of the gene content of known reference genomes. Therefore, the accuracy of any given sample type will depend heavily on the availability of appropriate references. On the other hand, the input data for the standard PICRUSt workflow are partial 16S rRNA gene sequences, and therefore, eukaryotic, or viral contributions to the metagenome will not be predicted. Future research will use shotgun sequencing to comprehensively analyze genes from all organisms present in a sample. This can provide more accurate knowledge of the metabolic mechanisms that may be taking on to allow these organisms to adapt to their environment. Also, these data would allow the further exploration of the functional and taxonomic microbial diversity in freshwater environments and the potential impacts of water quality and climate change (rainy season) on the functioning of these ecosystems.

**CHAPTER IV: CHARACTERIZING A
SUBTROPICAL HYPEREUTROPHIC
LAKE: FROM PHYSICOCHEMICAL
VARIABLES TO SHOTGUN
METAGENOMIC DATA**

This chapter focuses on characterizing a subtropical hypereutrophic lake from physicochemical variables to shotgun metagenomic data to accomplish the fourth aim of this thesis. Sample sequencing was financed through the 2022 Core Lab Genomics Tec-BASE Seed Fund for Research Projects from Tecnológico de Monterrey.

In this chapter, the taxonomic and functional structure of the microbial communities in Lake Cajititlán was examined during the rainy season using shotgun metagenomic sequencing, the physicochemical characteristics of this lake and its interaction with the microbial communities were also analyzed to identify the main factors affecting water quality and biota, specifically fish. A screening of the bacterial communities that could be involved in fish mortality in this reservoir, and their genes associated with pathogenicity in fish mortality (*fur*, *luxS*, *aer*, *act*, *aha*, *exu*, *lip*, *ser*) was carried out. Finally, the dynamics of the microbial communities within Lake Cajititlán and their genes associated with the functional properties of the main biogeochemical cycles (nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and carbon) were analyzed.

The summary conclusions of this chapter indicate that abiotic factors could influence the microbial communities of Lake Cajititlán, generating a surplus of microorganisms that can thrive under high amounts of nutrients and low dissolved oxygen, causing a microenvironment not typically found in healthy lakes. In addition, genetic evidence from the microbial communities suggests that genes involved in nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and carbon metabolism were regulated by anthropogenic sources of nutrients that reached the lake from diffuse and non-diffuse sources.

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Characterizing a subtropical hypereutrophic lake: from physicochemical variables to shotgun metagenomic data

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A. Summary

Lake Cajititlán is a subtropical and endorheic lake, which is heavily impacted by nutrient pollution. Agricultural runoff and poorly treated wastewater have entered this reservoir at alarming rates during past rainy seasons, causing the cultural eutrophication of this body of water and resulting in several massive fish kill events. In this study, shotgun metagenomic sequencing was used to examine the taxonomic and functional structure of microbial communities in Lake Cajititlán during the rainy season. Several water quality features and their interactions with microbial communities were also assessed to identify the major factors affecting the water quality and biota, specifically fish species. According to current water quality regulations, most of the physicochemical variables analyzed (dissolved oxygen, pH, Secchi disk, NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , blue-green algae, total phosphorus, and chlorophyll-*a*) were outside of the permissible limits. *Planktothrix agardhii* and *Microcystis aeruginosa* were the most abundant phytoplankton species, and the dominant bacterial genera were *Pseudomonas*, *Streptomyces*, and *Flavobacterium*, with *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, and *Aeromonas veronii* representing the most abundant bacterial species. All of these microorganisms have been reported to be potentially harmful to fish, and the latter three (*P. fluorescens*, *S. maltophilia*, *A. veronii*) also contain genes associated with pathogenicity in fish mortality (*fur*, *luxS*, *aer*, *act*, *aha*, *exu*, *lip*, *ser*). Genetic evidence from the microbial communities analyzed herein reveals that

anthropogenic sources of nutrients in the lake altered genes involved in nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and carbon metabolism, mainly at the beginning of the rainy season. These findings suggest that abiotic factors influence the structure of the microbial communities, along with the major biogeochemical cycles of Lake Cajititlán, resulting in temporal variations and an excess of microorganisms that can thrive in high-nutrient and low-oxygen environments. After reviewing the literature, this appears to be the first study that focuses on characterizing the water quality of a subtropical hypereutrophic lake through associations between physicochemical variables and shotgun metagenomic data. In addition, there are few studies that have coupled the metabolism of aquatic ecosystems with nutrient cycles.

B. Introduction

Anthropogenic activities and processes negatively impact water sources around the world, degrading the health of these systems, along with the ecological services they support and the biodiversity they harbor (Dokulil *et al.*, 2000; de Anda and Shear, 2001; Skoulikidis *et al.*, 2006; Skoulikidis, 2009; Kagalou *et al.*, 2012; Kalogianni *et al.*, 2017; Katsuki *et al.*, 2019; Abell *et al.*, 2019; Yu *et al.*, 2020; Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021).

In freshwater environments, phytoplankton make up the autotrophic component of the planktonic community and are thus the base of the food web. Massive phytoplankton blooms impact aquatic habitats by blocking light penetration and depleting oxygen at night (Ssebiyonga *et al.*, 2013). In addition, certain genera of cyanobacteria (*Microcystis*, *Anabaena*, *Planktothrix*, *Oscillatoria*, *Anabaenopsis*, *Nostoc*) can be toxic to fish because they produce microcystins, a class of peptide toxins that can cause cell damage and organismal death by inhibiting phosphatases (Fu *et al.*, 2005). Furthermore, some of the bacterial species can cause serious disease in fish. For instance, *Aeromonas veronii* can affect freshwater fish, amphibians, birds, and mammals (D'Aloia *et al.*, 1996; Ghenghesh *et al.*, 1999; Zhang *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, *Pseudomonas fluorescens* is the most common culprit of fish illness and is frequently associated with skin and fin diseases (Pełkala-Safińska, 2018). There have likewise been reports of health disorders and mortality in freshwater fish caused by *Shewanella putrefaciens*, *Acinetobacter* spp., and *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* (Pełkala-Safińska, 2018).

Changes in lake water quality impact microbial communities and their metabolic activities, altering biogeochemical processes such as sulfur, nitrogen, phosphorus, and carbon metabolism (Liu *et al.*, 2018; Wang *et al.*, 2018; Yao *et al.*, 2018; Hupfer and Lewandowski, 2008). However, there is still limited knowledge on the interactions between water quality and biogeochemical processes within tropical and subtropical lake ecosystems (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021, 2022). Therefore, it is crucial to understand how microbial metabolism drives biogeochemical processes in these types of lakes that have high levels of nutrient pollution (Newton *et al.*, 2011; Graham *et al.*, 2016). Microbial metagenomics has proven to be quite valuable in informing remediation strategies for deteriorated ecosystems (Bowker, 2007; Steven *et al.*, 2012). This technique allows for a fuller understand of the microbial community and what drives its structure, knowledge which is necessary for informed decision making (Guisan *et al.*, 2013). Most of the reported metagenomic studies in lakes have been performed using amplicon sequencing, which is the most widely used approach for characterizing microbial diversity (Sharpton, 2014; Parulekar *et al.*, 2017; Zhang *et al.*, 2018; Nakatsu *et al.*, 2019; Oyewusi *et al.*, 2020). Amplicon sequencing studies in bacteria and archaea usually focus on the small 16S rRNA subunit, which is a phylogenetically and taxonomically informative marker (Hassler *et al.*, 2022). Alternatively, in shotgun metagenomic sequencing, the entire genome is divided into small fragments and individually sequenced. This produces DNA sequences (reads) that align with multiple genomic regions (contigs) (Quince *et al.*, 2017). As a result, metagenomic data allows researchers to investigate the following two elements of a microbial community simultaneously: 1) which organisms are present (bacteria, viruses, eukaryotes, archaea), and 2) what can they do (Hamady and Knight, 2009).

Lake Cajititlán is a small endorheic, subtropical, shallow lake located in the municipality of Tlajomulco de Zúñiga in the Mexican state of Jalisco (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). This lake is both a symbol of identity and an important source of income for the inhabitants of Tlajomulco and the surrounding area, as the main economic activities of the region (e.g., tourism and fishing) depend on it. However, Lake Cajititlán is currently at risk of severe degradation due to the construction of new housing developments, the overexploitation of aquifers, and because of local, municipal, and agricultural wastewater that is being directly discharged to the lake (Caro-Becerra *et al.*, 2017). Agriculture is the main economic activity in the Lake's basin. Nevertheless, due to the

excessive use of fertilizers, agricultural activities are one of the primary sources of nutrient pollution, resulting in cultural eutrophication process that is exacerbated by the endorheic nature of this reservoir (de Anda *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, the water quality of this lake is also affected by the lack of tertiary treatments to remove nutrients from wastewater, which is discharged into the lake from three municipal wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) (de Anda *et al.*, 2019). As a result, the lake has become hypereutrophic, triggering phytoplankton blooms, which have caused several massive fish kills between 2013 and 2022. All of these fish kill events occurred either during or immediately following the rainy season (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2018; de Anda *et al.*, 2019) due to the high rates of dissolved oxygen (DO) consumption by primary consumers during the night cycle, resulting in oxygen depletion (anoxia/hypoxia) (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2018, 2020). Understanding the structure and function of microbial communities in freshwater lakes with severe anthropogenic pollution problems, like Lake Cajititlán, would greatly benefit remediation plans. Therefore, the objective of the present study was to assess the associations between water quality and microbial communities within Lake Cajititlán by analyzing several physicochemical variables along with shotgun metagenomic data during the rainy season. After reviewing the literature, this appears to be the first study that focuses on understanding the water quality of a subtropical hypereutrophic lake through associations between physicochemical variables and the structure and function of microbial communities using shotgun metagenomic sequencing.

C. Experimental methods

C.1. Study area

Lake Cajititlán is a subtropical endorheic lake in the state of Jalisco, located about 25 kilometers from Guadalajara, Mexico's second largest city (Limón-Macías *et al.*, 1983; Caro-Becerra *et al.*, 2017; Fig. 21). The storage volume is 70.89 hm³, the maximum depth is 5.4 m, and the surface area is 1,744 ha (de Anda *et al.*, 2019). As reported by Gradilla-Hernández *et al.* (2019), the hot-dry season in the area lasts from February to May, the rainy season is from June to September, and the cold-dry season is from October to January. According to monthly historical trends (1998–2018) in precipitation for Lake Cajititlán, July receives the most precipitation (7.60 mm), followed by August (5.93 mm) and then September (5.93 mm) (5.47 mm) (CONAGUA, 2021). Annual historical behavior for the TN:TP ratio and the ecosystem-specific water quality index

(ES-WQI) for Lake Cajititlán has also been reported, with the lowest ES-WQI values in July and the highest fluctuations in the TN:TP ratio during the rainy season (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021).

Physicochemical data were measured *in situ* once a month from March to September 2018 at three depths (80 cm, intermediate depth, and interstitial) and at five sampling stations (CEA-1, CEA-2, CEA-3, CEA-4, and CEA-5; Fig. 21). Dissolved oxygen (DO), electrical conductivity (EC), pH, water temperature (WT), nitrate (NO_3^-), ammonium (NH_4^+), turbidity, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), phycocyanin-containing blue-green algae (BGA-PC), and chlorophyll-*a* were measured using two multiparameter probes (6600 and 6829 V2 YSI® at xylem brand, OH, USA) (YSI, 2009). Furthermore, during the rainy season (July-September) of 2018, water samples were taken once a month for shotgun metagenomic analysis, as these months have displayed the lowest water quality index values recorded in Lake Cajititlán and because the massive fish kill events were observed during these same months (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2018; de Anda *et al.*, 2019; Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). Water samples were collected using a Van Dorn water sampler at the same sites and depths that the physicochemical parameters were measured and were placed in disinfected 1L plastic containers. Two duplicates of each sample (2 L each) were taken, for a total of 60 samples. Total nitrogen (TN) and total phosphorus (TP) measurements were provided by the State Water Commission (CEA by its Spanish abbreviation). These measurements were taken at a depth of 0.8 meters at the same sites and sampling months as the other physicochemical parameters.

Figure 21. Geographical location of Lake Cajititlán and its watershed. Map derived from Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021 publication.

C.2. DNA extraction and metagenomic shotgun sequencing

Each water sample replicate was first filtered using a membrane with a 20-25 μm pore diameter. The filtrate was subsequently run through a second membrane with a 0.45 μm pore size. The FastDNA Spin Kit for Soil (MP Biomedicals, OH, United States) was then used to extract and purify the DNA from the samples, by adding 100 mg of each filter piece to a lysis matrix according to the manufacturer's instructions. Quantification of DNA was conducted using a NanoDrop ND-1000 UV-Vis spectrophotometer (NanoDrop Technologies, Wilmington, DE). The DNA samples were then pooled by the depth of each site (CEA-1 to CEA-5) and sampling month (July to September; e.g., sample 1: CEA-1/July/80 cm and interstitial), to ultimately obtain 30 total samples (five samples per sampling month and its replica, July=10, August=10, and September=10). The samples were then cleaned using the AM Pure XP kit (Beckman Coulter, IN, USA), and their DNA was quantified using the Qubit 2.0 fluorometer (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA). Additionally, absorbance ratios at 260/280 and 260/230 nm were measured to analyze the purity of the samples. Finally, the samples were subjected to shotgun metagenomic sequencing on

the Illumina® Novaseq6000 platform (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA), yielding paired-end read lengths of 2 x 150 bp and 5 Gb of clean data per sample. Sequencing was carried out at the National Genomic Sequencing Laboratory Tec-BASE of Tecnológico de Monterrey.

C.3. Bioinformatic analyses

OmicsBox 2.0.36 bioinformatics software was used to analyze and process the raw reads from the Lake Cajititlán samples (BioBam Bioinformatics, 2019). The reads were preprocessed using the Trimmomatic tool, which includes removing adapters and contaminant sequences, trimming bases, and filtering short, low-quality reads (Bolger *et al.*, 2014). Subsequently, the samples were subjected to a quality control check using the FASTQ tool (Andrews, 2010). The final clean paired-end reads for each sample were individually subjected to metagenomic assembly using metaSPAdes, which is an assembly toolkit containing several assembly pipelines based on the de Bruijn graph (Nurk *et al.*, 2017). The assemblages were then compared to the RefSeq v.2021_04 database using Kraken2 to obtain the microbial composition of Lake Cajititlán (Wood *et al.*, 2019). Metagenomic gene prediction was performed using FragGeneScan, which is an application to find (fragmented) genes in short reads (Rho *et al.*, 2010). The samples were then functionally annotated using the EggNOG mapper, which employs precomputed EggNOG-based orthology assignments (Huerta-Cepas *et al.*, 2018). Finally, using the "Sample comparison GO chart" function, a comparative analysis of genetic ontology annotations was performed between the different samples of each month.

C.4. Statistical analysis

All statistical analyses were carried out using the R (R version 4.1.2) software unless otherwise stated (R Core Team, 2021). All bar graphs and line plots were constructed using the ggplot2 package (Wickham, 2016). The heatmap was developed using the dist() function and the pheatmap package (Kolde, 2019). Mean values and standard deviations (SD) were calculated for each physicochemical parameter by sampling month with the mean() and sd() functions. One-way analyses of variance (ANOVA) ($\alpha=0.05$) were performed to test for temporal differences in water quality features. The mean physicochemical parameter values were compared to different national standards and international recommendations (Vollenweider and Kerekes, 1981, 1982; Salas, 2003; WHO, 2003; MRCCC, 2013; LFD, 2019; NOM-001, 2021).

A box plot was created to depict the relative read abundances of Lake Cajititlán's microbial communities at the domain-level (archaea, bacteria, eukaryotes, and viruses). The relative read abundance of each of the 30 samples was calculated individually, and the results were plotted by sampling month. All boxplots were constructed to incorporate the results of one-way ANOVA ($\alpha= 0.05$) and Tukey's HSD tests, which were performed using the stats package's TukeyHSD function (R Core Team, 2021). Phytoplankton species and bacterial genera were examined using bar graphs of relative read abundance over the sampling month. Bar charts were created using the scales packages. Taxa of phytoplankton species and bacterial genera that were found in proportions of less than 0.01%, were categorized as "others" (Wickham and Seidel, 2022).

Principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) was also performed to investigate differences in phytoplankton species and bacterial genera across the sampling months. The vegan package and the cmdscale function were used to calculate distances based on Bray-Curtis differences (Oksanen *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, a pairwise analysis of variance (ADONIS) was also conducted using the vegan package and the adonis2() function to test the significance of temporal changes in the composition of Lake Cajititlán's bacterial and phytoplankton communities (Clarke, 1993; Anderson, 2001; Anderson *et al.*, 2006). Additionally, a redundancy analysis (RDA) was performed to determine the relationship between these communities and the physicochemical parameters using the vegan and ggord packages (Oksanen *et al.*, 2022; Beck, 2021).

A literature search was conducted to analyze which bacterial species have been reported as pathogenic to fish using different terms or keywords such as pathogenic bacteria, fish pathogens, fish pathogenic bacteria, fish bacterial disease, fish diseases, and fish pathogens, among others. This search was performed using PubMed, PubMed Central, ScienceDirect, JSTOR and Scopus databases, resulting in 22 articles relevant to the objective (Loch and Faisal, 2010; Menanteau-Ledouble *et al.*, 2016; Basri *et al.*, 2020; Pękala-Safińska, 2018; Shabana *et al.*, 2022; Swain *et al.*, 2007; Wang *et al.*, 2009; Li *et al.*, 2020; Geng *et al.*, 2007; Geng *et al.*, 2010a, b; Ellermeier and Schlauch 2007; Johnson *et al.*, 2011; Troxell *et al.*, 2010; Liu *et al.*, 2015; Ilardi *et al.*, 2009; Almodóvar *et al.*, 2004; Ngwa *et al.*, 2014; Bukowska *et al.*, 2017; Dang *et al.*, 2011; Humbert *et al.*, 2013; Harke *et al.*, 2016).

Genes involved in the metabolism of carbon, nitrogen, and sulfur, as well as in the phosphorus cycle were searched for in the KEGG database (<https://www.genome.jp/kegg/ko.html>), and the abundance of the group of genes by metabolic pathway was shown through bar charts of relative read abundance per sampling month using the phyloseq and vegan packages (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2015 and 2016; McMurdie and Holmes, 2013; Oksanen *et al.*, 2022). Finally, the metabolic pathways that were statistically significant for each sampling month were thoroughly analyzed, and a graphic representation of the metabolic pathways, their stages, and the genes involved was created, followed by a Euclidean distance heatmap to visualize gene abundance per sampling month (Kolde, 2019).

D. Results

D.1. Water quality characteristics

All physicochemical parameters, except for TN and TP, showed significant temporal fluctuations when comparing the values reported for the seven sampling months (Table 26). Most of these parameters were outside the permissible limits. However, March (which is in the hot-dry season) showed the fewest parameters outside the limits. WT and EC were the only variables that were within acceptable limits for all the months analyzed. The lowest ORP values and highest turbidity values were observed in July, whereas the highest TN values were observed in June, the onset of the rainy season (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2019). Compared with the limits established by the applicable Mexican regulation, the TP, DO, and pH were outside of the permissible limits for all months, except for the DO, which was found to be within these guidelines for March and June (Table 26).

Table 26. Water physicochemical features of Lake Cajititlán between March–September of 2018. The asterisk symbol in the parameters denotes statistical significance among months at a $p < 0.05$ level. Underlined values indicate that they exceed acceptable limits. Dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, water temperature (WT), Secchi disk, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), ammonium (NH_4^+), nitrate (NO_3^-), blue-green algae (BGA-PC), chlorophyll-*a*, electrical conductivity (EC), total nitrogen, total phosphorus, and turbidity.^{1,1} Use 1. Aquatic life protection: freshwater, includes wetlands (LDF, 2019); ^{1,2} Use 2. Aquatic life protection: coastal waters and estuaries (LDF, 2019); ² NOM-001, 2021; ³ MRCCC,2013; ⁴ WHO, 2003; ⁵ Vollenweider and Kerekes, 1981, 1982; Salas, 2003.

Parameter	Unit	Acceptable limit	Mar Mean \pm SD	Apr Mean \pm SD	May Mean \pm SD	Jun Mean \pm SD	Jul Mean \pm SD	Aug Mean \pm SD	Sep Mean \pm SD
DO*	mg/L	5.00 ^{1,1}	6.14 \pm 3.22	<u>3.96 \pm 3.29</u>	<u>4.43 \pm 4.53</u>	6.59 \pm 3.39	<u>2.83 \pm 0.61</u>	<u>3.25 \pm 1.87</u>	<u>4.32 \pm 1.77</u>
pH*	-	6.50-8.50 ^{1,1} 6.9 ²	<u>9.19 \pm 0.07</u>	<u>8.70 \pm 0.10</u>	<u>8.82 \pm 0.11</u>	<u>9.66 \pm 0.14</u>	<u>10 \pm 0.05</u>	<u>9 \pm 0.05</u>	<u>9.28 \pm 0.19</u>
WT*	°C	35.00 ²	20.77 \pm 0.84	21.57 \pm 1.23	23.72 \pm 1.29	23.24 \pm 0.66	24.16 \pm 1.55	24.73 \pm 1.12	24.35 \pm 0.34
Secchi disk*	cm	<150.00 ⁵ Hypereutrophic	<u>8.35 \pm 3.30</u>	<u>8.45 \pm 2.56</u>	<u>8.30 \pm 0.60</u>	<u>10.06 \pm 1.48</u>	<u>9 \pm 1.14</u>	<u>21.8 \pm 7.57</u>	<u>8.2 \pm 8.09</u>
ORP*	mV	-	188.35 \pm 18.35	137.74 \pm 40.14	120.47 \pm 57.03	193.19 \pm 30.11	47.90 \pm 12.36	66.18 \pm 19.30	101.78 \pm 7.04
NH_4^+ *	mg/L	0.06 ^{1,1}	<u>2.74 \pm 0.07</u>	<u>2.83 \pm 0.67</u>	<u>2.55 \pm 0.72</u>	<u>3.02 \pm 0.17</u>	<u>4.50 \pm 0.38</u>	<u>4.08 \pm 1.46</u>	<u>2.49 \pm 0.92</u>
NO_3^- *	mg/L	0.04 ^{1,2}	<u>3.16 \pm 0.23</u>	<u>4.59 \pm 0.42</u>	<u>4.21 \pm 0.12</u>	<u>3.10 \pm 0.62</u>	<u>3.67 \pm 0.34</u>	<u>2.67 \pm 0.56</u>	<u>0.87 \pm 0.24</u>
BGA-PC*	cell/mL	100,000 ⁴	<u>272,458 \pm 3,752</u>	<u>272,446 \pm 8,133</u>	<u>274,154 \pm 9,548</u>	<u>278,447 \pm 7,608</u>	<u>275,129 \pm 5,551</u>	<u>167,662 \pm 79,268</u>	<u>268,078 \pm 3,996</u>
Chlorophyll- <i>a</i> *	$\mu\text{g/L}$	>25.00 ⁵ Hypereutrophic	<u>47.30 \pm 8.40</u>	<u>45.30 \pm 9.74</u>	<u>52.92 \pm 11.29</u>	<u>40.53 \pm 2.54</u>	<u>42.16 \pm 5.20</u>	<u>42.83 \pm 7.40</u>	<u>47.40 \pm 9.36</u>
EC*	mS/cm	0-1.5 ³	1.00 \pm 0.01	1.07 \pm 0.02	1.04 \pm 0.01	1.11 \pm 0.005	1.08 \pm 0.003	1.21 \pm 0.16	1.16 \pm 0.12
TN	mg/L	-	11.33 \pm 1.77	12.51 \pm 3.75	14.21 \pm 5.58	15.87 \pm 4.67	11.46 \pm 1.08	12.88 \pm 2.52	9.85 \pm 0.63
TP	mg/L	0.05 ^{1,1} >0.1 ⁵ Hypereutrophic	<u>1.58 \pm 0.06</u>	<u>1.42 \pm 0.13</u>	<u>1.64 \pm 0.09</u>	<u>1.58 \pm 0.06</u>	<u>1.51 \pm 0.06</u>	<u>1.52 \pm 0.24</u>	<u>1.41 \pm 0.10</u>
Turbidity*	NTU	-	76.84 \pm 2.17	88.11 \pm 9.32	94.99 \pm 10.55	106.89 \pm 4.13	97.40 \pm 5.87	42.17 \pm 6.46	68.94 \pm 7.13

D.2. Bioinformatic analysis

The sequencing of all samples resulted in a total of 748,721,392 raw reads and 748,721,392 contigs (Table 27). Kraken2 was used to compare the reads to the RefSeq v.2021_04 reference database, resulting in 29,544,581 total reads (49.87%) that were classified in one of the following taxonomic domains: bacteria (46.45%), eukaryotes (3.17%), archaea (0.27%) and viruses (0.07%) (Table 27). Regarding EggNOG Mapper results, a predicted gene annotation of 12,491,565 (> 18%) was obtained (Table 28). Classified reads per month ranged from 49.98% to 51.72% (Table 28). Statistical analyses revealed no significant differences in the abundance of archaea and viruses per sampling month (Fig. 22). However, temporal differences were detected in the bacteria and eukaryotes. Furthermore, an inverse trend was observed between these two domains in the first two months (July and August); while the relative read abundance of bacteria decreased, the abundance of eukaryotes increased (Fig. 22).

Table 27. Number of reads and contigs obtained from sequencing data analysis at domain level.

Domain (30 samples)	Total initial reads	Total clean reads	Total contigs	Taxonomic classification of contigs (%)	Unclassified contigs (%)
Bacteria				27,457,854 (46.45)	
Eukaryota	748,721,392	731,028,699	59,236,568	1,881,981 (3.17)	29,691,987 (50.12)
Archaea				160,851 (0.27)	
Viruses				43,895 (0.07)	

Table 28. Number of contigs and annotation results by sampling month.

Month	n	Total contigs	Taxonomic classification of contigs (%)	Total predicted genes	EggNOG annotation sequence (%)
Jul	1	23,077,10	11,534,336	26,937,166	4,897,282
	0	5	(49.98)		(18.18)
Aug	1	16,657,43	8,615,889	19,793,200	3,645,666
	0	8	(51.72)		(18.42)
Sep	1	18,182,99	9,394,356	21,173,907	3,948,617
	0	9	(51.67)		(18.65)

Figure 22. Relative read abundance of Lake Cajititlán's microbial communities at the domain level by sampling month: (A) Archaea, (B) Bacteria, (C) Eukaryota, and (D) Viruses. Relative read abundances were calculated separately for each domain.

D.3. Temporal variations of the diversity and abundance of phytoplankton and bacterial communities

The diversity and abundance of phytoplankton (Fig. 23) and bacterial communities (Fig. 24) were assessed at different sampling months using relative read abundance bar plots. The temporal differences were examined using PCoA. RDAs were then used to evaluate the relationship between the presence and prevalence of these communities and the physicochemical variables of Lake Cajititlán. Within the phytoplankton communities, *Planktothrix agardhii* (17.70%) and *Microcystis aeruginosa* (14.00%) were consistently the most abundant species during all sampled months (Fig. 23A). The *Pseudomonas* (8.95%), *Streptomyces* (5.32%), and *Flavobacterium* (3.36%) bacterial genera were the most abundant in all sampled months (Fig. 24A). Significant temporal variations were only detected in the composition of the phytoplankton ($p < 0.05$) and bacterial ($p < 0.05$) communities between July and September according to the ADONIS analysis (but not observed with the PCoA analysis) (Fig. 23B, and 24B; Table 29, and 30).

Figure 23. (A) Phytoplankton species relative read abundance by sampling month. (B) PCoA of phytoplankton communities by sampling month. (C) RDA of phytoplankton composition and physicochemical variables by sampling month. Dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, water temperature (WT), oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrate (NO₃⁻), blue-green algae (BGA-PC), chlorophyll-*a* and electrical conductivity (EC).

Figure 24. (A) Relative read abundance of bacteria genera by sampling month. (B) PCoA of bacterial communities by sampling month. (C) RDA of bacterial composition and physicochemical variables by sampling month. Dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, water temperature (WT), oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrate (NO₃⁻), blue-green algae (BGA-PC), chlorophyll-a and electrical conductivity (EC).

Table 29. Pairwise dissimilarity tests of phytoplankton communities for the different months using ADONIS. The numbers outside the parentheses are “R².” P-values are in parenthesis. Bold values denote statistical significance at the $p < 0.05$ level.

Phytoplankton communities	All (P-values)
All	0.13 (0.55)
Jul vs. Aug	0.05 (0.38)
Jul vs. Sep	0.20 (0.05)
Aug vs. Sep	0.06 (0.21)

Table 30. Pairwise dissimilarity tests of the bacterial communities for the different months using ADONIS. The numbers outside the parentheses are “R².” P-values are in parenthesis. Bold values denote statistical significance at the $p < 0.05$ level.

Bacterial communities	All (P-values)
All	0.05 (0.62)
Jul vs. Aug	0.03 (0.07)
Jul vs. Sep	0.25 (0.05)
Aug vs. Sep	0.04 (0.55)

According to the RDA, the physicochemical factors that were most correlated with the taxonomic composition of the phytoplankton communities during July were TP and pH. Similarly, NH₄⁺, NO₃⁻, and TP were most correlated with the communities in August and EC and turbidity were most correlated with the taxonomic composition in September (Fig. 23C). The first three redundancy components explained 55% of the variability (RDA1: 25%; RDA2: 17%; RDA3: 13%) (Table 31). The first component was positively correlated with ORP. The second component was negatively correlated with NH₄⁺ and TN, but positively correlated with BGA-PC. Turbidity, ORP, pH, and NO₃⁻ were the most highly (positively) correlated parameters with the third component (Table 32). Likewise, WT, NH₄⁺, chlorophyll-*a* and BGA-PC were most correlated with the taxonomic composition of the bacterial communities in July. NH₄⁺, TP, and TN were most correlated with the communities in August, whereas TP, ORP, and DO were more

correlated with the taxonomic composition in September (Fig. 24C). The first three components explained 61% of the variability (RDA1: 39%; RDA2: 14%; RDA3: 8%; Table 33). DO, BGA-PC, and TN were most (positively) correlated with the first component. The second component was most correlated with TN (positive correlation), along with BGA-PC and chlorophyll-*a* (both with negative correlations). DO and TP were the most highly (positively) correlated with the third component, (Table 34).

Parameters with positive correlations may imply that microorganisms thrive in environments with higher values of these physicochemical factors. Conversely, negative correlations indicate that higher values of these parameters negatively influence the predominance of microbial populations during the study period (Liu *et al.*, 2014).

Table 31. Redundancy analysis (RDA) of phytoplankton communities. Eigenvalues, proportion explained, and cumulative proportion by 12 RDA axes are shown.

Component	Eigenvalue	Proportion explained	Cumulative proportion
RD1	21.52	0.25	0.25
RD2	13.44	0.17	0.42
RD3	9.30	0.13	0.55
RD4	7.30	0.09	0.64
RD5	5.80	0.09	0.73
RD6	4.87	0.07	0.8
RD7	4.50	0.07	0.87
RD8	4.36	0.05	0.92
RD9	3.71	0.03	0.95
RD10	3.11	0.02	0.97
RD11	2.72	0.02	0.99
RD12	2.22	0.01	1.00

Table 32. Eigenvalues of the physicochemical variables in the RDA of phytoplankton communities. Water temperature (WT), dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, electrical conductivity (EC), ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrate (NO₃⁻), turbidity, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), blue-green algae (BGA-PC), total nitrogen (TN), total phosphorus (TP).

Variable	RDA1	RDA2	RDA3	RDA4
DO	0.08	0.44	-0.24	-0.56
pH	0.17	0.20	0.66	-0.03
WT	0.14	-0.17	0.11	-0.72
Turbidity	0.06	0.19	0.66	0.07
ORP	0.41	0.11	0.74	0.04
NH ₄ ⁺	0.07	-0.47	0.41	-0.51
NO ₃ ⁻	0.23	-0.45	0.67	-0.10
BGA-PC	0.14	0.52	0.20	0.33
Chlorophyll- <i>a</i>	0.25	0.39	-0.08	-0.05
EC	-0.10	0.01	-0.13	0.11
TN	0.45	-0.78	-0.14	-0.03
TP	-0.22	-0.19	0.10	-0.66

Table 33. Redundancy analysis (RDA) of bacterial composition. Eigenvalues, proportion explained, and cumulative proportion by 12 RDA axes are shown.

Component	Eigenvalue	Proportion explained	Cumulative proportion
RD1	277.01	0.39	0.39
RD2	103.70	0.14	0.53
RD3	62.07	0.08	0.61
RD4	58.13	0.08	0.69
RD5	36.72	0.05	0.74
RD6	33.73	0.04	0.78
RD7	30.12	0.04	0.82
RD8	23.93	0.03	0.85

RD9	23.73	0.05	0.90
RD10	22.46	0.03	0.93
RD11	19.82	0.04	0.97
RD12	18.50	0.03	1.00

Table 34. Eigenvalues of the physicochemical variables in the RDA of bacterial communities. Water temperature (WT), dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, electrical conductivity (EC), ammonium (NH₄⁺), nitrate (NO₃⁻), turbidity, oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), blue-green algae (BGA-PC), total nitrogen (TN), total phosphorus (TP).

Variable	RDA1	RDA2	RDA3	RDA4
DO	0.30	-0.23	0.26	0.75
pH	0.14	-0.34	0.04	-0.14
WT	0.08	0.14	0.13	0.65
Turbidity	0.11	-0.27	0.02	-0.14
ORP	0.26	-0.15	-0.02	-0.41
NH ₄ ⁺	-0.13	0.15	0.17	-0.06
NO ₃ ⁻	0.05	0.06	-0.12	-0.40
BGA-PC	0.30	-0.34	0.06	-0.20
Chlorophyll- <i>a</i>	0.25	-0.33	0.15	-0.07
EC	-0.16	0.01	-0.11	-0.21
TN	0.32	0.76	-0.16	-0.13
TP	-0.25	-0.04	0.23	0.29

D.4. Bacterial species and their virulence factors reported as pathogenic for fish

A literature search was carried out to determine which bacterial species have been reported as fish pathogens in other freshwater bodies to compare with this study. *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (21.37%), *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* (18.86%), and *Aeromonas veronii* (12.58%) were the most abundant species, as shown in in Figure 25. The monthly abundance of *P. fluorescens* (50.03%) was higher in July, and its abundance decreased throughout the sampling months. The relative abundance of *S. maltophilia* remained constant during the three-month investigation. The highest abundance of *A. veronii* was observed in August (50.73%), followed by July (38.74%) and September (10.53%). The remaining pathogenic bacteria in the chord diagram were found to be less abundant for all three months of study.

P. fluorescens is one of the main causes of septicemic diseases in freshwater fish, causing severe economic losses in aquaculture (Shabana *et al.*, 2022; Swain *et al.*, 2007; Wang *et al.*, 2009). This species is usually associated with pathologies of the skin and fins of fish and has also been reported to cause sudden mortality in fish (Pełkala-Safińska, 2018). *A. veronii* is a major pathogen causing sepsis and ulcer syndrome in freshwater fish (Li *et al.*, 2020). *S. maltophilia* has been reported to cause infectious intussusception syndrome in these freshwater animals (Geng *et al.*, 2007; Geng *et al.*, 2010a, b). The virulence factors that play an essential role in the development of diseases caused by *P. fluorescens* and *A. veronii* in fish are depicted in a heatmap (Fig. 26). So far, no information has been found on virulence genes associated with *S. maltophilia* fish diseases. For *P. fluorescens* to be infectious to the host, the acquisition of iron is essential, which is related to the pathogenic *fur* gene (Ellermeier and Schlauch 2007; Johnson *et al.*, 2011; Troxell *et al.*, 2010; Liu *et al.*, 2015). The highest relative abundance of the *fur* gene occurred in July, followed by September, while the fewest were observed in August (Fig. 26). The genes responsible for diseases (sepsis and ulcer syndrome) caused by *A. veronii* are as follows: *aer*, *act*, *aha*, *ser*, *exu*, *lip*, and *luxS* (Li *et al.*, 2020). The heatmap shows a trend like that of the *fur* gene, with all virulence genes most abundant in July, followed by September, and then August. The *exu* (nuclease) gene was the most abundant gene, while *luxS* (quorum sensing controlled gene) was the least abundant (Li *et al.*, 2020; Fig. 26).

Figure 25. Chord diagram showing the distribution of bacterial species reported as pathogenic for fish. The numbers around the circumference represent the percentage of relative abundance coverage of the bacterial species by sampling month in Lake Cajititlán.

Figure 26. Heatmap with virulence factors that play an important role in the development of diseases caused by *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and *Aeromonas veronii* in fish through the study months. Ferric uptake regulator (*fur*), S-ribosylhomocysteinase (*luxS*), aerolysin (*aer*), cytotoxic enterotoxin (*act*), adhesin (*aha*), DNases (*exu*), lipase (*lip*), serine protease (*ser*).

D.5. Influence of microbial communities on biogeochemical cycles

The relative read abundances of functional genes involved in the biogeochemical cycles for nitrogen, phosphorus, carbon, and sulfur were calculated based on annotated reads (Fig. 27). In general, all of the biogeochemical cycle pathways were more abundant in July, then decreased in

August, and slightly increased in September. The genes associated with sulfur metabolism only displayed significant differences between July and September (p-value= 0.0352; Fig. 27A) for the sulfur oxidation system (SOX system). No significant differences were identified regarding central carbon metabolism (Fig. 27B). The genes associated with nitrogen metabolism showed significant differences for all of the following pathways: the denitrification pathway (July vs. September: p-value= 0.0169), the comammox pathway (July vs. September: p-value= 0.0257), the dissimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonia (DNRA) pathway (July vs. August: p-value = 0.0017; July vs. September: p-value= 0.0016), the assimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonia pathway (ANRA) (July vs. August: p-value= 0.0007 July vs. September: p-value= 0.0001), and the nitrification pathway (July vs. September: p-value= 0.0317). There were no temporal variations in the nitrogen fixation or the anammox pathways (Fig. 27C). Regarding the phosphorus cycle, the relative read abundance of genes involved in microbial regulation of organic P-mineralization (OPM) was significantly different between July and September (p-value= 0.0412). There were no significant temporal variations in the genes involved in inorganic P solubilization or P uptake and transport (IPS-PUT), nor in the genes related to P-starvation response regulation (PSRR; Fig. 27D).

Figure 27. Relative read abundance of genes associated with major pathways in (A) Sulfur metabolism; ASR: assimilatory sulfate reduction; DSR: dissimilatory sulfate reduction; SOX system: sulfur oxidation system. (B) Central carbon metabolism; CFPP: carbon fixation pathways in prokaryotes; CFPO: carbon fixation in photosynthetic organisms. (C) Nitrogen metabolism; DNRA: dissimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonia; ANRA: assimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonia. (D) Phosphorus cycle; IPS-PUT: Inorganic P solubilization and P uptake and transport; OPM: organic P-mineralization; PSRR: P-starvation response regulation. Different letters indicate significant differences within a single pathway.

The metabolic pathways that were statistically different between sampling month for relative read abundances were further analyzed using an Euclidean distance heatmap and a graphical

representation. (Fig. 28A). All pathways for the nitrogen cycle are depicted since the majority displayed significant differences between sampling months (Fig. 28B). The SOX system and the OPM pathways (Fig. 28C) represent sulfur and phosphorus metabolism, respectively (Fig. 28D). The pathways involved in central carbon metabolism are not displayed because no temporal variations were detected.

The heatmap reveals that most of the studied genes were overrepresented in July, then declined in August, and then some slightly surged again in September, particularly those of the SOX system pathway (Fig. 28D). However, notable exceptions were detected for some genes, such as the *nosZ* gene of the denitrification pathway, which is required to obtain N_2 from N_2O , where *nosZ* was more highly represented in July and August and displayed the lowest annotated reads in September. Reads for the *amoCAB* genes, which are necessary to produce hydroxylamine (NH_2OH) from NH_4 , decreased throughout the months of the study (Fig. 28B). The *soxZ* gene, which is required to produce S, SO_3 and SH in the SOX system pathway of sulfur metabolism, was most abundant in September, followed by July, and August (Fig. 28C). Finally, the *phn* gene, which is required for the mineralization of organic phosphorus in the OPM pathway of the phosphorus cycle, was most abundant in August, followed by July and September (Fig. 28D).

Figure 28. (A) Heatmap of significant metabolic pathways and their genes. (B) Nitrogen metabolism. (C) Sulfur pathway; sulfur oxidation system (SOX system). (D) Phosphorus pathway; organic P-mineralization (OPM). Genes with asterisks indicate that they were detected in this study.

E. Discussion

E.1. The water quality of Lake Cajititlán

Most physicochemical parameters (except for WT and EC) from March to September 2018 were outside of the permissible limits defined by the applicable Mexican regulation and international water quality recommendations (Table 26). This is concerning because the reservoir's main activity is commercial fishing as well as weekend recreational boat trips, implying an impact on the local economy, i.e., loss of tourism, aesthetic value, fisheries, and seriously affecting the food web dynamics and nutrient balance (de Anda *et al.*, 2019).

The rapid changes in water quality parameters during the wet season have been attributed to runoff caused by heavy rainfall (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021, 2022). Furthermore, significant temporal changes in physicochemical parameters can be observed even during the dry-hot season (March-May; Table 26), indicating that these alterations could be due mainly to climate change impacts on the hydrological cycle of Lake Cajititlán (Inglezakis *et al.*, 2016). Consequently, the physicochemical and biological properties of this body of water are concerning throughout the year. Other research in lakes and estuaries have focused on the influence of climate change on water temperature, nutrient loads, and eutrophication (Kirilova *et al.*, 2011; Chaturvedi *et al.*, 2021). An analysis of the potential effects of climate change in the basin region of Lake Cajititlán would allow for a better understanding of the seasonal dynamics in the reservoir's physicochemical parameters.

Eutrophication is assessed using the OECD's trophic status classification, which considers three parameters: TP, chlorophyll-*a*, and secchi disc transparency (Caspers, 1982). According to the findings of this study, Lake Cajititlán is classified as hypereutrophic because the values of these three parameters fell into that category during all seven months of evaluation (Table 26). This is the worst OECD classification in terms of trophic status and water quality in bodies of water. According to Ram *et al.* (2014) and Kangur *et al.* (2005), the main causes for massive fish kills in different bodies of water include natural and anthropogenic hypoxia as well as the proliferation of harmful algae. Accordingly, the presence of phytoplankton biomass as well as fish killed or fish gasping for air on the surface of Lake Cajititlán were observed during the monitoring activities of this study. Moreover, cyanobacteria species that are capable of producing toxins that harm fish were identified through shotgun metagenomics. Five of the seven months studied (Table 26) displayed DO levels below the acceptable limit for aquatic life (5 mg/L; LFD, 2019), which could be driving the mass fish kill episodes in Lake Cajititlán (Smith and Schindler, 2009; OECD and Díaz, 2010).

E.2. Dynamics and abundance of the microbial communities and their physicochemical influences

There are very few studies on the analysis of microbial communities of a freshwater system, and even fewer a eutrophic state and are being analyzed with shotgun metagenomics. In this have

study, approximately 50% of the total reads were classified taxonomically (Table 27). These findings were compared with a similar study, which examined water samples from soda lakes with and without cyanobacterial blooms and using the same metagenomic pipeline as this study. The authors analyzed 24 water samples and obtained about 14 million reads, of which 5,385,139 reads were taxonomically assigned (less than 50%; Andreote *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, it is possible to infer that current genomic databases have limitations and are not representative of water microbiomes. Most of the information added to existing databases comes from pharmaceutical and industrial biotechnology, and human health research efforts, which can mislead genetic annotations of water microbiomes (for example, annotations that are obviously incompatible with water ecosystems), or there is not enough information on water microbial communities to annotate metagenomic studies (Wu *et al.*, 2009; Segata *et al.*, 2012; Huttenhower *et al.*, 2012; Choi *et al.*, 2017).

Significant temporal differences were observed in the composition of phytoplankton and bacterial communities between July and September (Table 29, and 30). This suggests that the abundance and diversity of these two communities are related, as has been shown in other lakes where changes in environmental factors and phytoplankton communities have influenced the composition of bacterial communities and ecosystem-wide changes (Woodhouse *et al.*, 2015; Ramanan *et al.*, 2016). *Planktothrix agardhii* and *Microcystis aeruginosa* were the most abundant species observed in this study (Fig. 23A). These findings are consistent with a study carried out in Lake Cajititlán that analyzed the 16S and 18S rRNA genes to study the phytoplankton communities of this reservoir, in which the genera *Planktothrix* spp. and *Microcystis* spp. were identified. However, the target metagenomic analysis used in that study did not allow for the classification of these phytoplankton groups at the species level (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021). Other studies have used other methods (e.g., Malassez counting chamber method) to characterize phytoplankton communities and reported that these two cyanobacteria species are the most dominant in phytoplankton communities in other shallow, subtropical, and eutrophic water bodies, such as Lake Cajititlán (Gaęała *et al.*, 2010; Briand *et al.*, 2008; Kruk *et al.*, 2002; Suda *et al.*, 2002; Bouchamma *et al.*, 2004). This suggests that the characteristics of this type of water bodies promote the growth of these two cyanobacteria species. Additionally, studies that investigated the genes involved in the production of microcystins (mcy-genes) revealed that

Planktothrix and *Microcystis* predominate in blooms of toxigenic cyanobacteria in freshwater bodies (Ngwa *et al.*, 2014; Bukowska *et al.*, 2017; Dang *et al.*, 2011; Humbert *et al.*, 2013; Harke *et al.*, 2016). Thus, the production of microcystins could be involved in the massive fish kill events that have occurred in Lake Cajititlán. This toxin has already been detected in the water of Lake Cajititlán in a previous study (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021), but toxicological studies regarding bioaccumulation in fish tissues are still needed to confirm this theory.

The most abundant bacterial genera were *Pseudomonas*, *Streptomyces*, and *Flavobacterium* (Fig. 24A). This is consistent with other studies that have found these taxa to be among the most abundant genera in freshwater systems, as well as eutrophic and hypereutrophic water bodies (Choi *et al.*, 2005; Michaud *et al.*, 2012; Shao *et al.*, 2021). This suggests that these bacteria thrive in subtropical and eutrophic environments, like Lake Cajititlán. Moreover, they coincide with the most abundant bacterial genera reported by Díaz-Torres *et al.* (2021) using the 16S rRNA gene, except for *Streptomyces*, which was not even identified as one of the most abundant genera (> 0.01%). Additionally certain genera that were detected herein (*Acidovorax*, *Acinetobacter*, *Aeromonas*, *Agrobacterium*, *Devosia*, *Microbacterium*, *Mycobacterium*, *Mycolicibacterium*, *Nocardioides*, *Rhizobium*, *Rhodococcus*, and *Streptomyces*) were not detected in that previous study, and vice versa (*Aromatoleum*, *Chthoniobacter*, *CL500* and *Cylindrospermopsis*). However, this is expected, as shotgun metagenomic sequencing analysis has potential advantages over meta-barcoding sequencing, such as more genetic information per sample (higher sequencing depth) and the possibility for a better quantitative match (Bell *et al.*, 2021) Furthermore, shotgun metagenomic sequencing covers all genetic information in a sample, so the data may be utilized for metabolic function profiling, metagenomic assembly and binning, antibiotic resistance gene profiling, among other things (Segata *et al.*, 2012; Sunagawa *et al.*, 2013; Laudadio *et al.*, 2019).

NH₄⁺, TP, TN, ORP, DO, EC, BGA-PC, and turbidity were the most correlated factors with the prevalence of phytoplankton and bacterial communities throughout the research period according to the RDA. The TN and NH₄⁺ parameters are important water quality factors that influence the distribution of bacterial and phytoplankton communities. These organisms need a substantial quantity of nitrogen for the synthesis of their primary constituents, which include NAD, purines

and pyrimidines, amino acids, and amino sugars. Furthermore, both these organisms and archaea are key drivers in the transformation of diverse types of N into chemical forms used by plants (NH_4^+ and NO_3^-) (Reitzer, 1996; Wang *et al.*, 2018). In Lake Cajititlán, rains have been reported to cause significant fluctuations in nutrient concentrations, which increase during the wet season due to surface runoff containing large amounts of nitrogenous and phosphorous fertilizers (Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2020; Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021, 2022). This is consistent with the were higher values of NH_4^+ observed in the wet season (June-September; mean=3.52 mg/L) compared to the dry season (March-May; mean=2.50 mg/L). In terms of TP, no significant differences were detected. Because microorganisms and plants require P in the form of phosphates, which were not evaluated in this study, the direct influence of this element on bacterial and phytoplankton populations in Lake Cajititlán cannot be correlated (CEDRSSA, 2019; Zheng *et al.*, 2019).

E.3. Analysis of bacterial species reported as pathogenic for fish

The most abundant species during the three months of this study were *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, and *Aeromonas veronii* (Fig. 25). The most important species in fish pathology is *P. fluorescens*, which is frequently associated with skin problems and fin diseases. Furthermore, infections with this species have been associated with sudden fish kills (Pełkala-Safińska, 2018). The ferric uptake regulator gene (*fur*) in the *P. fluorescens* pathogen is essential for optimum infection to occur in fish, as this gene regulates the expression of several proteins (Liu *et al.*, 2015). In this study, this species relative read abundance was greatest in July, which matched with the highest abundance of *fur* gene reads. However, no direct association was observed in August and September (Fig. 25, Fig. 26). *S. maltophilia* is commonly isolated from freshwater fish (Dungan *et al.*, 2003; Juhnke and des Jardin, 1989), causing lethargy, skin depigmentation, focal hemorrhages, petechiae, and edema in the body cavity, and even fish mortality (Geng *et al.*, 2010a).

A. veronii has been reported to infect freshwater fish, amphibians, birds, and mammals, causing significant losses in the aquaculture sector and threatening food safety (D'Aloia *et al.*, 1996; Ghenghesh *et al.*, 1999; Zhang *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, *A. veronii* can cause infections in humans, particularly the elderly and immunocompromised children, resulting in sepsis, gastroenteritis, and other diseases (Mencacci *et al.*, 2003; Roberts *et al.*, 2006; Chen *et al.*, 2015). Because this

species was the third most abundant in this research, it is imperative that aquatic products from Lake Cajititlán undergo proper food safety inspection before consumption (Fig. 25). Previous research shows that the pathogenicity of *A. veronii* in fish is multifactorial. In this study, seven important virulence genes (*aer*, *act*, *aha*, *ser*, *exu*, *lip*, and *luxS*) were detected (Fig. 26; Li *et al.*, 2020). These findings are consistent with an investigation conducted in China, where 203 freshwater fish were collected, and 87 strains of *A. veronii* isolated, 50% of which carried at least four or more of the virulence genes evaluated in this work (Li *et al.*, 2020). These results are of great importance for future decision-making with the objective of conserving the ecosystem as well as the food safety of aquatic products from Lake Cajititlán. The infection process of *P. fluorescens*, *S. maltophilia*, *A. veronii* and other pathogenic microorganisms, together with stressful factors for the fish, could be the cause of the massive kill events that have been reported at this reservoir (Towsend *et al.*, 1992; Glibert *et al.*, 2001; Kangur *et al.*, 2005). However, toxicological and pathological analyses in fish and proteomic analyses are required to determine whether the genes detected in this study are being expressed. Previous studies of Lake Cajititlán evaluated the 16S rRNA gene at the genus level and made theoretical inferences about which species of pathogenic bacteria could be present according to the genera found (Díaz-Torres *et al.*, 2021, 2022). In the present research, use of the shotgun sequencing approach allowed for the characterization of bacteria in this reservoir at the species level, enabling the identification of previously described species, as can be observed in the chord diagram (Fig. 25).

E.4. Microbial community biological functions in association to biogeochemical cycles

Significant temporal changes in several pathways of nitrogen, phosphorus, and sulfur metabolism were observed in this study (Fig. 27C). Regarding nitrogen metabolism, the *narGHI*, *napAB*, and *nirK* genes were the most abundant in the denitrification pathway, which intensified in July (Fig. 28A). The first step of the denitrification pathway (NO_3^- to NO_2^-) is governed by the first two genes (*narGHI* and *napAB*). The second step (NO_2^- to NO) is mainly regulated by *nirK*, because its abundance was higher than *nirS*. The third step (NO to N_2O) is controlled by *norBC* and the last step (N_2O to N_2) by *nosZ*. However, this last gene was more abundant in August and its lowest abundance was observed in September (Fig. 28A and 28B). This might imply that each stage of this metabolic pathway does not occur sequentially (Howarth *et al.*, 2011). On the other

hand, anaerobic conditions with DO values less than 1.7 mg/L are required for nitrogen removal, and thus for conventional biological denitrification (Daigger, 2014). In this study, DO values lower than required were reported at different sites and sampling depths, mainly in April and May (Table 35). However, it is well known that the DO in eutrophic water bodies reaches its peak during the day due to the accelerated photosynthetic process carried out by the excessive amount of phytoplankton (monitoring time of this study 8:00-13:00), and it is depleted during the night, attributed to the respiration metabolism, and perhaps as a result, the genes of microorganisms capable of denitrification are present (Smith and Schindler, 2009; Fig. 27C and 28A). On the other hand, these results also suggest that facultative anaerobic microorganisms capable of performing complete denitrification, such as *P. aeruginosa*, *P. fluorescens*, *P. stutzeri*, and *P. denitrificans*, could carry out the denitrification process at higher concentrations of DO, as demonstrated in a previous study, in which the authors showed that *P. stutzeri* isolated from a wastewater treatment system, can carry out nitrification and denitrification simultaneously in the presence of high levels of oxygen (bottles containing an atmosphere of 92% oxygen; Su *et al.*, 2001; Arat *et al.*, 2015; Liou and Madsen, 2008; Tang *et al.*, 2020). This information coincides with the fact that *Pseudomonas* was the most abundant genus in this study (Fig. 27C). In addition, the genes (*narGHI*, *norBC*, *napAB*, *nirK*, *nirS*, *nosZ*) involved in the denitrification process were found annotated in the species *P. fluorescens*, *P. stutzeri*, and *P. aeruginosa*; this information suggests that it is worth investigating more about facultative anaerobic microorganisms in water ecosystems since it could be very useful for water remediation processes.

Table 35. Water dissolved oxygen concentrations (DO) of Lake Cajititlán by sampling depth from March to September 2018. Bold letters indicate a value \leq to 1.7 mg/L of DO, which is required for the nitrogen removal process to occur (Daigger, 2014).

Sampling point	Sampling Depth	March	April	May	June	July	August	September
CEA-01	0.8	6.74	10.16	8.05	4.58	4.24	3.81	7.69
	1	8	10.04		2.57			
	2	4.7	1.54	1.07	2.27	2.51	2.92	6.8
CEA-02	0.8	15	9.36	16.8	7.75	2.58	8.17	5.74
	1.5	7.7	1.65	2.59	4.93	2.21	2.85	3.71

	3.4	5.55	0.82	0.8	3.68	2.66	2.16	3.02
CEA-03	0.8	10	4.01	6.76	7.16	3.04	2.64	3.07
	2	5.95	1.68	2.36	4.78	2.32	2.08	2.63
	4.2	3.1	1.17	0.85	3.22	2.09	1.83	1.95
CEA-04	0.8	5.44	3.83	8.61	9.93	3.14	2.63	3.69
	1.5	4.22	2.2	1.89	7.72	2.33	1.98	3.4
	3.2	2.82	1.67	0.95	4.36	2.85	1.7	3.3
CEA-05	0.8	4.64	6.73	8.42	12.81	2.98	4.61	3.7
			3.4	1.94	11.89	2.14	2.91	3.3
	2.3	2.1	1.18	0.9	11.22	2.18	1.82	4.28

The denitrification process, as well as the anammox, are important in the removal of nitrogen from aquatic ecosystems. However, the anammox pathway showed no temporal variations and was substantially less abundant than the denitrification process (Ward *et al.*, 2009; Bernhard, 2010). Therefore, these results suggest that denitrification is the most important nitrogen removal mechanism in Lake Cajititlán, as previously suggested by Díaz-Torres *et al.* (2022) using the PICRUSt functional inference approach.

Similar to the denitrification pathway, all genes involved in comammox metabolism were found to be more abundant in July (Fig. 27C and 28A). Because this pathway involves the direct conversion of NH_3 into NO_3^- by a single *Nitrospira* bacterium, also known as comammox *Nitrospira*, these results correspond to the greatest NH_4^+ levels shown in July compared to the other months (Lawson and Lückner, 2018). Comammox bacteria are distinguished from other canonical nitrifiers due to their unique metabolic mechanism (Palomo *et al.*, 2018; Annavajhala *et al.*, 2018). While this genus was not classified as the most abundant bacteria in this study, its presence was identified in the metadata, and it became more abundant in July. Furthermore, the genes involved in the comammox process (*pmoABC-amoABC*, *hao*, *narGH*) were found to be annotated in the phylum Nitrospirae, indicating that this bacterium may be carrying out this metabolism in Lake Cajititlán.

A greater relative read abundance of DNRA-associated genes was identified throughout the research compared to other nitrogen pathways (Fig. 27C), indicating that microbial communities in the water column had a sustained capability to convert NO_3^- to NH_3 . A greater abundance of all the genes (*narGHI*, *napAB*, *nirBD*, and *nrfAH*) involved in this metabolic pathway was observed in July, similar to the ANRA pathway. Although the final product of both pathways is the same, ANRA is produced under aerobic conditions when reduced nitrogen is limited, and DNRA occurs when oxygen is limited (anaerobic conditions) and their respective reduced products (NH_4^+ and $\text{N}_2 + \text{N}_2\text{O}$, respectively) are produced in greater amounts (Teje *et al.*, 1981; Henson *et al.*, 2017). Based on the OD measurements (Table 26), the genes of the DNRA pathway are more functional in Lake Cajititlán than the genes of ANRA (Fig. 27C). This suggests that the massive bloom of phytoplankton in Lake Cajititlán is mostly attributable to the use of nitrogen from chemical fertilizers that reach this reservoir through surface drag, rather than a symbiotic interaction with atmospheric nitrogen-fixing bacteria (Aasfar *et al.*, 2021).

Nitrification is an aerobic nitrogen oxidation pathway that produces NO_3^- from NH_3 (EPA, 2002). This pathway was the least abundant in the sampled months (Fig. 27C), which might be due to the *Nitrospira* species enhancing comammox metabolism more than other nitrifying bacteria conducting nitrification; although *Nitrospira* bacteria participate in the nitrification pathway, the whole genetic repertory for ammonia and nitrate oxidation (*pmoABC-amoABC*), hydroxylamine (*hao*), and nitrate oxidoreductase (*narGH*) are required for comammox metabolism (Camejo *et al.*, 2017; Palomo *et al.*, 2018). According to genes associated with nitrification metabolism (*hao*, *amoCAB*, *nrxAB*), these were more abundant in July, as were the other nitrogen pathways (Fig. 28A). Nitrifying bacteria include species of genera such as *Nitrosomonas*, *Nitrosococcus*, *Nitrobacter*, *Nitrosolobus*, *Nitrosovibrio*, *Nitrospina*, *Nitrospira*, and *Nitrococcus* (Hagopian and Riley, 1998). In this study, only the *Nitrobacter* and *Nitrospira* genera were detected in the database; the set of read abundance from these two genera was more abundant in July, followed by September and August, which corresponds with the dynamics of this metabolism (Fig. 28A).

All phosphorus metabolic pathways were more abundant in July than in August and September (Ren *et al.*, 2019). The most abundant pathway was organic OPM, followed by IPS-PUT, and PSRR (Fig. 27D). Temporal changes were only detected in genes implicated in the OPM pathway

(*phoAD*, *upgQ*, *appA*, and *phn*). The increased representation of these genes in July suggests an increase in the P concentration of the water. However, phosphates were not measured in this study, which is how microorganisms and plants utilize P, and no temporal variations were observed for TP (Table 1; Karl, 2000). All genes, except for *phn*, were more abundant in July. The highest abundance of *phn*, which codes for phosphonoacetate hydrolase and is involved in the pathway's final step, was observed in August (Fig. 28A and B). The *phn* gene was more abundant in August, which indicates that there could be a greater organic P mineralization during that month. All the genes involved in the OPM pathway had the lowest abundance in September, which might imply that there was less phosphorus available for the microbial communities in this reservoir.

Regarding sulfur metabolism, the genes associated with the ASR pathway were more abundant than the genes of other metabolic pathways (Fig. 27A). Fungi, prokaryotes, and photosynthetic organisms use ASR to convert inorganic SO_4^{2-} to S_2^- , which is then incorporated into amino acid carbon skeletons to produce Cys or homo-Cys (Brunold, 1993). This process occurs in both anaerobic and aerobic conditions and has advantages over the DSR pathway, which only occurs in anaerobic environments (Kushkevych *et al.*, 2020). These findings suggest that the ASR pathway was the most abundant in this study due to the capacity of facultative anaerobic microbes to function both in the presence of DO (i.e., on the surface of Lake Cajititlán), as well as at low DO concentrations (near the sediments of the lake). However, only the SOX system pathway displayed significant temporal variations (Fig. 27A). This system, which is present in many sulfur oxidizing bacteria and certain archaea, completely oxidizes reduced sulfur (S) species to SO_4^{2-} (Quentmeier and Friedrich, 2001; Sauvé *et al.*, 2007; Grabarczyk *et al.*, 2015). The heatmap data shows that all the genes involved in the SOX system pathway were more abundant in July, except for the *soxZ* gene, which was most abundant in September (Fig. 28A). Microbial redox reactions of inorganic sulfur compounds are one of the vital processes responsible for the environmental balance of sulfur, mainly sulfur anions. These reactions are mostly mediated by alpha-Proteobacteria sulfur oxidizing (*sox*) genes. *SoxZ* is a sulfur compound chelating protein that binds to *soxY* and forms a complex with *soxB*, a sulfate thiolesterase, eventually cleaving the sulfur adduct (Bagchi and Ghosh, 2005). As a result, our findings show that the involvement of

the sulfur genes is critical since crucial unions are formed to produce the ultimate product, thiosulfate.

Although there were no temporal differences in the carbon cycle pathways, carbohydrate metabolism was the most abundant (Fig. 27B). Surface runoff and untreated or partially treated wastewater discharged into Lake Cajititlán by three treatment plants provide an important source of energy for the reservoir's microbial communities. Furthermore, organic matter pollution increases during the rainy season when wastewater mixes with rain and when treatment plants are over capacity, releasing a mixture of sewage and rainwater into the lake (de Anda *et al.*, 2019; Gradilla-Hernández *et al.*, 2019).

F. Conclusions

This research discusses the interactions between abiotic and biotic elements of a subtropical and hypereutrophic lake. Most physicochemical variables (DO, pH, Secchi disk, NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , BGA-PC, TP, and chlorophyll-*a*) were outside of the permissible limits. Likewise, significant temporal variations were observed for most of the physicochemical parameters (DO, pH, WT, Secchi disk, ORP, NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , BGA-PC, chlorophyll-*a*, and EC). These abiotic factors influence the structure of microbial communities, as well as the major nutrient-associated biogeochemical cycles of Lake Cajititlán. The most abundant phytoplankton species identified were *Planktothrix agardhii* and *Microcystis aeruginosa*, both of which are potentially toxic to fish due to their capacity to produce microcystins. *Pseudomonas*, *Streptomyces*, and *Flavobacterium* were the most abundant bacterial genera. *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, and *Aeromonas veronii* were the most abundant bacterial species reported as harmful to fish, and some of their genes (*fur*, *luxS*, *aer*, *act*, *aha*, *exu*, *lip*, *ser*) are associated with fish infection. The physicochemical factors most associated with the prevalence of phytoplankton and bacterial communities were NH_4^+ , TP, TN, ORP, DO, EC, BGA-PC, and turbidity. The genes associated with carbohydrate metabolism, CFPP, DNRA, denitrification, IPS-PUT, OPM, and ASR were found in greater abundance in the microbial communities. Denitrification, comammox, DNRA, ANRA, nitrification, the SOX system, and OPM were the metabolic pathways that displayed significant temporal variations. The genetic evidence presented in this study suggests that the genes for the metabolism of nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and carbon were regulated by

anthropogenic nutrient sources reaching Lake Cajititlán, since all metabolic pathways were more abundant in July. This was presumably induced by surface drags produced by rainfall and/or organic matter that enters the lake through the effluents of the WWTPs. Alterations in the biogeochemical cycles have endangered the biodiversity of Lake Cajititlán in recent years. Additional research, such as genome-wide transcriptional profiling of the bacteria directly involved in biogeochemical cycles and associated proteomic analyses, might aid in elucidating the connection between gene transcript abundance, enzyme activity, and its regulation by different nutrient sources. This, in turn, will contribute to a better understanding of the metabolic and ecological niches of microbial communities in aquatic environments.

GENERAL CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

General conclusions and perspectives

We have analyzed the response of microbial communities to variations in water quality and physicochemical conditions during the rainy season in a subtropical and hypereutrophic lake. Our results show that the composition and abundance of the microbial communities of Lake Cajititlán change rapidly and temporally. These variations resulted from the rainy season, which causes high seasonal surface runoff and thus alterations in water quality (DO, Chlorophyll-*a*, NH₄⁺, NO₃⁻, ORP, turbidity, TN, and EC). Therefore, abiotic, and biotic parameters are critical indicators for observing changes and successional stages of subtropical lakes during the rainy season.

Within the cyanobacterial community using the 16S rRNA gene targeting metagenomics, *Planktothrix* and *Cylindrospermopsis* were found to be the dominant genera of the cyanobacterial community, while the classes Chlorophyceae, Chrysophyceae, and Trebouxiophyceae were the most abundant within the microalgae community using the 18S rRNA gene. The most abundant bacteria genera found were *Flavobacterium* and *Pseudomonas* (16S rRNA gene). While using shotgun metagenomics, the most abundant phytoplankton species were *Planktothrix agardhii* and *Microcystis aeruginosa*, the bacterial genera were *Pseudomonas*, *Streptomyces* and *Flavobacterium*, and the most abundant bacterial species were *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* and *Aeromonas veronii*. The most abundant phytoplankton species detected are potentially toxic to fish because they can produce microcystins. Such toxins were detected in this body of water and ranged between 0.210 and 0.880 µg L⁻¹. Pathological and/or culture-dependent studies of the fish were not carried out to determine the causes of death; therefore, these toxins could not be associated with their mortality. Consistent with the results of targeted metagenomics (16S and 18S rRNA genes) and shotgun metagenomics allowed further exploration of the taxonomic microbial diversity of Lake Cajititlán.

In this study, most of the physicochemical factors (DO, pH, Secchi disk, NH₄⁺, NO₃⁻, BGA-PC, chlorophyll-*a*, and TP) were outside the permissible limit according to different national standards and international recommendations in water quality for water bodies, in the same way, the parameters (TP, DO, pH and WT) that ensure the protection of aquatic life in freshwater

bodies analyzed did not meet the permissible limits according to the Federal Law of Rights during the rainy season. As a result, these findings imply that high levels of physicochemical parameters may be affecting Lake Cajititlán's aquatic life, which is particularly concerning because the reservoir's main activity is commercial fishing as well as recreational boat trips on weekends, implying an impact on the local economy, i.e., loss of tourism, aesthetic value, fisheries, and seriously affecting the food web dynamics and nutrient balance. On the other hand, the low DO levels detected indicate that the death of fish in Lake Cajititlán could be mainly related to anoxia due to the massive blooms of phytoplankton observed in this reservoir.

Using the PICRUSt2 functional inference method, bacterial communities from Lake Cajititlán showed a higher relative abundance of genes associated with denitrification, nitrogen fixation, ASR, cysteine, the SOX system, and all phosphorus pathways. Genes linked with carbohydrate metabolism, CFPP, DNRA, denitrification, IPS-PUT, OPM, and ASR were more abundant in microbial communities using the shotgun sequencing approach. The genetic evidence presented in this thesis reveals that anthropogenic sources of nutrients that reached Lake Cajititlán, mainly during the beginning of the rainy season, regulated genes involved in nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and carbon metabolism. This was attributed to the fact that all metabolic pathways were more abundant in July (PICRUSt2 and Shotgun metagenomic), which was induced by surface runoff caused by rain and/or organic matter entering the lake via WWTPs effluents. The PICRUSt2 functional inference approach has several limitations since the data used for the analysis are partial 16S rRNA gene sequences. Therefore, contributions from eukaryotes, viruses, and archaea are not predicted as the shotgun metagenomic analysis does. Thus, the functional differences observed about biogeochemical cycles imply that shotgun sequencing enabled exhaustive analysis of the genes of all the microbial communities present in the samples of Lake Cajititlán, and a greater exploration of the metabolic mechanisms of these communities. Alterations in biogeochemical cycles increase the vulnerability of biodiversity, food security, human health, and water quality, which could also be involved in the massive fish kills in Lake Cajititlán in recent years.

Further research, such as genome-wide transcriptional profiling of bacteria directly involved in biogeochemical cycles and associated proteomic analyses, could help elucidate the connection

between gene transcript abundance, enzyme activity, and its regulation by different sources of enzymes and nutrients. This, in turn, will contribute to a better understanding of microbial communities' metabolic and ecological niches in aquatic environments.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations

WWTPs: Wastewater treatment plants

PICRUST: Phylogenetic investigation of communities by reconstruction of unobserved states

FCI: Compactness index

Rc: Circularity ratio

HAB: Harmful algal bloom

MC: Microcystins

TDI: Tolerable daily intake

NPLD: Nepten liver disease

DO: Dissolved oxygen

TN: Total nitrogen

TP: Total phosphorus

WT: Water temperature

EC: Electrical conductivity

AT: Air temperature

PREC: Precipitation

EV: Evaporation

ES-WQI: Ecosystem-specific water quality index

KEGG: Kyoto encyclopedia of genes and genomes

KO: KEGG orthology

HTS: High throughput sequencing

NGS: Next generation sequencing

QIIME: Quantitative insights into microbial ecology

ASVs: Amplicon sequence variants

CONAGUA: National water commission

CEA: State water commission

PCoA: Principal coordinate analysis

PerMANOVA: Permutational multivariate analysis

ANOVA: Analysis of variance

ANOSIM: Analysis of similarity

RDA: Redundancy analysis
ADONIS: Permutational multivariate analysis of variance using distance matrices
ELISA: Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay
PE: Red-pigmented phycoerythrin
PC: Phycocyanin
ANRA: Assimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonia
DNRA: Dissimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonia
SOX system: Sulfur oxidation system
CFPP: Carbon fixation pathways in prokaryotes
CFPO: Carbon fixation in photosynthetic organisms
OPM: Organic phosphorus mineralization
PSRR: Phosphorus starvation response regulation
PUT: Phosphorus uptake transport
IPS: Inorganic phosphorus solubilization
ASR: Assimilatory sulfate reduction
DSR: Dissimilatory sulfate reduction
SRB: Sulfate reducing bacteria
IPS-PUT: Inorganic phosphorus solubilization and phosphorus uptake
luxS: S-rubosylhomocysteinase
aer: Aerolysin
aha: Adhesin
exu: Dnases
lip: Lipase
ser: serine protease
act: Cytotoxic enterotoxin

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data availability statement

Sequencing experiments were uploaded to the NCBI Sequence Read Archive under the following accession numbers:

16S rRNA gene sequences: PRJNA626359

18S rRNA gene sequences: PRJNA626364

Shotgun sequencing: PRJNA851822

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